

Universal Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 17 to 32 With Digits 2 and 5

Inder J. Taneja¹

The whole work is without use of any programming language.

Abstract

This work brings universal magic squares of order 17 to 32. By universal we understand that the magic squares are upside-down and mirror looking independent of magic square sums. The work is for two digits as {2,5}. For the digits {1,8} and {6,9}, the work is given in [39] and [40] respectively. It can easily be extended for the digits {0,1} and {0,8}. Similar kind of work for the orders 3-16 can be seen in [38]. The block-wise constructions for the magic squares of orders 18, 20, 21, 24, 25, 27, 28, 30 and 32 are also included. Moreover, in case of orders 25 and 32, we have bimagic squares, while for the case of order 24 the semi-bimagic square. The whole work is without use of any programming language. It is just based on the number's combinations.

Contents

1	Introduction	3
2	Universal Magic Squares With Digits 2 and 5	3
2.1	Magic Square of Order 17	4
2.2	Magic Square of Order 18	6
2.2.1	Blocks of Order 6	6

¹Formerly, Professor of Mathematics, Federal University of Santa Catarina, Florianópolis, SC, Brazil (1978-2012). Also worked at Delhi University, India (1976-1978).

E-mail: ijthaneja@gmail.com;

Web-sites: <https://inderjtaneja.com>; <https://indertaneja.com>;

Twitter: @IJTANEJA; **Instagram:** @crazynumbers.

2.3	Magic Square of Order 19	9
2.4	Magic Square of Order 20	12
2.4.1	Blocks of Order 4	12
2.4.2	Blocks of Order 5	15
2.5	Magic Square of Order 21	17
2.5.1	Without Block	17
2.5.2	Block of Order 7	20
2.5.3	Block of Order 3	22
2.6	Magic Square of Order 22	24
2.7	Magic Square of Order 23	27
2.8	Magic Square of Order 24	30
2.8.1	Blocks of Order 6	30
2.8.2	Blocks of Order 4	34
2.8.3	Blocks of Order 12	36
2.8.4	Semi-bimagic Square	39
2.9	Magic Square of Order 25	44
2.9.1	Magic Square	44
2.9.2	Bimagic Square	47
2.10	Magic Square of Order 26	52
2.11	Magic Square of Order 27	56
2.11.1	Without Block	56
2.11.2	Block of Order 9	60
2.12	Magic Square of Order 28	64
2.12.1	Blocks of Order 4	64
2.12.2	Blocks of Order 7	68
2.13	Magic Square of Order 29	71
2.14	Magic Square of Order 30	74
2.14.1	Blocks of Order 6	74
2.14.2	Blocks of Order 5	78
2.15	Magic Square of Order 31	82
2.16	Magic Square of Order 32	86
2.16.1	Blocks of Order 4	86

2.16.2 Bimagic Square	92
3 Final Comments	98
4 Appendix	99
5 Author’s Contributions to Magic Squares	109
1 Introduction	

In the previous paper [38], author worked with three groups together for the magic squares of orders 3 to 16. In each group there are only two digits, i.e., $\{1, 8\}$, $\{2, 5\}$ and $\{6, 9\}$. In the first and second case we have results as **upside-down** and **mirror looking**, while the third case for the digits $\{6, 9\}$ the results are **upside-down**. In the second group with the digits $\{2, 5\}$, the numbers are written in digital form to have the conditions of **upside-down** and **mirror looking**. In some cases **palindromic-type magic squares** are also written. For more details refer Author’s work [38].

The whole work is based on combination of two digits. For example 2-digits combinations of two letters a and b give us 4 possibilities, i.e., aa, ab, ba, bb . In the similar way considering two letters 3 by 3 combinations, there are 8 possibilities, i.e., $aaa, aab, aac, abb, acc, abc, bbb, ccc$. Complete details of these type of combinations is given in the end in Appendix 4.

This work is for the magic squares of orders 17 to 32 only using the $\{2, 5\}$ written in digital form. In case of upside-down these two numbers remains the same, while in case of mirror looking 2 becomes 5 and 5 as 2. The work for the digits $\{1, 8\}$ and $\{6, 9\}$ refer [39, 40]. In some cases **block-wise** constructions are also given. These are for the magic squares of orders 18, 20, 21, 24, 25, 27, 28, 30 and 32. All the magic squares are constructed in this work are **universal magic squares** i.e., **upside-down** and **mirror looking** independent of magic sums. The study of magic squares of orders 33 to 64, and then from 65 to 128 shall be given in another works.

2 Universal Magic Squares With Digits 2 and 5

In the previous paper [38], we worked 2 by 2 combination of numbers in different ways. For example, in case of magic squares of orders 3 and 4, we worked with 2-digits combinations. In case of orders 5 to 8 we worked with 3-digits combinations. In case of orders 9 to 16, we worked with 4-digits combinations. In this work, we

shall work with 5-digits combinations resulting in magic squares of order 17 to 32 except the cases of **semi-bimagic** and **bimagic squares** of orders 24, 25 and 32. The whole work is without use of any **programming language**. It is just with number's combinations.

2.1 Magic Square of Order 17

Example 2.1. *The pandiagonal universal magic square of order 17 for the digits 2 and 5 written in digital form is given below in two parts:*

17x17	pan	64747447468	64747447468	64747447468	64747447468	64747447468	64747447468	64747447468	64747447468
	2225222252	2225555555	2252255522	2255555222	2522252225	2525225555	2555225252	2555522555	5222222255
64747447468	5555522255	2222522225	2225255552	2225555255	2252252525	2255552222	2522225552	2525225222	2555222522
64747447468	5552222522	5555222252	5555555555	2222555522	2225255222	2225552225	2252225555	2255525252	2522222555
64747447468	5522222555	5525522255	5522222225	5555255552	5555555255	2222552525	2225252222	2225525552	2252225222
64747447468	5222525222	5252522522	5522222252	5525555555	5552255522	5555255222	5555522225	2222525555	2225225252
64747447468	2555525252	5222222555	5222522255	5252522225	5522255552	5525555255	5552252525	5555252222	5555255552
64747447468	2525225552	2555225222	2555522522	5222222252	5222555555	5252555522	5522255222	5525552225	5522255555
64747447468	2255525555	2522225252	2525222555	2555222255	2555522225	5222255552	5222555255	5252552525	5522252222
64747447468	2225552222	2252225552	2255525222	2522222522	2525222252	2555255555	2555555522	5222255222	5222552225
64747447468	2222552225	2225225555	2225525252	2252222555	2255522255	2522222225	2525255552	2555255255	2555552525
64747447468	5555252525	5555552222	2222525552	2225225222	2225522522	2252222252	2255555555	2522255522	2525255222
64747447468	5525555222	5552252225	5555225555	5555525252	2222522555	2225222255	2225522225	2252255552	2255555255
64747447468	5252555255	5522252525	5525552222	5552225552	5555225222	5555522522	2222522252	2225255555	2225555522
64747447468	5222255522	5222555222	5252552225	5522225555	5525525252	5552222555	5555222255	5555522225	2222555552
64747447468	2555255552	2555555255	5222252525	5222552222	5252525552	5522225222	5525522522	5552222252	5555255555
64747447468	2522255555	2525255522	2555255222	2555552225	5222225555	5222525252	5252522555	5522222255	5525522225
64747447468	2252222225	2255555552	2522255255	2525252525	2555252222	2555525552	5222225222	5222522522	5252522252
	64747447468	64747447468	64747447468	64747447468	64747447468	64747447468	64747447468	64747447468	64747447468
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9

64747447468	64747447468	64747447468	64747447468	64747447468	64747447468	64747447468	64747447468	64747447468
5222522225	5252555552	5522255255	5525552525	5552252222	5555225552	5555252222	2222522522	64747447468
2555522252	5222255555	5222555522	5252555222	5522252225	5525525555	5552225252	5555222555	64747447468
2525222255	2555222225	2555555552	5222255255	5222552525	5252552222	5522225552	5525525222	64747447468
2255522522	2522222252	2525255555	2555255522	2555555222	5222252225	5222525555	5252525252	64747447468
2225522555	2252222255	2255522225	2522255552	2525255255	2555252525	2555552222	5222225552	64747447468
2222525222	2225222522	2225522252	2252255555	2255555522	2522255222	2525252225	2555225555	64747447468
5555225252	5555522555	2222522255	2225222225	2225555552	2252255255	2255552525	2522252222	64747447468
5525525552	5552225222	5555222522	5555522252	2222555555	2225255522	2225555222	2252252225	64747447468
5252525555	5522225252	5525522555	5552222255	5555222225	5555555552	2222555255	2225252525	64747447468
5222252222	5222525552	5252525222	5522222522	5525522252	5552255555	5555255522	5555555222	64747447468
2555252225	2555525555	5222225252	5222522555	5252522255	5522222225	5525555552	5552255255	64747447468
2522252525	2525252222	2555225552	2555525222	5222222522	5222522252	5252555555	5522255522	64747447468
2252255222	2255552225	2522225555	2525225252	2555222555	2555522255	5222222225	5222555552	64747447468
2225255255	2225552525	2252252222	2255525552	2522225222	2525222522	2555222252	2555555555	64747447468
5555555522	2222555222	2225252225	2225525555	2252225252	2255522555	2522222255	2525222225	64747447468
5552255552	5555255255	5555552525	2222552222	2225225552	2225525222	2252222522	2255522252	64747447468
5522255555	5525555522	5552255222	5555252225	5555525555	2222525252	2225222555	2225522255	64747447468
64747447468	64747447468	64747447468	64747447468	64747447468	64747447468	64747447468	64747447468	64747447468
10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	

The magic square given in Example 2.1 is constructed based on 2 by 2 combinations of following 17 numbers:

$$\{22225, 22252, 22255, 22522, 22555, 25222, 25252, 25552, 25555, 52222, 52225, 52525, 55222, 55255, 55522, 55552, 55555\}$$

Let's check the sum of these numbers in three situations:

Numbers used:

$$647468 := 22225 + 22252 + 22255 + 22522 + 22555 + 25222 + 25252 + 25552 + 25555 + \\ + 52222 + 52225 + 52525 + 55222 + 55255 + 55522 + 55552 + 55555$$

Upside-down:

$$647468 := 52222 + 25222 + 55222 + 22522 + 55522 + 22252 + 25252 + 25552 + 55552 + \\ + 22225 + 52225 + 52525 + 22255 + 55255 + 22555 + 25555 + 55555$$

Mirror looking:

$$674741 := 25555 + 52555 + 22555 + 55255 + 22255 + 55525 + 52525 + 52225 + 22225 + \\ + 55552 + 25552 + 25252 + 55522 + 22522 + 55222 + 52222 + 22222$$

Using 2 by 2 combinations of these 17 numbers, the **magic sums** are given by

$$S_{17 \times 17} := 64747447468 = 100000 \times 647468 + 647468 \quad (1)$$

and

$$S_{17 \times 17} := 67474774741 = 100000 \times 674741 + 674741 \quad (2)$$

The **original magic square** and **upside-down** cases, the **magic sums** are same as given in (1). In case of **mirror looking**, the **magic sum** is as given in (2). Even though the **magic sums** are different but the magic square given in Example 2.1 is a **universal magic square** of order 17.

2.2 Magic Square of Order 18

2.2.1 Blocks of Order 6

Example 2.2. *The universal magic square of order 18 for the digits 2 and 5 written in digital form is given below in two parts:*

mgc								
2522222252	5255555522	5255555222	5255522555	2522222255	2522255525	2222222222	5555555225	5555552255
5255255525	2522522255	5255255222	2522522555	2522555522	5255222252	5522555555	2255222552	5522552255
5225255525	5225255522	2552522555	2552555222	5225222255	2552522252	5225555555	5225555225	2552225522
2552555525	2552522255	5225222555	5225255222	2552555522	5225222252	2552255555	2552222552	5225525522
2522522252	5255222255	2522555222	5255222555	5255255522	2522555525	2255222222	5522522552	2255252255
5255522252	2522255522	2522222555	2522255222	5255522255	5255555525	5555522222	2222255225	2222225522
2225222222	5552555225	5552552255	5552525522	2225222552	2225255555	2522225222	5255552552	5255552252
5552255555	2225522552	5552252255	2225525522	2225555225	5552222222	5255252555	2522525225	5255252252
5522255555	5522255225	2255525522	2255552255	5522222552	2255522222	5225252555	5225252552	2552525525
2255555555	2255522552	5522225522	5522252255	2255555225	5522222222	2552552555	2552525225	5225225525
2225522222	5552222552	2225552255	5552225522	5552255225	2225555555	2522525222	5255225225	2522552252
5552522222	2225255225	2225225522	2225252255	5552522552	5552555555	5255525222	2522252552	2522225525
2222225222	5555552552	5555552252	5555525525	2222225225	2222252555	2225222252	5552555522	5552555222
5522552555	2255225225	5522552252	2255225525	2255252552	5522525222	5552255525	2225522255	5552255222
5225552555	5225552552	2552225525	2552252252	5225525225	2552225222	5522255525	5522255522	2255522555
2552252555	2552225225	5225525525	5225552252	2552252552	5225525222	2255555525	2255522255	5522222555
2255225222	5522525225	2255252252	5522525525	5522552552	2255252555	2225522252	5552222255	2225555222
5555525222	2222252552	2222225525	2222252252	5555525225	5555552555	5552522252	2225255522	2225222555
6999999993	6999999993	6999999993	6999999993	6999999993	6999999993	6999999993	6999999993	6999999993
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9

									6999999993
555525522	222222552	222255555	222522522	555255255	555255252	5552525525	2225225225	2225252555	6999999993
2255225522	2255255225	5522522222	5552252555	2225525225	5552252252	2225525525	2225552552	5552225222	6999999993
2552252255	5225522552	2552222222	5522252555	5522252552	2255525525	2255552252	5522225225	2255525222	6999999993
5225552255	2552255225	5225522222	2255552555	2255525225	5522225525	5522252252	2255552552	5522225222	6999999993
5522525522	5522555225	2255255555	2225525222	5552225225	2225552252	5552225525	5552252552	2225552555	6999999993
2222252255	5555522552	5555555555	5552525222	2225252552	2225225525	2225252252	5552525225	5552552555	6999999993
5255525525	2522225225	2522252555	2222222252	5555555522	5555555222	5555522555	2222222255	2222255525	6999999993
2522525525	2522552552	5255225222	5522555525	2255222255	5522555222	2255222555	2255255522	5522522252	6999999993
2552552252	5225225225	2552525222	5225555525	5225555522	2552222555	2552255222	5225522255	2552222252	6999999993
5225252252	2552552552	5225225222	2552255525	2552222255	5225522555	5225555222	2552255522	5225522252	6999999993
5255225525	5255252552	2522552555	2255222252	5522522255	2255255222	5522522555	5522555522	2255255525	6999999993
2522252252	5255525225	5255552555	5555522252	2222255522	2222222555	2222255222	5555522255	5555555525	6999999993
5552522555	2225222255	2225255525	2522222222	5255555225	5255552255	5255525522	2522222552	2522255555	6999999993
2225522555	2225555522	5552222252	5255255555	2522522552	5255252255	2522525522	2522555225	5255222222	6999999993
2255555222	5522222255	2255522252	5225255555	5225255225	2552525522	2552552255	5225222552	2552522222	6999999993
5522255222	2255555522	5522222252	2552555555	2552522552	5225225522	5225252255	2552555225	5225222222	6999999993
5552222555	5552255522	2225555525	2522522222	5255222552	2522552255	5255225522	5255255225	2522555555	6999999993
2225255222	5552522255	5552555525	5255522222	2522255225	2522225522	2522252255	5255522552	5255555555	6999999993
6999999993	6999999993	6999999993	6999999993	6999999993	6999999993	6999999993	6999999993	6999999993	6999999993
10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19

It is based on the 2 by 2 combinations of 18 numbers:

$$\{22222, 22225, 22252, 22255, 22522, 22555, 25252, 25552, 25555, 52222, 52225, 52525, 55222, 55255, 55522, 55525, 55552, 55555\}$$

Let's divide the above 18 numbers in three groups with **equal sums**:

$$A := 22222 + 55555 + 25252 + 52525 + 22555 + 55222 = 233331$$

$$B := 22522 + 55255 + 22225 + 55552 + 25555 + 52222 = 233331$$

$$C := 25552 + 52225 + 22255 + 55522 + 22252 + 55525 = 233331.$$

Let's check the sum of these numbers for **Upside-down** and **Mirror looking** cases:

Upside-down:

$$A := 22222 + 55555 + 25252 + 52525 + 55522 + 22255 = 233331$$

$$B := 22522 + 55255 + 52222 + 25555 + 55552 + 22225 = 233331$$

$$C := 25552 + 52225 + 55222 + 22555 + 25222 + 52555 = 233331$$

Mirror looking:

$$A := 55555 + 22222 + 52525 + 25252 + 22255 + 55522 = 233331$$

$$B := 55255 + 22522 + 25555 + 52222 + 22225 + 55552 = 233331$$

$$C := 52225 + 25552 + 22555 + 55222 + 52555 + 25222 = 233331.$$

We observe that in all the three situations the sum remains the same. Using 2 by 2 combinations of these 18 numbers, the magic sum is given by

$$S_{18 \times 18} := 69999999993 = 100000 \times 699993 + 699993, \quad (3)$$

where

$$699993 := 22222 + 22225 + 22252 + 22255 + 22522 + 22555 + 25252 + 25552 + 25555 + \\ + 52222 + 52225 + 52525 + 55222 + 55255 + 55522 + 55525 + 55552 + 55555.$$

Thus, we have a **block-wise universal magic square** of order 18 with magic sum given in (3), where each block of order 6 is a **universal magic square** with **magic sums** given by

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 23333333331 = 100000 \times 233331 + 233331. \quad (4)$$

2.3 Magic Square of Order 19

Example 2.3. *The pandiagonal universal magic square of order 19 for the digits 2 and 5 written in digital form is given below in two parts:*

	pan	72252222515	72252222515	72252222515	72252222515	72252222515	72252222515	72252222515	72252222515	72252222515
	2222522225	2225255552	2225555255	2252252525	2252552225	2255525555	2522225252	2525222555	2555222522	2555522252
72252222515	5555222252	5555555555	2222555522	2225255222	2225552522	2252252222	2252525552	2255525222	2522222525	2525222255
72252222515	5525522255	5552222225	5555255552	5555552555	2222552525	2225252225	2225525555	2252225252	2252522555	2255522522
72252222515	5252522522	5522222252	5525555555	5552255522	5555255222	5555552522	2222552222	2225225552	2225525222	2252222525
72252222515	5222522525	5252222255	5252522225	5522255552	5525552555	5552252525	5555252225	5555525555	2222525252	2225222555
72252222515	2555522555	5222222522	5222522252	5252255555	5252555522	5522255222	5525552522	5552252222	5555225552	5555525222
72252222515	2525225222	2555222525	2555522255	5222222225	5222555552	5252255255	5252552525	5522252225	5525525555	5552225252
72252222515	2255525252	2522222555	2525222522	2555222252	2555555555	5222255522	5222555222	5252252522	5252552222	5522225552
72252222515	2252225552	2252525222	2255522525	2522222255	2525222225	2555255552	2555552555	5222252525	5222552225	5252225555
72252222515	2225225555	2225525252	2252222555	2252522522	2255522252	2522255555	2525255522	2555255222	2555552522	5222252222
72252222515	5555552222	2222525552	2225225222	2225522525	2252222255	2252522225	2255555552	2522255255	2525252525	2555252225
72252222515	5552252225	5555225555	5555525252	2222522555	2225222522	2225522252	2252255555	2252555522	2255555222	2522252522
72252222515	5522252522	5525552222	5552225552	5555225222	5555522525	2222522255	2225222225	2225555552	2252255255	2252552525
72252222515	5252252525	5252552225	5522225555	5525525252	5552222555	5555222522	5555522252	2222555555	2225255522	2225555222
72252222515	5222255222	5222552522	5252252222	5252525552	5522225222	5525522525	5552222255	5555222225	5555555552	2222555255
72252222515	2555255255	2555552525	5222252225	5222525555	5252225252	5252522555	5522222522	5525522252	5552255555	5555255522
72252222515	2522255522	2525255222	2555252522	2555552222	5222225552	5222525222	5252222525	5252522255	5522222225	5525555552
72252222515	2252555552	2255552555	2522252525	2525252225	2555225555	2555525252	5222222555	5222522522	5252222252	5252555555
72252222515	2225555555	2252255522	2252555222	2255552522	2522252222	2525225552	2555225222	2555522525	5222222255	5222522225
	72252222515	72252222515	72252222515	72252222515	72252222515	72252222515	72252222515	72252222515	72252222515	72252222515
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10

72252222515	72252222515	72252222515	72252222515	72252222515	72252222515	72252222515	72252222515	72252222515	72252222515
5222255555	5222555522	5252255222	5252552522	5522252222	5525525552	5552225222	5555222525	555522255	72252222515
2555222225	2555555552	5222255255	5222552525	5252252225	5252525555	5522225252	5525522555	5552222522	72252222515
2522222252	2525255555	2555255522	2555555222	5222252522	5222552222	5252225552	5252525222	5522222525	72252222515
2252522255	2255522225	2522255552	2525255255	2555252525	2555552225	5222225555	5222525252	5252222555	72252222515
2225522522	2252222252	2252555555	2255555522	2522255222	2525252522	2555252222	2555525552	5222225222	72252222515
2222522525	2225222255	2225522225	2252255552	2252555255	2255552525	2522252225	2525225555	2555225252	72252222515
5555222555	5555522522	2222522252	2225255555	2225555522	2252255222	2252552522	2255552222	2522225552	72252222515
5525525222	5552222525	5555222255	5555522225	2222555552	2225255255	2225552525	2252252225	2252525555	72252222515
5252525252	5522222555	5525522522	5552222252	5555255555	5555555522	2222555222	2225252522	2225552222	72252222515
5222525552	5252225222	5252522525	5522222255	5525522225	5552255552	5555255255	5555552525	2222552225	72252222515
2555525555	5222225252	5222522555	5252222522	5252522252	5522255555	5525555522	5552255222	5555252522	72252222515
2525252222	2555225552	2555525222	5222222525	5222522255	5252222225	5252555552	5522255255	5525552525	72252222515
2255552225	2522225555	2525225252	2555222555	2555522522	5222222252	5222555555	5252255522	5252555222	72252222515
2252252522	2252552222	2255525552	2522225222	2525222525	2555222255	2555522225	5222255552	5222555255	72252222515
2225252525	2225552225	2252225555	2252525252	2255522555	2522222522	2525222252	2555255555	2555555522	72252222515
5555555222	2222552522	2225252222	2225525552	2252225222	2252522525	2255522255	2522222225	2525255552	72252222515
5552255255	5555252525	5555552225	2222525555	2225225252	2225522555	2252222522	2252522252	2255555555	72252222515
5522255522	5525555222	5552252522	5555252222	5555525552	2222525222	2225222525	2225522255	2252222225	72252222515
5252255552	5252555255	5522252525	5525552225	5552225555	5555225252	5555522555	2222522522	2225222252	72252222515
72252222515	72252222515	72252222515	72252222515	72252222515	72252222515	72252222515	72252222515	72252222515	72252222515
11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	

The magic square given in Example 2.3 is constructed based on 2 by 2 combination of following 19 numbers:

$$\{22225, 22252, 22255, 22522, 22525, 22555, 25222, 25252, 25552, 25555, 52222, 52225, 52522, 52525, 55222, 55255, 55522, 55552, 55555\}$$

Let's check the sum of these numbers in three situations:

Numbers used:

$$722515 := 22225 + 22252 + 22255 + 22522 + 22525 + 22555 + 25222 + 25252 + 25552 + 25555 + \\ + 52222 + 52225 + 52522 + 52525 + 55222 + 55255 + 55522 + 55552 + 55555$$

Upside-down:

$$722515 := 52222 + 25222 + 55222 + 22522 + 52522 + 55522 + 22252 + 25252 + 25552 + 55552 + \\ + 22225 + 52225 + 22525 + 52525 + 22255 + 55255 + 22555 + 25555 + 55555$$

Mirror looking:

$$755248 := 25555 + 52555 + 22555 + 55255 + 25255 + 22255 + 55525 + 52525 + 52225 + 22225 + \\ + 55552 + 25552 + 55252 + 25252 + 55522 + 22522 + 55222 + 52222 + 22222$$

Using 2 by 2 combinations of these 19 numbers, the **magic sums** are given by

$$S_{19 \times 19} := 72252222515 = 100000 \times 722515 + 722515 \quad (5)$$

and

$$S_{19 \times 19} := 75525555248 = 100000 \times 755248 + 755248. \quad (6)$$

The **original magic square** and **upside-down** cases, the **magic sums** are the same as given in (5). In case of **mirror looking**, the **magic sum** is as given in (6). Even though the **magic sums** are different but the magic square given in Example 2.3 is a **universal magic square** of order 19.

2.4 Magic Square of Order 20

2.4.1 Blocks of Order 4

Example 2.4. *The universal pandiagonal magic square of order 20 for the digits 2 and 5 written in digital form is given below in two parts:*

	pan	777777770	777777770	777777770	777777770	777777770	777777770	777777770	777777770	777777770
	225555222	552255522	2225522255	5552222555	2255552222	5522255552	2225522225	5552225555	2255552555	5522255525
777777770	2225522555	5552222255	2255555522	5522255222	2225525555	5552222225	2255555552	5522252222	2225525222	5552222252
777777770	5552255522	2225555222	5522222555	2255522255	5552255552	2225552222	5522225555	2255522225	5552255525	2225552555
777777770	5522222255	2255522555	5552255222	2225555522	5522222225	2255525555	5552252222	2225555552	5522222252	2255525222
777777770	255555222	5222255522	2222522255	5555222555	2555552222	5222255552	2222522225	5555225555	2555552555	5222255525
777777770	2222522555	5555222255	2555555522	5222255222	2222525555	5555222225	2555555552	5222252222	2222525222	5555222252
777777770	5555255522	2222555222	5222222555	2555522255	5555255552	2222552222	5222225555	2555522225	5555255525	2222552555
777777770	5222222255	2555522555	5555255222	2222555522	5222222225	2555525555	5555252222	2222555552	5222222252	2555525222
777777770	2522255222	5255555522	2225222255	5552522555	2522252222	5255555552	2225222225	5552525555	2522252555	5255555525
777777770	2225222555	5552522255	2522255522	5255555222	2225225555	5552522225	2522255552	5255552222	2225225222	5552522252
777777770	5552555522	2225255222	5255522555	2522222255	5552555552	2225252222	5255525555	2522222225	5552555525	2225252555
777777770	5255522255	2522222555	5552555222	2225255522	5255522225	2522225555	5552552222	2225255552	5255522252	2522225222
777777770	2525555222	5252255522	2252522255	5525222555	2525552222	5252255552	2252522225	5525225555	2525552555	5252255525
777777770	2252522555	5525222255	2525555522	5252255222	2252525555	5525222225	2525555552	5252252222	2252525222	5525222252
777777770	5525255522	2252555222	5252222555	2525522255	5525255552	2252552222	5252225555	2525522225	5525255525	2252552555
777777770	5252222255	2525522555	5525255222	2252555522	5252222225	2525525555	5525252222	2252555552	5252222252	2525525222
777777770	2552255222	5225555522	2255222255	5522522555	2552252222	5225555552	2255222225	5522525555	2552252555	5225555525
777777770	2255222555	5522522255	2552255522	5225555222	2255225555	5522522225	2552255552	5225552222	2255225222	5522522252
777777770	5522555522	2255255222	5225522555	2552222255	5522555552	2255252222	5225525555	2552222225	5522555525	2255252555
777777770	5225522255	2552222555	5522555222	2255255522	5225522225	2552225555	5522552222	2255255552	5225522252	2552225222
	777777770	777777770	777777770	777777770	777777770	777777770	777777770	777777770	777777770	777777770
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10

777777770	777777770	777777770	777777770	777777770	777777770	777777770	777777770	777777770	777777770	777777770
2225522252	5552225222	2255552522	5522255252	2225522525	5552225255	2255552255	5522255225	2225522552	5552225522	777777770
2255555525	5522252555	2225525255	5552222525	2255555252	5522252522	2225525522	5552222552	2255555225	5522252255	777777770
5522225222	2255522252	5552255252	2225552522	5522225255	2255522525	5552255225	2225552255	5522225522	2255522552	777777770
5552252555	2225555252	5522222525	2255525255	5552252522	2225555252	5522222552	2255525522	5552252255	2225555225	777777770
2222522252	5555225222	2555552522	5222255252	2222522525	5555225255	2555552255	5222255225	2222522552	5555225522	777777770
2555555525	5222252555	2222525255	5555222525	2555555252	5222252522	2222525522	5555222552	2555555225	5222252255	777777770
5222225222	2555522252	5555255252	2222552522	5222225255	2555522525	5555255225	2222552255	5222225522	2555522552	777777770
5555252555	2222555252	5222222525	2555525255	5555252522	2222555252	5222222552	2555525522	5555252255	2222555225	777777770
2225222252	5552525222	2522252522	5255555252	2225222525	5552525255	2522252255	5255555225	2225222552	5552525522	777777770
2522255525	5255552555	2225225255	5552522525	2522255252	5255552522	2225225522	5552522552	2522255225	5255552255	777777770
5255525222	2522222522	5552555252	2225252522	5255525255	2522222525	5552555225	2225252255	5255525522	2522222552	777777770
5552552555	2225255525	5255522525	2522225255	5552552522	2225255252	5255522552	2522225522	5552552255	2225255225	777777770
2252522252	5525225222	2525552522	5252255252	2252522525	5525225255	2525552255	5252255225	2252522552	5525225522	777777770
2525555525	5252252555	2252525255	5525222525	2525555252	5252252522	2252525522	5525222552	2525555225	5252252255	777777770
5252225222	2525522252	5525255252	2252552522	5252225255	2525522525	5525255225	2252552255	5252225522	2525522552	777777770
5525252555	2252555525	5252222525	2525525255	5525252522	2252555252	5252222552	2525525522	5525252255	2252555225	777777770
2255222252	5522525222	2552252522	5225555252	2255222525	5522525255	2552252255	5225555225	2255222552	5522525522	777777770
2552255525	5225552555	2255225255	5522522525	2552255252	5225552522	2255225522	5522522552	2552255225	5225552255	777777770
5225525222	2552222252	5522555252	2255252522	5225525255	2552222525	5522555225	2255252255	5225525522	2552222552	777777770
5522552555	2255255525	5225522525	2552225255	5522552522	2255255252	5225522552	2552225522	5522552255	2255255225	777777770
777777770	777777770	777777770	777777770	777777770	777777770	777777770	777777770	777777770	777777770	777777770
11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	

It is based on the 2 by 2 combinations of 20 numbers:

$$\{22255, 55222, 22555, 55522, 22225, 52222, 25555, 55552, 22252, 25222, 55525, 52555, 22525, 52522, 25255, 55252, 22552, 25522, 52255, 55225\}$$

Let's divide the above 20 numbers in five groups with four numbers each with **equal sums**:

$$A := 22255 + 55222 + 22555 + 55522 = 155554$$

$$B := 22225 + 52222 + 25555 + 55552 = 155554$$

$$C := 22252 + 25222 + 55525 + 52555 = 155554$$

$$D := 22525 + 52522 + 25255 + 55252 = 155554$$

$$E := 22552 + 25522 + 52255 + 55225 = 155554.$$

Let's check the sum of these numbers for **Upside-down** and **Mirror looking** cases:

Upside-down:

$$A := 55222 + 22255 + 55522 + 22555 = 155554$$

$$B := 52222 + 22225 + 55552 + 25555 = 155554$$

$$C := 25222 + 22252 + 52555 + 55525 = 155554$$

$$D := 52522 + 22525 + 55252 + 25255 = 155554$$

$$E := 25522 + 22552 + 55225 + 52255 = 155554$$

Mirror looking:

$$A := 22555 + 55522 + 22255 + 55222 = 155554$$

$$B := 25555 + 55552 + 22225 + 52222 = 155554$$

$$C := 52555 + 55525 + 25222 + 22252 = 155554$$

$$D := 25255 + 55252 + 22525 + 52522 = 155554$$

$$E := 52255 + 55225 + 22552 + 25522 = 155554$$

We observe that in all the three situations the sum remains the same. Using 2 by 2 combinations of these 20 numbers, the magic sum is given by

$$S_{20 \times 20} := 77777777770 = 100000 \times 777770 + 777770 \tag{7}$$

where

$$777770 := 22255 + 55222 + 22555 + 55522 + 22225 + 52222 + 25555 + 55552 + 22252 + 25222 + \\ + 55525 + 52555 + 22525 + 52522 + 25255 + 55252 + 22552 + 25522 + 52255 + 55225.$$

Thus, we have a **block-wise pandiagonal universal magic square** of order 20 with magic sum given in (7), where each block of order 4 is a **pandiagonal universal magic square** with equal **magic sums** given by

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 1555555554 = 100000 \times 155554 + 155554. \tag{8}$$

2.4.2 Blocks of Order 5

Example 2.5. *The universal magic square of order 20 for the digits 2 and 5 written in digital form is given below in two parts:*

20x20-mgc									
2222522225	2555555552	5222225555	5555225522	2552252222	2225222255	2522255522	5255522555	5552522552	5225555222
5555225555	2552225522	2222552222	2555522225	5222255552	5552522555	5225522552	2225255222	2522222255	5255555522
2555552222	5222222225	5555255552	2552225555	2222525522	2522255222	5255522255	5552555522	5225522555	2225222552
2552255552	2222525555	2555525522	5222252222	5555222225	5225555522	2225222555	2522222552	5255555222	5552522255
5222225522	5555252222	2552222225	2222555552	2555525555	5255522552	5552555222	5225522255	2225255522	2522222555
2225522252	2255555525	5522225222	5552252255	2255252555	2252522525	2525555252	5252225255	5525255225	5522552522
5552225222	2255252255	2225552555	2255522252	5522255525	5525225255	5522555225	2252552522	2525522525	5252255252
2255552555	5522222252	5552255525	2255225222	2225552255	2525552522	5252222525	5525255252	5522525255	2252555225
2255255525	2225525222	2255552255	5522252555	5552222252	5522555252	2252525255	2525555225	5252252522	5525222525
5522252255	5552252555	2255222252	2225555525	2255525222	5252255225	5525252522	5522522525	2252555252	2525525255
2252522255	2525555522	5252222555	5525222552	5522555222	2225522225	2255555552	5522225555	5552225522	2255252222
5525222555	5522522552	2252555222	2525522255	5252255522	5552225555	2255225522	2225552222	2255522225	5522255552
2525555222	5252222255	5525255522	5522522555	2252522552	2255552222	5522222225	5552255552	2255225555	2225525522
5522555522	2252522555	2525522552	5252255222	5525222255	2255255552	2225525555	2255525522	5522252222	5552222225
5252222552	5525255222	5522522255	2252555522	2525522555	5522225522	5552252222	2255222225	2225555552	2255525555
2225222525	2522255252	5255525255	5552555225	5225552522	2222522252	2555555525	5222225222	5555252255	2552252555
5552525255	5225555225	2225252522	2522222525	5255555252	5555225222	2552252255	2222552555	2555522252	5222255525
2522252522	5255522525	5552555252	5225525255	2225255225	2555552555	5222222252	5555255525	2552225222	2222552255
5225555252	2225225255	2522255225	5255552522	5552522525	2552255525	2222525222	2555552255	5222252555	5555222252
5255555225	5552552522	5225522525	2225255252	2522225255	5222252255	5555252555	2552222252	2222555525	2555525222
7777777770	7777777770	7777777770	7777777770	7777777770	7777777770	7777777770	7777777770	7777777770	7777777770
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10

										7777777770
222522525	225555252	552222525	555225225	225525252	22522252	252555525	525222522	552525255	552255255	7777777770
555222525	225525225	222555252	225552252	552225252	552522522	552255225	225255255	252552252	525225525	7777777770
225555252	552222525	555225252	225522525	222555225	252555255	525222252	552525525	552252222	225255225	7777777770
225525252	222552255	225555225	552225222	555222252	552255525	225252222	252555225	525225255	55222252	7777777770
552225225	555225222	225522252	222555252	225552255	525225225	552525255	552252222	225255525	252552222	7777777770
222252225	255555522	522222555	555522252	255225222	222522225	252225552	525525555	555252552	522555222	7777777770
555522255	255222252	222255522	255552225	522225552	555252555	522552552	222525222	252222225	525555552	7777777770
255555222	522222255	555525522	255222255	222252252	252225222	525552225	555255552	522552555	222522552	7777777770
255225522	222252255	255552252	522225222	555522225	522555552	222522555	252222552	525555222	555252225	7777777770
522222552	555525522	255222225	222255552	255552255	525552552	555255222	522552225	222525552	252222555	7777777770
222522225	252225552	525552222	555255225	522555255	222252252	255555252	522222525	555525522	255225252	7777777770
555252222	522555225	222525255	252222225	525555552	555522255	255225225	222255252	255552252	522225252	7777777770
252225255	525552225	555255525	522552222	222525225	255555252	522222252	555525522	255222255	222255225	7777777770
522555525	222522522	252225225	525555255	555252225	255225252	222252255	255555225	522225252	555522252	7777777770
525555225	555255255	522552225	222525525	252222522	522225225	555525252	255222252	222255525	255552255	7777777770
225222225	252555552	525222555	552522552	552255222	222552225	225555552	552222255	555222252	225525222	7777777770
552522555	552252552	225255222	252552225	525225552	555222255	225522252	222555222	225552225	552225552	7777777770
252555222	525222225	552525552	552252555	225252552	225555222	552222225	555225552	225522255	222552252	7777777770
552255552	225252555	252552552	525225222	552522225	225525552	222552255	225552252	552225222	555222225	7777777770
525222552	552525222	552252225	225255552	252552555	552222252	555225222	225522225	222555552	225552255	7777777770
7777777770	7777777770	7777777770	7777777770	7777777770	7777777770	7777777770	7777777770	7777777770	7777777770	7777777770
11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	

It is based on the 2 by 2 combinations of 20 numbers considered in Example 2.4. These 20 numbers are divided in 4 parts of 5 each with unequal sums. This lead us to a **block-wise universal magic square** of order 20 with the **magic sum** as given in (7). Each block of order 5 is a **pandiagonal magic square** of order 5 with different magic sums.

2.5 Magic Square of Order 21

2.5.1 Without Block

Example 2.6. *The universal magic square of order 21 for the digits 2 and 5 written in digital form is given below in two parts:*

21x21	mgc									
2222522225	5252522255	2252252525	2225522252	5552225522	5555252255	5555525555	5552552222	5255555522	5522555555	5525555525
2225552525	2225222252	2222522522	5252522225	5555522222	5552525555	5552252255	5555225522	5525555552	5522255525	5255555555
5252522522	2252222225	2225522255	2225252525	5552552255	5555525522	5555252222	5552225555	5522255555	5525555522	5522555552
2225222255	2222552525	5252522252	2252222522	5555225555	5552252222	5552525522	5555522255	5522555525	5255555552	5522255522
2552255522	5222255555	5225555525	2555555552	2255222552	5252525222	2525252525	2522222555	2222552555	2225555255	2252255222
5225555552	2555555525	2552255555	5222255522	2522252525	2255522555	2255225252	5252522552	2252255225	2225255222	2222555255
2555555555	5225555522	5222255552	2552255525	5252525252	2525222552	2522225222	2255552525	2225255255	2252252555	2225555225
5222255525	2552255552	2555555522	5225555555	2255525222	2255252525	5252522555	2525225252	2225555222	2222555225	2225252555
5552252555	5555255255	5555555222	5552555225	5255522225	5522522522	5525522252	5522222255	2552225522	5252552222	5225552525
5555555225	5552555222	5552255255	5555252555	5525522255	5522222252	5255522522	5522522225	5222252525	2555525555	2552252255
5552555255	5555552555	5555255225	5552255222	5522222522	5525522225	5522522255	5255522252	5252552255	5225525522	5222252222
5555255222	5552255225	5552552555	5555555255	5522522252	5255522255	5522222225	5525522522	2555552222	2552252525	5252525555
2252222252	2225522522	2225222225	2222522255	2525222555	2522225252	2255522552	2255225222	5225525555	5222252255	2555525522
2255225522	2522252255	2525225555	2255552222	2222555522	2225555555	2252255525	2225255552	5552222552	5555225252	5555522555
2525252222	2255525555	2255252255	2522225522	2252255552	2225255525	2222555555	2225555522	5555525222	5552522555	5552225252
2255552255	2525225522	2522252222	2255225555	2225255555	2252255522	2225555552	2222555525	5552525252	5555522552	5555225222
2522225555	2255252222	2255525522	2525252255	2225555525	2222555552	2225255522	2252255555	5555222555	5552225222	5552522552
5255522552	5522525252	5525522555	5522225222	2552252555	5222255255	5225555222	2555555225	2255222225	2522225222	2525222252
5525525222	5522222555	5255525252	5522522552	5225555225	2555555222	2552255255	5222252555	2525222255	2255522252	2255222522
5522225252	5525522552	5522525222	5255522555	2555555255	5225552555	5222255225	2552255222	2255522522	2525222225	2522222255
5522522555	5255525222	5522222552	5525525252	5222255222	2552255225	2555552555	5225555255	2522222252	2255222255	2255522225
8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11

										8333333325
5522255552	2225222522	2552222552	5222225252	5225522555	2555525222	2255252555	2522255255	2525255222	2255555225	8333333325
5522555522	2252222555	5225525222	2555522555	2552225252	5222222552	2525255225	2255555222	2255255255	2522252555	8333333325
5255555525	2222522252	2555525252	5225522552	5222225222	2552222555	2255555255	2525252555	2522255225	2255255222	8333333325
5525555555	2225522225	5222222555	2552225222	2555522552	5225525252	2522255222	2255255225	2255552555	2525255255	8333333325
2225255225	2255525252	5552222225	5555222522	5555222522	5552522255	5255525522	5522552255	5525525555	5522252222	8333333325
2225552555	2525225222	5555522255	5552522252	5552222522	5555222225	5525552222	5522225555	5255552255	5522525522	8333333325
2222555222	2255222555	5552522522	5555522225	5555222255	5552222252	5522252255	5525525522	5522552222	5255525555	8333333325
2252255255	2522222552	5555222252	5552222255	5552522225	5555522522	5522525555	5255552222	5522225522	5525552255	8333333325
5222225555	2555552255	2255255522	2522255555	2525255525	2255555552	2222522552	2225525252	2252222555	2225225222	8333333325
5252525522	5225552222	2525255552	2255555525	2255255555	2522255522	2252225222	2225222555	2222525252	2225522552	8333333325
2555552525	2552225555	2255555555	2525255522	2522255552	2255255525	2225225252	2252222552	2225525222	2222522555	8333333325
5225552255	5222225522	2522255525	2255255552	2255555522	2525255555	2225522555	2222525222	2225222552	2252225252	8333333325
2552252222	5252552525	5525555222	5522555255	5522252555	5255555225	5555555255	5555255555	5552555522	5552255552	8333333325
5552525222	5522255255	5255552555	5252555225	5525552525	5522555222	2552222225	5222222522	5225522252	2555522255	8333333325
5555222552	5525555225	5522552525	5522255222	5255555255	5252552555	5225522255	2555522252	2552222522	5222222225	8333333325
5552222555	5255555222	5252555255	5525552555	5522555225	5522252525	2555522522	5225522225	5222222255	2552222252	8333333325
5555525252	5522552555	5522255225	5255552525	5252555222	5525555255	5222222252	2552222255	2555522225	5225522522	8333333325
2255522255	5552555555	2222525522	2225552255	2252225555	2225252222	5552255522	5252555552	5555525255	5552555255	8333333325
2522222225	5555555552	2252252222	2225225555	2222552255	2225525522	5555252525	5552555525	5552255555	5252555522	8333333325
2255222252	5552255525	2225252255	2252225522	2225552222	2222525555	5252555555	5555555222	5555255552	5552552525	8333333325
2525222522	5555255522	2225525555	2222552222	2225225522	2252252255	5552555552	5552252525	5252555525	5555555555	8333333325
8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325
12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	

The magic square given in Example 2.6 is constructed based on 2 by 2 combination of following 21 numbers:

$$\{22225, 22252, 22255, 22522, 22552, 22555, 25222, 25252, 25522, 25555, 52222, 52255, 52525, 52555, 55222, 55225, 55255, 55522, 55525, 55552, 55555\}.$$

Let's check the sum of these numbers in three situations:

Numbers used:

$$833325 := 22225 + 22252 + 22255 + 22522 + 22552 + 22555 + 25222 + 25252 + 25522 + 25555 + 52222 + \\ + 52255 + 52525 + 52555 + 55222 + 55225 + 55255 + 55522 + 55525 + 55552 + 55555$$

Upside-down:

$$833325 := 52222 + 25222 + 55222 + 22522 + 25522 + 55522 + 22252 + 25252 + 22552 + 55552 + 22225 + \\ + 55225 + 52525 + 55525 + 22255 + 52255 + 55255 + 22555 + 52555 + 25555 + 55555$$

Mirror looking:

$$799992 := 25555 + 52555 + 22555 + 55255 + 52255 + 22255 + 55525 + 52525 + 55225 + 22225 + 55552 + \\ + 22552 + 25252 + 22252 + 55522 + 25522 + 22522 + 55222 + 25222 + 52222 + 22222$$

Using 2 by 2 combinations of these 21 numbers, the **magic sums** are given by

$$S_{21 \times 21} := 8333333325 = 100000 \times 833325 + 833325 \quad (9)$$

and

$$S_{21 \times 21} := 7999999992 = 100000 \times 799992 + 799992. \quad (10)$$

The **original magic square** and **upside-down** cases, the **magic sums** are the same as given in (9). In case of **mirror looking**, the **magic sum** different and is as given in (10). Even though the **magic sums** are different but the magic square given in Example 2.6 is a **universal magic square** of order 21.

2.5.2 Block of Order 7

Example 2.7. *The universal semi-magic square of order 21 for the digits 2 and 5 written in digital form is given below in two parts:*

21x21	semi-mgc									
2225222225	2255222555	2525225222	5222252255	5255552525	5525555522	5555255525	2225522255	2252222522	2552225522	2555525555
5525552525	5555255522	2225255525	2255222225	2525222555	5222225222	5255552255	5522555222	555555225	2225555555	2252222255
5222222555	5255525222	5525552255	5555252525	2225255522	2255255525	2525222225	2555522522	5522225522	5522525555	5555552222
2255255522	2525255525	5222222225	5255522555	5525525222	5555252255	2225252525	2252255225	2552255555	2555522255	5522222522
5555225222	2225252255	2255252525	2525255522	5222255525	5255522225	5525522555	5555525522	2225525555	2252255222	2552255225
5255555525	5525522225	5555222555	2225225222	2255252255	2525252525	5222255522	5522255555	5522522255	5555522522	2225525522
2525252255	5222252525	5255555522	5525555525	5555222225	2225222555	2255225222	2552225555	2555552222	5522255225	5522555555
2222522255	2255522522	2522225522	5225525555	5252555222	5552255225	5552555555	2225222252	2255222552	2525225252	5222252222
5552255222	5552555225	2222555555	2255522255	2522222522	5225525522	5252525555	5525552555	5555255255	2225255552	2255222252
5225522522	5252525522	5552225555	5552555222	2222555225	2255555555	2522222255	5222222552	5255525252	5525552222	5555252555
2255555225	2522255555	5225522255	5252522522	5552225522	5552525555	2222555222	2255255255	2525255552	5222222252	5255522552
5552525522	2222525555	2255555222	2522255225	5225555555	5252522255	5552222522	5555225252	2225252222	2255252555	2525255255
5252555555	5552222255	5552522522	2222525522	2255525555	2522255222	5225555225	5255555552	5525522252	5555222552	2225225252
2522225555	5225555222	5252555225	5552255555	5552522255	2222522522	2255525522	2525252222	5222252555	5255555255	5525555552
2225522252	2252222552	2552225252	2555552222	5522252555	5522555255	5555555552	2222522225	2255522555	2522225222	5225552255
5522552555	5555552555	2225555552	2252222252	2552222552	2555525252	5522252222	5552252525	5552555522	2222555525	2255522225
2555522552	5522225252	5522552222	5555552555	2225555255	2252255552	2552222252	5225522555	5252525222	5552252255	5552552525
2252255255	2552255552	2555522252	5522222552	5522525252	5555552222	2225552555	2255555522	2522255525	5225522225	5252522555
5555525252	2225552222	2252252555	2552255255	2555555552	5522222252	5522522552	5552525222	2222552255	2255552525	2522255522
5522255552	5522522252	5555522552	2225525252	2252252222	2552252555	2555555255	5252555525	5552222225	5552522555	2222525222
2552252222	2555552555	5522255255	5522555552	5555522252	2225522552	2252225252	2522252255	5225552525	5252555522	5552255525
8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11

										83333356920
5522255222	5522555225	5555555555	2222522252	2255522552	2522225252	5225552222	5252552555	5552255255	5552555552	8333333325
2552222522	2555525522	5522225555	5552252555	5552555255	2222555552	2255522252	2522222552	5225525252	5252552222	8333333325
2225555225	2252255555	2552222255	5225522552	5252525252	5552252222	5552552555	2222555255	2255555552	2522222522	8333333325
5522525522	5555525555	2225555222	2255555255	2522255552	5225522252	5252522552	5552225252	5552552222	2222552555	8333333325
2555555555	5522222255	5522522522	5552525252	2222552222	2255552555	2522255255	5225555552	5252522252	5552222552	8333333325
2252225555	2552255222	2555555225	5252555552	5552222252	5552522552	2222525252	2255552222	2522252555	5225555255	8333333325
5555522255	2225522522	2252225522	2522252222	5225552555	5252555255	5552255552	5552522252	2222522552	2255525252	8333333325
5255552555	5525555255	5555255552	2225522225	2252222555	2552225222	2555552255	5522252525	5522555522	5555555255	8333333325
2525222552	5222225252	5255552222	5522552525	5555555522	2225555525	2252222225	2552222555	2555525222	5522252255	8333333325
2225255255	2255255552	2525222252	2555522555	5522225222	5522552255	5555552525	2225555522	2252255525	2552222225	8333333325
5525525252	5555252222	2225252555	2252255522	2552255525	2555522225	5522222555	5522525222	5555522555	2225552525	8333333325
5222255552	5255522252	5525522552	5555525222	2225552255	2252252525	2552255522	2555555525	5522222225	5522522555	8333333325
2255252222	2525252555	5222255255	5522255525	5522522225	5555522555	2225525222	2252252255	2552252525	2555555522	8333333325
5555222252	2225222552	2255225252	2552252255	2555552525	5522255522	5522555525	5555522225	2225522555	2252225222	8333333325
5252552525	5552255522	5552555525	2225222255	2255222522	2525225522	5222225555	5255555222	5525555225	5555255555	8333333325
2522222555	5225525222	5252552255	5525555222	5555255225	2225255555	2255222255	2525222522	5222225522	5255525555	8333333325
2222555522	2255555525	2522222225	5222222522	5255525522	5525525555	5555255222	2225255225	2255255555	2525222255	8333333325
5552225222	5552552255	2222552525	2255255225	2525255555	5222222255	5255522522	5525525522	5555225555	2225255222	8333333325
5225555525	5252522225	5552222555	5555225522	2225225555	2255255222	2525255225	5222255555	5255522255	5525522522	8333333325
2255552255	2522252525	5225555522	5255555555	5525522255	5555222522	2225225522	2255225555	2525255222	5222255225	8333333325
5552522225	2222522555	2255525222	2525225555	5222255222	5255555225	5525555555	5555222255	2225222522	2255225522	8333333325
8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8569283325
12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	

It is based on the 2 by 2 combinations of 21 numbers considered in Example 2.6. These 21 numbers are divided in 3 parts of 7 each with unequal sums. These 9 blocks of order 7 are **pandiagonal magic squares with different magic sums**. This lead us to a **block-wise universal semi-magic square** of order 21 with the **magic sums** as given in (9) and (10).

Remark 2.1. *By the semi-magic square, it is understood that the sum of rows and columns is the same, while principal diagonals sums are different.*

2.5.3 Block of Order 3

Example 2.8. *The universal semi-magic square of order 21 for the digits 2 and 5 written in digital form is given below in two parts:*

21x21	semi-mgc									
5225252555	2522225222	5255552252	5255222225	5552255522	2222552552	2552555525	2255522555	5552525525	5222222252	5555255552
5255525222	5225252252	2522252555	2222555522	5255252552	5552222225	5552522555	2552525525	2255555525	2225255552	5222252222
2522252252	5255552555	5225225222	5552252552	2222522225	5255255522	2255525525	5552555525	2552522555	5555252222	2225222252
5252555555	5525522522	2225525252	2555522255	2522555255	5522252525	5225255222	2522225225	5255525555	5255252555	5552225222
2225522522	5252525252	5525555555	5522255255	2555552525	2522522255	5255525225	5225225555	2522255222	2222525222	5255252252
5525525252	2225555555	5252522522	2522552525	5522222255	2555555255	2522225555	5255555222	5225225225	5552252252	2222552555
5222222225	5555255522	2225252552	2525255525	2252222555	5555525525	5252522252	5525555552	2225552222	2555555555	2522522522
2225255522	5222252552	5555222225	5555522555	2525225525	2252255525	2225555552	5252552222	5525522252	5522222522	2555525252
5555252552	2225222225	5222255522	2252225525	5555555255	2525222555	5525552222	2225522252	5252555552	2522525252	5522255555
5255222255	5552255255	2222552525	2552555222	2255525225	5552525555	5222252555	5555225222	2225252252	2525222225	2252255522
2222555255	5255252525	5552222255	5552525225	2552525555	2255555222	2225225222	5222252252	5555252555	5555555522	2525252552
5552252525	2222522255	5255255255	2255525555	5552555222	2552525225	5555252252	2225252555	5222225222	2252252552	5555522225
2555555525	2522522555	5522225525	5225222252	2522255552	5255552222	5255255555	5552222522	2222525252	2552522255	2255555255
5522222555	2555525525	2522555525	5255555552	5225252222	2522222252	2222522522	5255225252	5552255555	5552555255	2552552525
2522525525	5522255525	2555522555	2522252222	5255522252	5225255552	5552225252	2222555555	5255222522	2255552525	5552522255
2525255222	2252225225	5555525555	5252552555	5525525222	2225552252	2555522225	2522555522	5522252552	5225255525	2522222555
5555525225	2525225555	2252255222	2225525222	5252552252	5525552555	5522255522	2555552552	2522522225	5255522555	5225225525
2252225555	5555555222	2525225225	5525552252	2225552555	5252525222	2522552552	5522222225	2555555522	2522225525	5255555525
2552522252	2255555552	5552552222	5222255555	5555222522	2225225252	2525222255	2252255255	5555525252	5252555222	5525525225
5552555552	2552552222	2255522252	2225222522	5222225252	5555255555	5555555255	2525252525	2252222255	2225525225	5252525555
2255552222	5552522252	2552555552	5555225252	2222525555	5222222522	2252252525	5555522255	2525255255	5525525555	2222555222
8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11

										83333357649
2225252222	2525255555	2252222522	5555525252	5252522255	5525555255	2225552525	2555555222	2522525225	5522225555	8333333325
5555222252	5555522522	2525225252	2252255555	2225555255	5252552525	5525522255	5522225225	2555525555	2522555222	8333333325
5222255552	2252225252	5555555555	2525222522	5525552525	2225522255	5252555255	2522525555	5522255222	2555525225	8333333325
2222552252	2552522225	2255555522	5552552552	5222255525	5555222555	2225225525	2525222252	2252255552	5555522222	8333333325
5552252555	5552555522	2552552552	2255522225	2225222555	5222225525	5555255525	5555555552	2525252222	2252222522	8333333325
5255225222	2255552552	5552522225	2552555522	5555225525	2225255525	5222222555	2252252222	5555522252	2525255552	8333333325
5522225252	5225222255	2522255255	5255552525	5255255222	5552225225	2222525555	2552552555	2255525222	5552552252	8333333325
2522555555	5255555255	5225252525	2522222255	2222525225	5255225555	5552255222	5552525222	2552552252	2255552555	8333333325
2555522522	2522252525	5255522255	5225255255	5552225555	2222555222	5255225225	2255552252	5552552555	2552525222	8333333325
5555552552	5252555525	5525522555	2225525525	2555522252	2522555552	5522252222	5225255555	2522222522	5255525252	8333333325
2252222225	2225522555	5252525525	5525555525	5522255552	2555552222	2522522252	5255522522	5225225252	2522255555	8333333325
2525255522	5525525525	2225555525	5252522555	2522552222	5522222252	2555555552	2522225252	5255555555	5225222522	8333333325
5552552525	5222255222	5555225225	2225225555	2525252555	2252225222	5555552252	5252522225	5525555522	2225552552	8333333325
2255522255	2225225225	5222225555	5555255222	5555525222	2525252252	2252252555	2225555522	5252552552	5525522225	8333333325
2552555255	5555225555	2225255222	5222225225	2252252252	5555552555	2525225222	5525552552	2225522225	5252555522	8333333325
5255525525	5255222252	5552255552	2222552222	2552555555	2255522522	5552525252	5222222255	5555255255	2225252525	8333333325
2522255525	2222555552	5255252222	5552222252	5552522522	2552525252	2255555555	2225255255	5222252525	5555222255	8333333325
5225222555	5552252222	2222522252	5255255552	2255525252	5552555555	2552522522	5555252525	2225222255	5222255255	8333333325
2225525555	2555552555	2522525222	5522252252	5225222225	2522255522	5255552552	5255255525	5552222555	2222525525	8333333325
5525555222	5522225222	2555552252	2522552555	5255555522	5225252552	2522222225	2222522555	5255225525	5552255525	8333333325
5252525225	2522552252	5522252555	2555525222	2522252552	5255522225	5225255522	5552225525	2222555525	5255222555	8333333325
8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8333333325	8576573325
12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	

It is based on the 2 by 2 combinations of 21 numbers considered in Example 2.6. These 21 numbers are divided in 7 parts of 3 each with unequal sums. These 49 blocks of order 3 are also **semi-magic** with different **semi-magic sums**. This lead us to a **block-wise universal semi-magic square** of order 21 with the **magic sums** as given in (9) and (10).

2.6 Magic Square of Order 22

Example 2.9. *The universal magic square of order 22 for the digits 2 and 5 written in digital form is given below in two parts:*

22x22	mgc									
2222222222	5522225555	5252552222	2555252525	5255222225	2525255522	5522525225	5222255222	2555555225	2222522522	5555555552
2555555222	2222522225	5255225555	5225552222	2222252255	5252522255	2552555255	5522225252	2222252552	2225522555	5555255522
5222252525	2555552552	2225522255	5252525555	5555522222	2222555555	5225522522	2555255225	5255225525	2252225225	5552255255
5252525552	5222252255	2555552525	2252222522	5225525555	5555252222	2225555552	5555522555	2222255222	2255525252	5525555225
2222552552	5225522222	5222255555	2555552255	2255522555	5555525555	5552252222	2252255522	5555225225	2522525525	5522555222
5552225252	2225552525	5555522225	5222255552	2555555555	2522525225	5555225555	5525552222	2255555255	2525225552	5522252552
2522555225	5525525525	2252252255	5555222255	5222255522	2555555552	2525225252	5552225555	5522552222	2552522222	5255252525
5522252222	2525255222	5522525552	2255555555	5552222522	5222255255	2555555522	2552525525	5525525555	2555222225	5252552255
5522525555	5255252222	2552552552	5522222222	2522555552	5525522555	5222255225	2555555255	2555225552	2222222255	5225555555
2252222225	2255522255	2522522522	2525222555	2552525225	2555225252	2222225525	2222525552	2225522222	2555525555	5225252225
5555255555	5552255552	5525555522	5522555255	5522255225	5255255222	5252552552	5225552525	5555522555	5222552252	5222252222
5555522255	5555222522	5552222555	5525525225	5522525252	5522225525	5255225552	5252522222	5225522225	5225252222	255552252
2255522522	2522522555	2525225225	2552525252	2555225525	2222225552	2222522222	2225522225	2252222255	5222252225	5222525555
5525552252	2552552225	5555225525	5555555225	2225552552	2255522222	5222555222	5225225225	2222555522	5552255555	2522522255
2525252225	5555525252	5225555255	2222555222	2252225552	5222555225	5225222555	2222255552	5552252252	5555252255	2255522225
5225525225	5252555522	2222255225	2225525525	5222555255	5225222522	2555255555	5555252252	2522552225	5555525255	2252222222
5255255552	2555255255	2222525252	5222555522	5225222255	2552552255	5555522522	2255552225	5252522555	5225552552	2225525552
2552555522	2222225225	5222555552	5225222225	2525252525	5225552252	2252252225	5255222522	5522255555	5252555222	2222525525
2555222555	5222555555	5225222222	2522552552	5252552252	2225552225	5522222255	5522552255	2525255552	5255255225	2222225252
5222552255	5225225552	2255555222	5255252252	2222552225	5522522225	5525552525	2522555555	2552522522	5522255255	2555225225
5225225525	2252255225	5522252252	2222252225	5525522222	5552252552	2255552255	2525222255	5222552525	5522555522	2552522555
2225555255	5522552252	2555252225	5552225552	5555255222	2252252525	2522522225	5222552552	5225225252	5525555552	2525222522
88525885250	88525885250	88525885250	88525885250	88525885250	88525885250	88525885250	88525885250	88525885250	88525885250	88525885250
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11

											88525885250
2225555555	2252222555	5225255255	5222525252	2522552255	5555252552	5552225525	2255525552	5225552225	2552552252	5525522255	88525885250
2252255552	2255525225	5222525525	2525255555	5552252525	5525525552	2522522222	5555552225	2555252252	5522522522	5225255225	88525885250
2255555522	2522525252	2552555552	5525552255	5522522222	2525222225	5555252225	2222252252	5522222555	5225255222	5222525552	88525885250
2522555255	2525225525	5522555555	5522222225	2552522255	5552252225	2222552252	5255225225	5225252552	5222522222	2555255522	88525885250
2525255225	2552525552	5255222255	2555222522	5525552225	2225552252	5252525252	5225252525	5222522225	2222255255	5522255552	88525885250
2552555222	2555222222	2222222555	5522552225	2252252252	5225525525	5225252255	5222522255	2222555225	5255255522	5252522522	88525885250
2555252552	2222222225	5522252225	2255552252	5555525552	5225255555	5222522522	2225555222	5252555255	5225522555	2222525225	88525885250
2222252525	2222522255	2522552252	5555222222	5225255552	5222522555	2252252552	5225555225	5555525225	2225525252	5255252225	88525885250
2222552255	2225522522	5552222225	5225255522	5222525225	2255552525	5555555222	5555225252	2252225525	5252552225	2525252252	88525885250
5222252252	5222552222	5555555522	5225555552	5252555555	5255252255	5522252525	5522552552	5525555222	5552255225	5555255255	88525885250
5225225555	2555552225	2225525225	2222522555	2222222522	2555222255	2552522225	2525222222	2522525552	2255525525	2252225252	88525885250
5222552225	5222225555	2222552525	2222252552	2555255222	2552555225	2525255255	2522555522	2255555552	2252255555	2225552255	88525885250
2555552222	5225252252	5252555225	5255255255	5522255522	5522555552	5525555555	5552252255	5555252525	5555525552	5225555222	88525885250
5252522225	5522552525	5225552255	2555525552	5222222555	2252255255	2555255552	5522222522	5255225252	2525252222	2222225555	88525885250
5255222222	5525552552	2555225555	5252552525	2555525525	5222222522	2225555522	2552555555	5522522255	5522225225	2522552222	88525885250
5522225552	5552255222	2255552222	2552525555	5255252552	2555525252	5222222255	2222555552	2525252255	5525522225	5522522555	88525885250
5522525525	5555255225	5525522522	2252252222	2525225555	5522255222	2555525225	5222222225	2222255555	2522552525	5552222222	88525885250
5525525252	5555555255	5555225552	5552222255	2225552222	2522525555	5522555225	2555522555	5222222222	2555252255	2255552552	88525885250
5552225225	5225555522	2252255222	5555525525	5555222225	2222552222	2255525555	5525555255	2555522522	5222225552	2552552525	88525885250
5555222555	5252555552	2525252552	2225555225	5225525252	5555522222	2222252222	2252225555	5552255522	2555522255	5222225525	88525885250
5555522522	5255255555	5222225252	2522555222	2222555255	5252525225	5225525552	2555252222	2225525555	5555255552	2555522225	88525885250
5225522255	5522252255	2555522222	5222225225	2255555225	2222255522	5255222555	5252525525	2552552222	2225525555	5555555555	88525885250
88525885250	88525885250	88525885250	88525885250	88525885250	88525885250	88525885250	88525885250	88525885250	88525885250	88525885250	88525885250
12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	

It is based on the 2 by 2 combinations of 22 numbers:

{22222, 22225, 22255, 22522, 22555, 25225, 25252, 25525, 25552, 25555, 52222, 52225, 52252, 52255, 52525, 52552, 55222, 55225, 55255, 55522, 55552, 55555}.

Let's check the sum of these numbers in three situations:

Numbers used:

$$885250 := 22222 + 22225 + 22255 + 22522 + 22555 + 25225 + 25252 + 25525 + 25552 + 25555 + 52222 + \\ + 52225 + 52252 + 52255 + 52525 + 52552 + 55222 + 55225 + 55255 + 55522 + 55552 + 55555$$

Upside-down:

$$885250 := 22222 + 52222 + 55222 + 22522 + 55522 + 52252 + 25252 + 52552 + 25552 + 55552 + 22225 + \\ + 52225 + 25225 + 55225 + 52525 + 25525 + 22255 + 52255 + 55255 + 22555 + 25555 + 55555$$

Mirror looking:

$$825844 := 22222 + 22225 + 22255 + 22522 + 22555 + 25225 + 25252 + 25525 + 25552 + 25555 + 52222 + \\ + 52225 + 52252 + 52255 + 52525 + 52552 + 55222 + 55225 + 55255 + 55522 + 55552 + 55555$$

Using 2 by 2 combinations of these 22 numbers, the **magic sums** are given by

$$S_{22 \times 22} := 88525885250 = 100000 \times 885250 + 885250 \quad (11)$$

and

$$S_{22 \times 22} := 82585225844 = 100000 \times 825844 + 825844. \quad (12)$$

The **original magic square** and **upside-down** cases, the **magic sums** are the same as given in (11). In case of **mirror looking**, the **magic sum** is as given in (12). Even though the **magic sums** are different but the magic square given in Example 2.9 is a **universal magic square** of order 22.

2.7 Magic Square of Order 23

Example 2.10. *The pandiagonal universal magic square of order 23 for the digits 2 and 5 written in digital form is given below in two parts:*

23x23	pan	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102
	2222522225	2225255552	2225555522	2252255225	2255252555	2255552255	2522252222	2525225552	2552225252	2555222555	2555522522	5222222252
9111111102	5555222252	5555555555	2222555525	2225255255	2225555222	2252252525	2255252225	2255525555	2522225522	2525225222	2552222552	2555222255
9111111102	5552222255	5552522225	5555255552	5555555522	2222555225	2225252555	2225552255	2252252222	2255225552	2255525252	2522222555	2525222522
9111111102	5522522522	5525522252	5552255555	5552555525	5555255255	5555552222	2222552525	2225252225	2225525555	2252225522	2255225222	2255522552
9111111102	5255522552	5522222255	5522522225	5525555552	5552255522	5552555225	5555252555	5555522555	2222552222	2225225552	2225525252	2252222555
9111111102	5225522555	5252522522	5255522252	5522255555	5522555525	5525555255	5552252222	5552552525	5555252225	5555255555	2222525522	2225225222
9111111102	5222225222	5222522552	5225522255	5252522225	5255555552	5522255522	5522555225	5525552555	5552252255	5552552222	5555225552	5555252522
9111111102	2555225252	2555522555	5222222522	5222522252	5225555555	5252555525	5255552555	5522252222	5522552525	5525552225	5552225555	5552525522
9111111102	2525225522	2552225222	2555222552	2555522255	5222222225	5222555552	5225555222	5252555225	5255552555	5522252255	5522552222	5525525552
9111111102	2255525552	2522225252	2525222555	2552222522	2555222252	2555555555	5222255525	5222555255	5225555222	5252552525	5255552225	5522225555
9111111102	2252225555	2255225522	2255525222	2522222552	2525222255	2552222225	2555255552	2555555522	5222255225	5222552555	5225552255	5252552222
9111111102	2222522222	2225525552	2252225252	2255222555	2255522522	2522222252	2525255555	2552255525	2555255255	2555552222	5222252525	5222552225
9111111102	5555522225	2222525555	2225225522	2225525222	2252222552	2255222255	2255522225	2522255552	2525255522	2552255225	2555252555	2555522255
9111111102	5552552255	5555252222	5555525552	2222525252	2225222555	2225522522	2252222252	2255255555	2255555225	2522252555	2525255222	2552252525
9111111102	5522252555	5522552255	5525552222	5552225552	5552525252	5555222555	5555225222	2222522252	2225255555	2225555525	2252252555	2255255222
9111111102	5252555222	5255552525	5522252225	5522525555	5525525522	5552225222	5552522552	5555222255	5555222255	2222555552	2225255522	2225555225
9111111102	5222555225	5225552555	5252552255	5255552222	5522225552	5522525252	5525522555	5552222522	5552252255	5552222225	5552555552	5555255522
9111111102	2552255522	2555255225	2555552555	5222252255	5222552222	5225525552	5252525252	5255522555	5522222522	5522252255	5522222255	5552255525
9111111102	2522255525	2525255255	2552255222	2555252525	2555552225	5222225555	5222525522	5225525222	5252522552	5255522255	5522222225	5522555552
9111111102	2255255552	2255555522	2522255225	2525252555	2552252255	2555252222	2555525552	5222225252	5222522555	5225522522	5252522252	5255555555
9111111102	2225555555	2252255525	2255255255	2255552222	2522252525	2525252225	2552225555	2555225522	2555525222	2555525222	5222222552	5222522255
	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12

9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102
5222555555	5225555525	5252555255	5255555222	5522252525	5522552225	5525525555	5552225522	5552525222	5552225552	5555222555	5555222555	9111111102
2555522225	5222255552	5222555522	5225555225	5252552555	5255552255	5522252222	5522525552	5525525252	5552222555	5552522522	9111111102	9111111102
2552222252	2555255555	2555555525	5222255255	5222555222	5225552525	5252552225	5255525555	5522225522	5522525222	5525522552	9111111102	9111111102
2522222255	2525222225	2552255552	2555255522	2555555225	5222252555	5222552255	5225552222	5252525552	5255525252	5522222555	9111111102	9111111102
2255222522	2255522252	2522255555	2525255525	2552255255	2555255222	2555552525	5222252225	5222525555	5225525522	5252525222	9111111102	9111111102
2225522552	2252222255	2255222225	2255555552	2522255522	2525255225	2552252555	2555252255	2555552222	5222225552	5222525252	9111111102	9111111102
2222522555	2225222522	2225522252	2252255555	2255255525	2255555255	2522255222	2525252525	2552252225	2555225555	2555255522	9111111102	9111111102
5555225222	5555522552	2222522255	2225222225	2225555552	2252255522	2255255225	2255552555	2522252255	2525252222	2552225552	9111111102	9111111102
5552225252	5552522555	5555222522	5555222522	2222555555	2225255525	2225555255	2252255222	2255252525	2255552225	2255552225	9111111102	9111111102
5522525552	5522225252	5522522555	5525522522	5552222252	5552555555	5555255525	5555552555	2222555222	2225252525	2225552225	9111111102	9111111102
5225525555	5252525522	5255525222	5522222552	5522522255	5525522225	5552255552	5552555522	5555255225	5555525555	2222552255	9111111102	9111111102
5222252222	5222525552	5225525252	5252522555	5255522522	5522222252	5522555555	5525555525	5552255255	5552555222	5552525252	9111111102	9111111102
2555252225	2555525555	5222225522	5222525222	5225522552	5252522255	5255522225	5522255552	5522555522	5525555225	5552252555	9111111102	9111111102
2525252255	2552252222	2555225552	2555525252	5222222555	5222522522	5225522252	5252555555	5255555525	5522255255	5522555222	9111111102	9111111102
2255552525	2522252225	2525225555	2552225522	2555225222	2555522552	5222222255	5222522225	5225555552	5252555522	5255555225	9111111102	9111111102
2252225555	2255252255	2255552222	2522225552	2525225252	2552222555	2555222522	2555522252	5222255555	5222555525	5225555255	9111111102	9111111102
2225255222	2225552525	2252252225	2255225555	2255525522	2522225222	2525222552	2552222255	2555222225	2555555552	5222255522	9111111102	9111111102
5555555225	2222552555	2225252255	2225552222	2252225552	2255225252	2255522555	2522222522	2525222252	2552255555	2555255525	9111111102	9111111102
5552555255	5555255222	5555552525	2222552225	2225225555	2225525522	2252225222	2255222552	2255522255	2522222225	2522222225	9111111102	9111111102
5525555522	5552255225	5552552555	5555252255	5555552222	2222525552	2225225252	2225522555	2252222522	2255222252	2255222252	9111111102	9111111102
5522255525	5522555255	5525555222	5552252525	5552552225	5555225555	5555525522	2222525222	2225222552	2225522255	2252222225	9111111102	9111111102
5252555552	5255555522	5522255225	5522552555	5525552255	5552252222	5552525552	5555225252	5555225555	2222522522	2225222252	9111111102	9111111102
9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102	9111111102
13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23		

It is based on the 2 by 2 combinations of 23 numbers:

$$\{22225, 22252, 22255, 22522, 22552, 22555, 25222, 25252, 25522, 25552, 25555, 52222, 52225, 52255, 52525, 52555, 55222, 55225, 55255, 55522, 55525, 55552, 55555\}.$$

Let's check the sum of these numbers in three situations:

Numbers used:

$$911102 := 22225 + 22252 + 22255 + 22522 + 22552 + 22555 + 25222 + 25252 + 25522 + 25552 + 25555 + 52222 +$$

$$+ 52225 + 52255 + 52525 + 52555 + 55222 + 55225 + 55255 + 55522 + 55525 + 55552 + 55555$$

Upside-down:

$$911102 := 52222 + 25222 + 55222 + 22522 + 25522 + 55522 + 22252 + 25252 + 22552 + 25552 + 55552 + 22225 +$$

$$+ 52225 + 55225 + 52525 + 55525 + 22255 + 52255 + 55255 + 22555 + 52555 + 25555 + 55555$$

Mirror looking:

$$877769 := 22222 + 22225 + 22255 + 22522 + 22555 + 25225 + 25252 + 25525 + 25552 + 25555 + 52222 +$$

$$+ 52225 + 52252 + 52255 + 52525 + 52552 + 55222 + 55225 + 55255 + 55522 + 55552 + 55555$$

Using 2 by 2 combinations of these 23 numbers, the **magic sums** are given by

$$S_{23 \times 23} := 9111111102 = 100000 \times 911102 + 911102 \quad (13)$$

and

$$S_{23 \times 23} := 8777777769 = 100000 \times 877769 + 877769. \quad (14)$$

The **original magic square** and **upside-down** cases, the **magic sums** are the same as given in (13). In case of **mirror looking**, the **magic sum** is as given in (14). Even though the **magic sums** are different but the magic square given in Example 2.10 is a **universal magic square** of order 23.

2.8 Magic Square of Order 24

2.8.1 Blocks of Order 6

Example 2.11. *The universal magic square of order 24 for the digits 2 and 5 written in digital form is given below in two parts:*

24x24	mgc										
2522222222	5255555225	5255552255	5255525522	2522222552	2522255555	2222222225	5555555255	5555552222	5555525555	2222222522	2222255552
5255255555	2522522552	5255252255	2522525522	2522555225	5255222222	5522555552	2255222522	5522552222	2255225555	2255255255	5522522225
5225255555	5225255225	2552525522	2552552255	5225222552	2552522222	5225555552	5225555255	2552225555	2552252222	5225522522	2552222225
2552555555	2552522552	5225225522	5225252255	2552555225	5225222222	2552255552	2552222522	5225525555	5225552222	2552255255	5225522225
2522522222	5255222552	2522552255	5255225522	5255255225	2522555555	2255222225	5522522522	2255252222	5522525555	5522555255	2255255552
5255522222	2522255225	2522225522	2522252255	5255522552	5255555555	5555522225	2222255255	2222225555	2222252222	5555522522	5555555552
2225225222	5552552552	5552552252	5552525525	2225225225	2225252555	2222522252	5555255522	5555255222	5555222555	2222522255	2222555525
5552252555	2225525225	5552252252	2225525525	2225552552	5552225222	5525555525	2252222255	5525555222	2252222555	2252255522	5525522252
5522252555	5522252552	2255525525	2255552252	5522225225	2255525222	5222255525	5222255522	2555522555	2555552222	5222222255	2555522252
2255552555	2255525225	5522225525	5522252252	2255552552	5522225222	2555555525	2555522255	5222222555	5222255222	2555555522	5222222252
2225525222	5552225225	2225552252	5552225525	5552252552	2225552555	2252222252	5525522255	2252255222	5525522555	5525555522	2252255525
5552525222	2225252552	2225225525	2225252252	5552525225	5552552555	5555222252	2222555522	2222522555	2222555222	5555222255	5555255525
2222522225	5555255255	5555252222	5555225555	2222522522	2222555552	2225222222	5552555225	5552552255	5552525522	2225222552	2225255555
5525555552	2252222522	5525552222	2252225555	2252255255	5525522225	5552255555	2225522552	5552252255	2225525522	2225555225	5552222222
5222255552	5222255255	2555525555	2555552222	5222222522	2555522225	5522255555	5522255225	2255525522	2255552255	5522222552	2255522222
2555555552	2555522522	5222225555	5222252222	2555555255	5222222225	2255555555	2255522552	5522225522	5522252255	2255555225	5522222222
2252222225	5525522522	2252252222	5525525555	5525555255	2252255552	2225522222	5552222552	2225552255	5552225522	5552255225	2225555555
5555222225	2222555255	2222525555	2222552222	5555222522	5555255552	5552522222	2222555225	2222522552	2222522255	5552522552	5552555555
2222222252	5555555522	5555555222	5555522555	2222222255	2222255525	2522225222	5255552552	5255552252	5255525525	2522225225	2522252555
5522555525	2255222255	5522555222	2255222555	2255255522	5522522252	5255252555	2522525225	5255252252	2522525525	2522552552	5255225222
5225555525	5225555522	2552222555	2552255222	5225522255	2552222252	5225252555	5225252552	2552525525	2552552252	5225225225	2552525222
2552255525	2552222255	5225522555	5225555222	2552255522	5225522252	2552552555	2552525225	5225225525	5225252252	2552552552	5225225222
2255222252	5522522255	2255255222	5522522555	5522555522	2255255525	2522525222	5255225225	2522552252	5255225525	5255252552	2522552555
5555222252	2222255522	2222222555	2222255222	5555222555	5555555525	5255525222	2522252552	2522225525	2522252252	5255525225	5255552555
9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12

												9333333324
2225222252	5552555222	5552555222	5552522555	2225222255	2225255525	2222525222	5555252552	5555252252	5555225525	2222525225	2222552555	9333333324
5552255525	2225522255	5552255222	2225522555	2225555522	5552222252	5525552555	2252225225	5525552252	2252225525	2252252552	5525525222	9333333324
5522255525	5522255522	2255522555	2255555222	5522222255	2255522252	5222252555	5222252552	2555525525	2555552252	5222225225	2555525222	9333333324
2255555525	2255522255	5522222255	5522255222	2255555522	5522222252	2555552555	2555525225	5222225525	5222252252	2555552552	5222225222	9333333324
2225522252	5552222255	2225555222	5552222555	5552255522	2225555525	2252225222	5525525225	2252252252	5525525525	552552552	2252252555	9333333324
5552522252	2222525522	2222522555	2222525222	5552522255	5552555525	5555225222	2222552552	2222525525	2222552252	5555225225	5555252555	9333333324
2522222225	5255555255	5255552222	5255525555	2522222522	2522255552	2222222222	5555552225	5555552255	5555255222	222222552	2222255555	9333333324
5255255552	2522522522	5255252222	2522525555	2522555255	5255222225	5522555555	2255222552	5522552255	2255225522	2255255225	5522522222	9333333324
5225255552	5225255255	2552525555	2552552222	5225222522	2552522225	5225555555	5225555225	2552225522	2552252255	5225522552	2552222222	9333333324
2552555552	2552522522	5225225555	5225252222	2552555255	5225222225	2552255555	2552222552	5225525522	5225552255	2552255225	5225522222	9333333324
2522522225	5255222522	2522552222	5255225555	5255255255	2522555552	2255222222	5522522552	2255252255	5522525522	5522555225	2255255555	9333333324
5255522225	2522255255	2522225555	2522252222	5255522522	5255555552	5555522222	2222255225	2222225522	2222252255	5555522552	5555555555	9333333324
2222225222	555552552	555552252	555525525	2222225225	2222252555	2522222252	525555522	525555222	5255522555	252222255	2522255525	9333333324
5522552555	2255225225	5522552252	2255225525	2255252552	5522525222	5255255525	2522522255	5255255222	2522522555	2522555522	5255222252	9333333324
5225552555	5225552552	2552225525	2552252252	5225525225	2552225222	5225255525	5225255522	2552225555	2552552222	5225222255	2552522252	9333333324
2552252555	2552225225	5225525525	5225552252	2552252552	5225525222	2552555525	2552522255	5225222555	5225255222	2552555522	5225222252	9333333324
2255225222	5522525225	2255252252	5522525525	5522552552	2255252555	2522522252	5255222255	2522555222	5255222555	5255255522	2522555525	9333333324
5555525222	2222252552	2222225525	2222252252	5555525225	5555525555	5255522252	2522255522	2522222555	2522255222	5255522255	5255555525	9333333324
2222522222	5555255225	5555252255	5555225522	2222522552	2222555555	2225222225	5552555255	5552552222	5552525555	2225222522	2225255552	9333333324
5525555555	2252222552	5525552255	2252225522	2252255225	5525522222	5552255552	2225522522	5552252222	2225525555	2225555255	5552222225	9333333324
5222255555	5222255225	2555525522	2555552255	5222222552	2555522222	5522255552	5522255255	2255525555	2255552222	5522225222	2255522225	9333333324
2555555555	2555522552	5222225522	5222252255	2555555225	5222222222	2255555552	2255522522	5522225555	5522252222	2255555255	5522222225	9333333324
2252222222	5525522552	2252252255	5525525522	5525555225	2252255555	2225522225	5552222522	2225552222	5552225555	5552255255	2225555552	9333333324
5555222222	2222555225	2222252552	2222552255	5555222552	5555255555	5552522225	2222525525	2222255555	2222522222	5552522522	5552555552	9333333324
9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324
13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	

It is based on the 2 by 2 combinations of 24 numbers:

$$\{22222, 22252, 22522, 22525, 22552, 25222, 25225, 25252, 25255, 25522, 25525, 25552, 52225, 52252, 52255, 52522, 52525, 52552, 52555, 55225, 55252, 55255, 55525, 55555\}.$$

Let's divide the above 24 numbers in four groups of 6 each with **equal sums**:

$$\begin{aligned}
 A &:= 22252 + 22255 + 22555 + 55222 + 55522 + 55525 = 233331 \\
 B &:= 25222 + 25225 + 25525 + 52252 + 52552 + 52555 = 233331 \\
 C &:= 22222 + 22552 + 25522 + 52255 + 55225 + 55555 = 233331 \\
 D &:= 22225 + 22522 + 25555 + 52222 + 55255 + 55552 = 233331
 \end{aligned}$$

Let's check the sum of these numbers for **Upside-down** and **Mirror looking** cases:

Upside-down:

$$\begin{aligned}
 A &:= 25222 + 55222 + 55522 + 22255 + 22555 + 52555 = 233331 \\
 B &:= 22252 + 52252 + 52552 + 25225 + 25525 + 55525 = 233331 \\
 C &:= 22222 + 25522 + 22552 + 55225 + 52255 + 55555 = 233331 \\
 D &:= 52222 + 22522 + 55552 + 22225 + 55255 + 25555 = 233331
 \end{aligned}$$

Mirror looking:

$$\begin{aligned}
 A &:= 52555 + 22555 + 22255 + 55522 + 55222 + 25222 = 233331 \\
 B &:= 55525 + 25525 + 25225 + 52552 + 52252 + 22252 = 233331 \\
 C &:= 55555 + 52255 + 55225 + 22552 + 25522 + 22222 = 233331 \\
 D &:= 25555 + 55255 + 22225 + 55552 + 22522 + 52222 = 233331
 \end{aligned}$$

We observe that in all the three situations the sum remains the same. Using 2 by 2 combinations of these 24 numbers, the magic sum is given by

$$S_{24 \times 24} := 93333333324 = 100000 \times 933324 + 933324, \quad (15)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
 933324 &:= 22222 + 22252 + 22522 + 22525 + 22552 + 25222 + 25225 + 25252 + \\
 &\quad + 25255 + 25522 + 25525 + 25552 + 52225 + 52252 + 52255 + 52522 + \\
 &\quad + 52525 + 52552 + 52555 + 55225 + 55252 + 55255 + 55525 + 55555.
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we have a **block-wise universal magic square** of order 24 with magic sum given in (15), where each block of order 6 is a **universal magic square** with **magic sums** given in eqrefeq18a2.

2.8.2 Blocks of Order 4

Example 2.12. *The pandiagonal universal magic square of order 24 for the digits 2 and 5 written in digital form is given below in two parts:*

	pan	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324
9333333324	2522252555	5255555225	222522252	5552525222	2522252522	5255555252	2225222525	5552525255	2522252255	5255555225	2225222552	5552525522
9333333324	2225225222	5552522252	2522255525	5255552555	2225225255	5552522525	2522255252	5255552522	2225225522	5552522552	2522255225	5255552255
9333333324	5552555525	2225252555	5255525222	2522222252	5552555252	2225252522	5255525255	2522222525	5552555225	2225252255	5255525522	2522222552
9333333324	5255522252	2522225222	5552552555	2225255525	5255522525	2522225255	5552552522	2225255252	5255522552	2522225522	5552552255	2225255225
9333333324	2525552555	5252255525	222522252	5525225222	2525552522	5252255252	2225222525	5525225255	2525552255	5252255225	2225222552	5525225522
9333333324	2225252522	5525222252	2525555525	5252252555	2225252555	5525222525	2525555252	5252252522	2225252522	5525222552	2525555225	5252252255
9333333324	5525255525	2225252555	5252225222	2525522252	5525255252	2225252522	5252225255	2525522525	5525255225	2225252255	5252225522	2525522552
9333333324	5252222252	2525525222	5525252555	2225255525	5252222525	2525522525	5525252522	2225255252	5252222552	2525525522	5525252255	2225255225
9333333324	2552252555	5225555525	2225222252	5522525222	2552252522	5225555252	2225222525	5522525255	2552252255	5225555225	2225222552	5522525522
9333333324	2225225222	5522522252	2552255525	5225552555	2225225255	5522522525	2552255252	5225552522	2225225522	5522522552	2552255225	5225552255
9333333324	5522555525	2225252555	5225525222	2552222252	5522555252	2225252522	5225525255	2552222525	5522555225	2225252255	5225525522	2552222552
9333333324	5225522252	2552225222	5522552555	2225255525	5225522525	2552225255	5522552522	2225255252	5225522552	2552225522	5522552255	2225255225
9333333324	2552552555	5225255525	2522522252	5255225222	2552552522	5225255252	2522522525	5255225255	2552552255	5225255225	2522522552	5255225522
9333333324	2522525222	5255222252	2552555525	5225252555	2522525255	5255222525	2552555252	5225252522	2522525522	5255222552	2552555225	5225252255
9333333324	5252555525	2522525555	5222525222	2555222252	5252555252	2522525222	5222525255	2555222525	5252555225	2522525255	5222525522	2555222552
9333333324	5222522252	2555225222	5252552555	2525255525	5222522525	2555225255	5252552522	2522525522	5222522552	2555225522	5252552255	2522525225
9333333324	2225225255	5525555525	2222222252	5555525222	2225225222	5525555252	2222222525	5555525255	2225225255	5525555225	2222222552	5555525522
9333333324	2222225222	5555522252	2225225525	5525552555	2222225255	5555522525	2225225525	5525552522	2222225522	5555522552	2225225525	5525552255
9333333324	5555555525	2222252555	5525525222	2225222252	5555555252	2222252522	5525525255	2225222525	5555555225	2222252255	5525525522	2225222552
	5525522252	2225225222	5555552555	2222255525	5525522525	2225222525	5555552522	2222255252	5525522552	2225225522	5555552255	2222255225
	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12

9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324
2522252252	5255552552	2225225225	5552525525	2522252225	5255552525	2225225252	5552525552	2522252525	5255555555	2225222222	5552522522	9333333324
2225225525	5552525225	2522252552	5255552252	2225225552	5552525252	2522252525	5255552225	2225222522	5552522222	2522255555	5255552555	9333333324
5552525552	2225225252	5255525525	2522225225	5552525255	2225222225	5255525552	2522225252	5552555555	2225252555	5255522522	2522222222	9333333324
5255525225	2522225525	5552522522	2225252552	5255525252	2522225552	5552522225	2225252525	5255522222	2522222522	5552555255	2225255555	9333333324
2525552252	5252252552	2225252225	5525225525	2525552225	5252252525	2225252522	5525225552	2525555255	5252255555	2225222222	5525222522	9333333324
2225252525	5525225225	2525552552	5252252252	2225255552	5525225252	2525552525	5252252225	2225222522	5525222222	2525555555	5252252555	9333333324
5525252552	2225252252	5252225525	2525525225	5525252525	2225252225	5252225552	2525252525	5525255555	2225252555	5252222522	2525522222	9333333324
5252225225	2525525525	5525252252	2225252552	5252225252	2525525552	5525252225	2225252525	5252222222	2525522522	5525252555	2225255555	9333333324
2552252252	5225552552	2225225225	5522525525	2552252225	5225552525	2225225252	5522525552	2552252525	5225555555	2225222222	5522522522	9333333324
2225225525	5522525225	2522252552	5225552252	2225225552	5522525252	2522252525	5225552225	2225222522	5522522222	2522255555	5225552555	9333333324
5522525552	2225252252	5225525525	2522225225	5522525255	2225252225	5225525552	2522225252	5522555555	2225252555	5225522522	2522222222	9333333324
5225252225	2522225525	5522522522	2225252552	5225225252	2522225552	5522522225	2225252525	5225522222	2522222522	5522555255	2225255555	9333333324
2552252252	5225252552	2522252225	5255225525	2552252225	5225252525	2522252522	5255225552	2552252525	5225255555	2522222222	5255222522	9333333324
2522252525	5255225225	2522252552	5225252252	2522255552	5255225252	2522252525	5225252225	2522222522	5255222222	2522255555	5225252555	9333333324
5255252552	2522252252	5222252525	2522252225	5255252525	2522252225	5222252552	2522252525	5255255555	2522252555	5222222522	2522222222	9333333324
5222252225	2522252525	5255225225	2522252552	5222252522	2522255552	5255222225	2222252525	5222222222	2522222522	5255252555	2222255555	9333333324
2552252252	5222252552	2522252225	5255225525	2552252225	5222252525	2522252522	5255225552	2552252525	5222255555	2522222222	5252222522	9333333324
2522252525	5255225225	2522252552	5222252252	2522255552	5255225252	2522252525	5222252225	2522222522	5255222222	2522255555	5222252555	9333333324
5255252552	2522252252	5222252525	2522252225	5255252525	2522252225	5222252552	2222252525	5525255555	2222252555	5525222522	2222222222	9333333324
5222252225	2222252525	5555522522	2222252552	5525525252	2222255552	5555522225	2222252525	5525525552	2222252525	5525522522	2222222222	9333333324
5525525225	2222252525	5555522522	2222252552	5525525252	2222255552	5555522225	2222252525	5525522222	2222252522	5525522522	2222255555	9333333324
9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324
13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	

It is based on the 2 by 2 combinations of 24 numbers considered in Example 2.11. These 24 numbers are divided in 6 parts of 4 each with equal sums.

$$A := 22252 + 25222 + 52555 + 55525 = 155554$$

$$B := 22525 + 25255 + 52522 + 55252 = 155554$$

$$C := 22552 + 25522 + 52255 + 55225 = 155554$$

$$D := 25225 + 25525 + 52252 + 52552 = 155554$$

$$E := 25252 + 25552 + 52225 + 52525 = 155554$$

$$F := 22222 + 22522 + 55255 + 55555 = 155554$$

These 6 groups of 4 each are written in such a way that each group is already **upside-down** in itself. Let's check the sum of each group only for **mirror looking** case:

$$A := 55525 + 52555 + 25222 + 22252 = 155554$$

$$B := 55252 + 52522 + 25255 + 22525 = 155554$$

$$C := 55225 + 52255 + 25522 + 22552 = 155554$$

$$D := 52552 + 52252 + 25525 + 25225 = 155554$$

$$E := 52525 + 52225 + 25552 + 25252 = 155554$$

$$F := 55555 + 55255 + 22522 + 22222 = 155554$$

Thus, we have a **block-wise pandiagonal universal magic square** of order 24 with magic sum given in (15), where each block of order 4 is a **pandigonal universal magic square** with equal **magic sums** given given in (8).

2.8.3 Blocks of Order 12

Example 2.13. *The universal magic square of order 24 for the digits 2 and 5 written in digital form is given below in two parts:*

24x24	mgc										
5552225222	5255225525	5552522555	2255552555	2552552252	2522255222	2225522252	2522525225	2225222255	5522255525	5225252552	5255555522
5552525525	5552222555	5255225222	2522252252	2255555222	2552552555	2225225225	2225522255	2522522252	5255552552	5522255522	5225255525
5255222555	5552525222	5552225525	2552555222	2522252555	2255552252	2522522255	2225222255	2225525225	5225255522	5255555525	5522252552
2225555525	2522552552	2225255522	5522222252	5225225225	5255522255	5552252555	5255252252	5552555222	2255525222	2552525525	2522222555
2225252552	2225555522	2522555525	5255525225	5522222255	5225222252	5552552252	5552255222	5255252555	2522225525	2255522555	2552525222
2522555522	2225255525	2225552552	5225222255	5255522252	5522225225	5255255222	5552552555	5552252252	2552522555	2522225222	2255525525
5522252555	5225252252	5255555222	2225525222	2522525525	2225222555	2255555525	2552552552	2522255522	5552222252	5255225225	5552522255
5255552252	5522255222	5225252555	2225225525	2225522555	2522525222	2522252552	2255555522	2552555525	5552525225	5552222255	5255222252
5225255222	5255552555	5522252252	2522522555	2225225222	2225525525	2552555522	2522255525	2255552552	5255222255	5552522252	5552225225
2255522252	2552525225	2522222255	5552255525	5255252552	5552555522	5522225222	5225225525	5255522555	2225552555	2522552252	2225255222
2522225225	2255522255	2552522252	5552552552	5552255522	5255255525	5255525525	5522222555	5225225222	2225252252	2225555222	2522525555
2552522255	2522222252	2255525225	5255255522	5552555525	5552252552	5225222555	5255525222	5522225525	2522555222	2225252555	2225552252
5222225222	2552225525	5555522555	2555552555	5225552252	2252255222	2222522252	2255225225	2222222255	5555255525	5522552552	5525555522
5555525525	5222222555	2552225222	2252252252	2555555222	5225552555	2222225225	2222522255	2255222252	5525552552	5555255522	5522555525
2552222555	5555525222	5222225525	5225555222	2252252555	2555552252	2255222255	2222222252	2222525225	5522555522	5525555525	5555252552
2222555525	2255252552	2222255522	5555222252	5522525225	5525522255	5222225255	2552252252	5555555222	2555525222	5225525525	2252222555
2222252552	2222555522	2255255525	5525525225	5555222255	5522522252	5555552252	5222255222	2552252555	2252225525	2555522555	5225525222
2255255522	2222255525	2222552552	5522522255	5525522252	5555225225	2552255222	5555552555	5222252252	5225522555	2252225222	2555525525
5555252555	5522552252	5525555222	2222525222	2255225525	2222222555	2555555525	5225552552	2252255522	5222222252	2552225225	5555222255
5525552252	5555255222	5522552555	2222225525	2222522555	2255225222	2252252552	2555555522	5225555525	5555525225	5222222255	2552222252
5522555222	5525552555	5555252252	2255222555	2222225222	2222525525	5225555522	2252255525	2555552552	2552222255	5555522252	5222225225
2555522252	5225525225	2252222255	5222255525	2552252552	5555555522	5555225222	5522525525	5525522555	2222552555	2255252252	2222255222
2252225225	2555522255	5225522252	5555552552	5222255522	2552255525	5525525525	5555222555	5522525222	2222252252	2222555222	2255252555
5225522255	2252222252	2555525225	2552255522	5555555525	5222252552	5522522555	5525525222	5555225525	2255255222	2222252555	2222552252
9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12

												9333333324
5552222522	5255252255	5552525555	2255555255	2552555225	2522255552	2225522222	2522522552	2225222225	5522255555	5225225522	5255552222	9333333324
5552552255	5552225555	5255222522	2522255225	2255555552	2552555255	2225222552	2225522225	2522522222	5255525522	5522252222	5225255555	9333333324
5255225555	5552522522	5552252255	2552555552	2522255255	2255555225	2522522225	2225222222	2225522552	5225252222	5255555555	5522255222	9333333324
2225555555	2522525522	2225252222	5522222222	5225222552	5255522225	5552255255	5255255225	5552555552	2255522522	2552552255	2522225555	9333333324
2225225522	2225552222	2522555555	5255522552	5522222225	5225222222	5552555225	5552255552	5255255255	2522252255	2255525555	2552522522	9333333324
2522552222	2225255555	2225525522	5225222225	5255522222	5522222552	5255255552	5552555255	5552255225	2552525555	2522222522	2255552255	9333333324
5522255255	5225255225	5255555552	2225522522	2522552255	2225225555	2255555555	2552525522	2522252222	5552222222	5255222552	5552522225	9333333324
5255555225	5522255552	5225255255	2225252255	2225525555	2522522522	2522225522	2255552222	2552555555	5552522552	5552222225	5255222222	9333333324
5225255552	5255555255	5522255225	2522525555	2225222522	2225552255	2552552222	2522255555	2255525522	5255222225	5552522222	5552222552	9333333324
2255522222	2552522552	2522222225	5552255555	5255225522	5552552222	5522222522	5225252255	5255525555	2225555255	2522555225	2225255552	9333333324
2522222552	2255522225	2552522222	5552525522	5552252222	5255255555	5255552255	5522225555	5225222522	2225255225	2225555552	2522555255	9333333324
2552522225	2522222222	2255522552	5255252222	5552555555	5552225522	5225225555	5255522522	5522252255	2522555552	2225255255	2225555225	9333333324
5222222522	2552252255	5555525555	2555555255	5225555225	2252255552	2222522222	2255222552	2222222225	5555255555	5522525522	5525552222	9333333324
5555552255	5222225555	2552222522	2252255225	2555555552	5225555255	2222222552	2222522225	2255222222	5525525522	5555252222	5522555555	9333333324
2552225555	5555522522	5222252255	5225555552	2252255255	2555555225	2255222225	2222222222	2222522552	5522552222	5525555555	5555225522	9333333324
2222555555	2255225522	2222252222	5555222222	5522522552	5525522225	5222255255	2552255225	5555555552	2555522522	5225552255	2252225555	9333333324
2222225522	2222552222	2255255555	5525522552	5555222225	5522522222	5555555225	5222255552	2552255255	2252252255	2555525555	5225522522	9333333324
2255252222	2222255555	2222525522	5522522225	5525522222	5555222552	2552255552	5555555255	5222255225	5225525555	2252222522	2555552255	9333333324
5555255255	5522555225	5525555552	2222522522	2255252255	2222225555	2555555555	5225525522	2252252222	5222222222	2552222552	5555522225	9333333324
5525555225	5555255552	5522555255	2222252255	2222525555	2255222522	2252225522	2555552222	5225555555	5555522552	5222222225	2552222222	9333333324
5522555552	5525555255	5555255225	2255225555	2222222522	2222552255	5225552222	2252255555	2555525522	2552222225	5555222222	5222222552	9333333324
2555522222	52255522552	2252222225	5222255555	2552225522	5555552222	5555222522	5522552255	5525525555	2222555255	2255255225	2222255552	9333333324
2252222552	2555522225	5225522222	5555525522	5222252222	2552255555	5525552255	5555225555	5522522522	2222255225	2222555552	2255255255	9333333324
5225522225	2252222222	2555522552	2552252222	5555555555	5222225522	5522525555	5525522522	5555252255	2255255552	2222255255	2222555225	9333333324
9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324	9333333324
13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	

This magic square is also constructed with the same number as of Example 2.11. As explained above these numbers lead us to a **universal magic square** with same magic sum given in (15).

The magic square given in Example 2.13 is constructed based on 4 blocks of order 12. These blocks are **universal magic squares** of order 12 with equal **magic sums** given by

$$S_{12 \times 12} := 4666666662 = 10000 \times 46662 + 46662 \quad (16)$$

where

$$A := 22252 + 22255 + 22555 + 25222 + 25225 + 25525 + 52252 + 52552 + 52555 + 55222 + 55522 + 55525 = 466662$$

$$B := 22222 + 22225 + 22522 + 22552 + 25522 + 25555 + 52222 + 52255 + 55225 + 55255 + 55552 + 55555 = 466662$$

Based these two groups A and B we get 4 **universal magic squares** of order 12 with equal **magic sums** as given in (16). Moreover, each **magic square** of order 12 has 16 blocks of order 3. These blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic squares** different magic sums.

Finally, the magic square of order 24 given in Example 2.13 is with 64 blocks of **semi-magic squares** of order 3 having **different magic sums**, and 4 blocks of order 12 with **equal magic sums**.

2.8.4 Semi-bimagic Square

Example 2.14. *The universal semi-bimagic square of order 24 for the digits 2 and 5 written in digital form is given below in three parts:*

24x24	mgc	semi-bi					
222525555555	555225222222	555222222255	222522555522	222555222252	555255555525	555252555552	222552222225
222555222225	555255555552	555252555525	222552222252	222525555522	555225222255	555222222222	222522555555
222522222222	555222555555	555225555522	222525222255	222552555525	555252222252	555255222225	222555555552
222552555552	555252222225	555255222252	222555555525	222522222255	555222555522	555225555555	222525222222
555222555525	222522222252	222525222225	555225555552	555252222222	222552555555	222555555522	555255222255
555252222255	222552555522	222555555555	555255222222	555222555552	222522222225	222525222252	555225555525
555225222252	222525555525	222522555552	555222222225	555255555555	222555222222	222552222255	555252555522
555255555522	222555222255	222552222222	555252555555	555225222225	222525555552	222522555525	555222222252
222225552555	555525225222	555522225255	222222552522	222255225252	555555552525	55552552552	222252225225
222255225225	555555552552	555525525255	222252225252	222225552522	555525225255	555522225222	222222552555
222222225222	555522552555	555525552522	222225225255	222252552525	555552225252	555555225225	222255552552
222252552552	555552225225	555555225252	222255552525	222222225255	555522552522	555525552555	222225225222
555522552525	222222225252	222225225225	555525552552	555552225222	222252552555	222255552522	555552252555
555552225255	222252552522	222255552555	555555225222	555522552552	222222225225	222225225252	555525552525
555525225252	222225552525	222222552552	555522225225	555555552555	222255225222	222252225255	555552552522
555555552522	222255225255	222252225222	555552552555	555525225225	222225552552	222222552525	555522225252
225225555255	552525222522	552522222555	225222555222	225255222552	552555555225	552552555252	225252222525
225255222525	552555555252	552552555225	225252222552	225225555222	552525222555	552522222522	225222555255
225222222522	552522555255	552525555222	225225222555	225252555225	552552222552	552555222525	225255555252
225252555252	552552222525	552555222552	225255555225	225222222555	552522555222	552525555255	225225222522
552522555225	225222222552	225225222525	552525555252	552552222522	225252555255	225255555222	552555222555
552552222555	225252555222	225255555255	552555222522	552522555252	225222222525	225225222552	552525555225
552525222552	225225555225	225222555252	552522222525	552555555255	225255222522	225252222555	552552555222
552555555222	225255222555	225252222522	552552555255	552525222525	225222555252	225222555225	552522222552
933333333324	933333333324	933333333324	933333333324	933333333324	933333333324	933333333324	933333333324
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8

225225552555	552525225222	552522225255	225222552522	225255225252	552555552525	552552552552	225252225225
225255225225	552555552552	552552552525	225252225252	225225552522	552525225255	552522225222	225222552555
225222225222	552522552555	552525552522	225225225255	225252552525	552552225252	552555225225	225255552552
225252552552	552552225225	552555225252	225255552525	225222225255	552522552522	552525552555	225225225222
552522552525	225222225252	225225225225	552525552552	552552225222	225252552555	225255552522	552555225255
552552225255	225252552522	225255552555	552555225222	552522552552	225222225225	225225225252	552525552525
552525225252	225225552525	225222552552	552522225225	552555552555	225255225222	225252225255	552552552522
552555552522	225255225255	225252225222	552552552555	552525225225	225225552552	225222552525	552522225252
222525552555	555225222522	555222222555	222522555222	222555222552	55525555225	555252555252	222552222525
222555222525	555255552552	555252555225	222552222552	222525555222	555225222555	555222222522	222522555255
222522222522	555222555255	555225555222	222525222555	222552555225	555252222552	555255222525	222555555252
222552555252	555252222525	555255222552	222555555225	222522222555	555222555222	555225555255	222525222522
555222555225	222522222552	222525222525	555225555252	555252222522	222552555255	222555555222	555255222555
555252222555	222552555222	222555555255	555255222522	555222555252	222522222525	222525222552	555225555225
555225222552	222525555225	222522555252	555222222525	555255555255	222555222522	222552222555	555252555222
555255552222	222555222555	222552222522	555252555255	555225222525	222525555252	222522555225	555222222552
222225555555	555525222222	555522222255	222222555522	222255222252	55555555525	55552555552	222252222225
222255222225	555555555552	55552555525	222252222252	222225555522	555525222255	555522222222	222222555555
222222222222	555522555555	555525555222	222225222255	222252555525	555552222252	555555222225	222255555552
222252555552	555552222225	555555222252	22225555525	222222222255	555522555522	555525555555	222225222222
555522555525	222222222252	222225222225	555525555552	555552222222	222252555555	222255555522	555555222255
555552222255	222252555522	222255555555	555555222222	555522555552	222222222225	222225222252	555525555525
555525222252	222225555525	222222555552	555522222225	555555555555	222255222222	222252222255	555552555522
555555555522	222255222255	222252222222	555552555555	555525222225	222225555552	222222555525	555522222252
933333333324	933333333324	933333333324	933333333324	933333333324	933333333324	933333333324	933333333324
9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16

								933333333324
222225555255	555525222522	555522222555	222225552222	222255222552	55555555225	55552555252	222252222525	933333333324
222255222525	55555555252	55552555225	222252222552	22225555222	555525222555	555522222522	22222555255	933333333324
222222222522	555522555255	55552555222	222225222555	222252555225	555522222552	555555222525	22225555252	933333333324
222252555252	555552222525	555555222552	22225555225	222222222555	555522555222	55552555255	222225222522	933333333324
555522555225	222222222552	222225222525	55552555252	555522222522	222252555255	22225555222	555552222555	933333333324
555522222555	222252555222	22225555255	555555222522	555522555252	222222222525	222225222552	55552555225	933333333324
555525222552	22222555225	222222555252	555522222525	55555555255	222255222522	222252222555	55552555222	933333333324
55555555222	222255222555	222225222522	55552555255	555525222525	22222555252	222222555225	555522222552	933333333324
22522555555	55252522222	55252222255	225222555522	225255222252	55255555525	55255255552	22525222225	933333333324
225255222225	55255555552	552552555525	225252222252	225225555522	552525222255	55252222222	22522255555	933333333324
22522222222	55252255555	552525555522	225225222255	225252555525	552552222252	552555222225	22525555552	933333333324
225252555552	552552222225	552555222252	225255555525	225222222255	552522555522	55252555555	22522522222	933333333324
552522555525	225222222252	225225222225	552525555552	55255222222	22525255555	225255555522	552555222255	933333333324
552552222255	225252555522	22525555555	55255522222	552522555552	225222222225	225225222252	552525555525	933333333324
552525222252	225225555525	225222555552	552522222225	55255555555	22525522222	225252222255	552552555522	933333333324
552555555522	225255222255	22525222222	55255255555	552525222225	225225555552	225222555525	552522222252	933333333324
222525552555	55522522222	555222225255	222522552522	222555225252	555255552525	555252552552	222552225225	933333333324
222555225225	555255552552	555252552525	2225522225252	222525552522	555225222525	555222222522	222522552555	933333333324
222522222522	555222552555	555225552522	2225252225255	222552552525	5552522225252	5552552225225	222555552552	933333333324
222552552552	555252222525	5552552225252	222555552525	2225222225255	555222552522	555225552555	222525222522	933333333324
555222552525	2225222225252	2225252225225	555225552552	555252222522	222552552555	222555552522	555255222525	933333333324
5552522225255	222552552522	222555552555	555255222522	555222552552	2225222225225	2225252225252	555225552525	933333333324
5552252225252	222525552525	222522552552	5552222225225	555255552555	222555222522	2225522225255	555252552522	933333333324
555255552522	222555222525	22255222222	55525255255	555225222225	222525552552	222522252525	5552222225252	933333333324
933333333324	933333333324	933333333324	933333333324	933333333324	933333333324	933333333324	933333333324	933333333324
17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	

It is based on the 2 by 2 combinations of 24 numbers of 6-digits. These are divided in three groups of eight each with equal sums. See below:

$$A := 222222 + 222225 + 222252 + 222255 + 555522 + 555525 + 555552 + 555555 = 3111108$$

$$B := 222522 + 222525 + 222552 + 222555 + 555222 + 555225 + 555252 + 555255 = 3111108$$

$$C := 225222 + 225225 + 225252 + 225255 + 552522 + 552525 + 552552 + 552555 = 3111108$$

Let's check the sum of these numbers for **Upside-down** and **Mirror looking** cases:

Upside-down:

$$A := 222222 + 522222 + 252222 + 552222 + 225555 + 525555 + 255555 + 555555 = 3111108$$

$$B := 225222 + 525222 + 255222 + 555222 + 222555 + 522555 + 252555 + 552555 = 3111108$$

$$C := 222522 + 522522 + 252522 + 552522 + 225255 + 525255 + 255255 + 555255 = 3111108$$

Mirror looking:

$$A := 555555 + 255555 + 525555 + 225555 + 552222 + 252222 + 522222 + 222222 = 3111108$$

$$B := 552555 + 252555 + 522555 + 222555 + 555222 + 255222 + 525222 + 225222 = 3111108$$

$$C := 555255 + 255255 + 525255 + 225255 + 552522 + 252522 + 522522 + 222522 = 3111108$$

We observe that in all the three situations the sum remains the same. Using 2 by 2 combinations of these 24 numbers, the magic sum is given by

$$S_{24 \times 24} := 9333333333324 = 1000000 \times 9333324 + 9333324, \quad (17)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} 9333324 := & 222222 + 222225 + 222252 + 222255 + 555522 + 555525 + 555552 + 555555 + \\ & 222522 + 222525 + 222552 + 222555 + 555222 + 555225 + 555252 + 555255 + \\ & 225222 + 225225 + 225252 + 225255 + 552522 + 552525 + 552552 + 552555 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we have a **block-wise universal magic square** of order 24 with magic sum given in (17). Moreover, it is **semi-bimagic square** of order 24 with **semi-bimagic sum** given by

$$Sb_{24 \times 24} := 4287436575077028177315828 \quad \text{only rows and columns.} \quad (18)$$

All the blocks of order 8 are also **pandiagonal bimagic squares** with **equal magic sums**:

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 3111111111108 = 1000000 \times 3111108 + 3111108. \quad (19)$$

The **bimagic sums** of order 8 are different in each case.

2.9 Magic Square of Order 25

2.9.1 Magic Square

Example 2.15. *The universal pandiagonal magic square of order 25 for the digits 2 and 5 written in digital form is given below in three parts:*

25X25	pan	9888888879	9888888879	9888888879	9888888879	9888888879	9888888879	9888888879
	2222522225	2522255222	5222225222	5522255555	5555522222	5255552555	5555222555	2255255552
9888888879	5522225222	5555555555	2222552222	2522222225	5222255222	2255555552	2555525555	5255522552
9888888879	2522252222	5222222225	5522255222	5555525222	2222555555	5555222552	2255252555	2255522555
9888888879	5555552222	2222525222	2522255555	5222252222	5522222225	2555522555	5255555552	5555225555
9888888879	5222255555	5522252222	5555522225	2222555222	2522225222	2255225555	2255522552	2555552555
9888888879	5552225522	2225555525	2525225525	5225522522	5252552552	5225255522	5522552255	5525522255
9888888879	5225525525	5252522522	5552252552	2225525522	2525255525	2225222255	2522552525	5225225252
9888888879	2225552552	2525225522	5225555525	5252525525	5552222522	5522525252	5525555522	2225252255
9888888879	5252555525	5552225525	2225522522	2525252552	5225525522	2522552255	5225222255	5522552525
9888888879	2525222522	5225552552	5252525522	5552255525	2225525525	5525552525	2225225252	2522555522
9888888879	5255552252	5555222252	2255255225	2255525225	2555555255	2552222225	2552555222	5255225222
9888888879	2255555225	2555525225	5255555255	5555252252	2255222252	5552525222	2252255555	2552252222
9888888879	5555255255	2255252252	2255522252	2555555225	5255525225	2552552222	5255222225	5552555222
9888888879	2555522252	5255555225	5555225225	2255255255	2255552252	2252255222	2552225222	2552555555
9888888879	2255225225	2255555255	2555552252	5255522252	5555255225	5255255555	5552552222	2252222225
9888888879	5225252555	5522522555	5525555552	2225225555	2522522552	2222525552	2522255525	5222225525
9888888879	2225255552	2522525555	5225222552	5522552555	5525522555	5522225525	5555522522	2222552552
9888888879	5522522552	5525552555	2225222555	2522555552	5225225555	2522252552	5222225522	5522255525
9888888879	2522522555	5225255552	5522525555	5525522552	2225252555	5555555525	2222525525	2522222522
9888888879	5525525555	2225222552	2522552555	5225222555	5522555552	5222222522	5522252552	5555525522
9888888879	2552255522	2552552255	5255222255	5552552525	2252225252	5552252252	2225522252	2525255225
9888888879	5552522255	2252252525	2552225252	2552555522	5255252255	5225555225	5252525225	5552255255
9888888879	2552525252	5255255522	5552552255	2252222255	2552252525	2225555255	2525252252	5225522252
9888888879	2252252255	2552222255	2552552525	5255225252	5552555522	5252522252	5552255225	2225525225
9888888879	5255252525	5552525252	2252255522	2552252255	2552522255	2525225225	5225555255	5252552252
	9888888879	9888888879	9888888879	9888888879	9888888879	9888888879	9888888879	9888888879
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8

9888888879	9888888879	9888888879	9888888879	9888888879	9888888879	9888888879	9888888879
2255525555	2555522552	2552225522	2552555525	5255225525	5552522522	2252252552	5552255522
5555252555	2255222555	5552525525	2252222522	2552252552	2552525522	5255255525	5225522255
2555555552	5255525555	2552552552	5255225522	5552555525	2252225525	2552222522	2225525252
2255222552	2255552555	2252255525	2552225525	2552522522	5255252552	5552525522	5252552255
5255522555	5555255552	5255222522	5552552552	2252225522	2552255525	2552525525	2525252525
2225252525	2522525252	2222552252	2522222252	5222255225	5522225225	5555552555	5255522225
5522555522	5525552255	5522255225	5555525225	2222555255	2522252252	5222222252	2255525222
2522522255	5225252525	2522255255	5222252252	5522222252	5555552225	2222525225	5555252222
5525525252	2225255522	5555522252	2222555225	2522225225	5222255255	5522252252	2555552222
5225252255	5522522255	5222225225	5522255255	5555552252	2222522252	2522255225	2255255555
5552555555	2252252222	5552252555	2225522555	2525255552	5225525555	5252522552	5225225522
2552522225	5255255222	5225555552	5252525555	5552222552	2225552555	2525222555	2225225525
2252225222	2552255555	2225522552	2525252555	5225522555	5252555552	5552225555	5522552552
5255252222	5552522225	5252522555	5552255552	2225525555	2525222552	5225552555	2522555525
2552255222	2552525222	2525225555	5225522552	5252552555	5552222555	2225555552	5525522522
5522222522	5555552552	5255555522	5555252255	2255222255	2255552525	2555525252	2552252252
2522225522	5222255525	2255522255	2555552525	5255525252	5555255522	2255252255	5552555225
5555525525	2222522522	5555225252	2255255522	2255552255	2555522255	5255552525	2552555255
5222252552	5522225522	2555552255	5255522255	5555252525	2255225252	2255555522	2252222252
2222555525	2522225525	2255252525	2255525252	2555555522	5255552255	5555222255	5255225225
5225525225	5252555255	5225222225	5522555222	5525525222	2225255555	2522552222	2222552555
2225552252	2525222252	2225225222	2522555555	5225252222	5522522225	5525555222	5522255552
5252555225	5552225225	5522552222	5525522225	2225255222	2522525222	5225255555	2522222552
2525255255	5225552252	2522555222	5225225222	5522555555	5525552222	2225222225	5555522555
5552222252	2225555225	5525555555	2225252222	2522522225	5225255222	5522525222	5222225555
9888888879	9888888879	9888888879	9888888879	9888888879	9888888879	9888888879	9888888879
9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16

9888888879	9888888879	9888888879	9888888879	9888888879	9888888879	9888888879	9888888879	9888888879	9888888879
2225552255	2525222255	5225552525	5252525252	5225252252	5522522252	5525555225	2225225225	2522555255	9888888879
5252552525	5552225252	2225555522	2525252255	2225255225	2522525225	5225255255	5522552252	5525522252	9888888879
2525255522	5225552255	5252522255	5552252525	5522555255	5525552252	2225222252	2522555225	5225225225	9888888879
5552222255	2225552525	2525225252	5225555522	2522522252	5225255225	5522525225	5525555255	2225252252	9888888879
5225525252	5252555522	5552252255	2225522255	5525525225	2225255255	2522552252	5225222252	5522555225	9888888879
5555255222	2255225222	2255555555	2555552222	2552252555	2552522555	5255255552	5552525555	2252222552	9888888879
2555555555	5255552222	5555222225	2255255222	5552555552	2252225555	2552222552	2552552555	5255222555	9888888879
2255222225	2255555222	2555525222	5255555555	2552522552	5255252555	5552522555	2252255552	2552225555	9888888879
5255525222	5555255555	2255252222	2255522225	2252222555	2552255552	2552525555	5255222552	5552552555	9888888879
2255552222	2555522225	5255555222	5555225222	5255225555	5552522552	2252252555	2552222555	2552555552	9888888879
5522555525	5525525525	2225222522	2522552552	2222555522	2522252255	5222222255	5522252525	5555252525	9888888879
2522522522	5225252552	5522525522	5525555525	5522222255	5555552525	2222525252	2522255522	5222252255	9888888879
5525525522	2225255525	2522525525	5225222522	2522225252	5222255522	5522252255	5555222255	2222552525	9888888879
5225225525	5522522522	5525552552	2225225522	5555552255	2222522255	2522252525	5222225252	5522255522	9888888879
2225252552	2522525522	5225255525	5522525525	5222252525	5522225252	5555555522	2222552255	2522222255	9888888879
2552522252	5255255225	5552525225	2252255255	5552222225	2225555222	2525225222	5225555555	5252552222	9888888879
2252225225	2552255255	2552552252	5255222252	5225525222	5252555555	5552252222	2225522225	2525255222	9888888879
5255252252	5552522252	2252255225	2552225225	2225552222	2525222225	5225555222	5252525222	5552255555	9888888879
2552255225	2552525225	5255255255	5552552252	5252555222	5552225222	2225555555	2525252222	5225522225	9888888879
5552555255	2252252252	2552222252	2552555225	2525255555	5225552222	5252522225	5552255222	2225525222	9888888879
2522222555	5222255552	5522225555	5555522552	5255525522	5555255525	2255225525	2255522522	2555552552	9888888879
5555525555	2222522552	2522252555	5222222555	2255525525	2555522522	5255552552	5555225522	2255255525	9888888879
5222252555	5522222555	5555555552	2222525555	5555252552	2255225522	2255555525	2555525525	5255522522	9888888879
2222555552	2522225555	5222222552	5522252555	2555555525	5255525525	5555222522	2255252552	2255525522	9888888879
5522222552	5555552555	2222522555	2522255552	2255222522	2255552552	2555525522	5255555525	5555225525	9888888879
9888888879	9888888879	9888888879	9888888879	9888888879	9888888879	9888888879	9888888879	9888888879	9888888879
17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	

It is based on the 2 by 2 combinations of 25 numbers:

$$\{22225, 22252, 22255, 22522, 22552, 22555, 25222, 25225, 25252, 25522, 25525, 25555, 52222, 52252, 52255, 52525, 52552, 52555, 55222, 55225, 55255, 55522, 55525, 55552, 55555\}.$$

Let's check the sum of these numbers in three situations:

Numbers used:

$$988879 := 22225 + 22252 + 22255 + 22522 + 22552 + 22555 + 25222 + 25225 + 25252 + \\ + 25522 + 25525 + 25555 + 52222 + 52252 + 52255 + 52525 + 52552 + \\ + 52555 + 55222 + 55225 + 55255 + 55522 + 55525 + 55552 + 55555$$

Upside-down:

$$988879 := 52222 + 25222 + 55222 + 22522 + 25522 + 55522 + 22252 + 52252 + 25252 + \\ + 22552 + 52552 + 55552 + 22225 + 25225 + 55225 + 52525 + 25525 + \\ + 55525 + 22255 + 52255 + 55255 + 22555 + 52555 + 25555 + 55555$$

Mirror looking:

$$955546 := 25555 + 52555 + 22555 + 55255 + 52255 + 22255 + 55525 + 25525 + 52525 + \\ + 55225 + 25225 + 22225 + 55552 + 52552 + 22552 + 25252 + 52252 + \\ + 22252 + 55522 + 25522 + 22522 + 55222 + 25222 + 52222 + 22222.$$

Using 2 by 2 combinations of these 25 numbers, the **magic sums** are given by

$$S_{25 \times 25} := 98888888879 = 100000 \times 988879 + 988879 \quad (20)$$

and

$$S_{25 \times 25} := 9555555546 = 100000 \times 955546 + 955546. \quad (21)$$

The **original magic square** and **upside-down** cases, the **magic sums** are the same as given in (20). In case of **mirror looking**, the **magic sum** is as given in (21). Even though the **magic sums** are different but the magic square given in Example 2.15 is a **universal pandiagonal magic square** of order 25. Moreover, It is **block-wise pandiagonal magic square** of order 25, where each block of order 5 is also a **pandiagonal magic square** with different **magic sums**.

2.9.2 Bimagic Square

Example 2.16. *The universal pandiagonal bimagic square of order 25 for the digits 2 and 5 written in digital form is given below in three parts:*

25x25-bi	pan	8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880
	222222222222	225225525525	252252225225	525525552552	552552252252	525252525252	552525225222	222552552525
8888888888880	525525225225	552552552552	222222252252	225225222222	252252525525	225222552525	252225252225	525252222552
8888888888880	225225252252	252252222222	525525525525	552552225225	222222552552	552525222552	222552525252	225222225222
8888888888880	552552525525	222222225225	225225552552	252252252252	525525222222	252225225222	525252552525	552525252225
8888888888880	252252552552	525525252252	552552222222	222222525525	225225225225	222552252225	225222222552	252225525252
8888888888880	552225225552	222252552252	225525252222	252552222525	525222525225	252525552225	525552252552	552222222252
8888888888880	252552252222	525222222525	552225525225	222252225552	225525552252	222225222252	225252525222	252525225525
8888888888880	222252525225	225525225552	252552552252	525222252222	552225222525	525552225525	552222552225	222225252552
8888888888880	525222552252	552225252222	222252222525	225525525225	252552225552	225252252552	252525222252	525552525222
8888888888880	225525222525	252552525225	525222225552	552225552252	222252252222	552222525222	222225225525	225252552225
8888888888880	525222552252	552225252222	222252222525	225525525225	252552225552	225252252552	252525222252	525552525222
8888888888880	225525222525	252225225225	525222225552	552225552252	222252252222	552222525222	222225225525	225252552225
8888888888880	552525552222	222552225252	225222222225	252225525552	525252225252	252222252252	525225222222	552225252552
8888888888880	252225222225	525252525552	552525225252	222552552222	225222252525	222525525525	225552225225	252222552552
8888888888880	222552225252	225222552222	252225252525	525252222225	552525525552	525225552552	552225225225	222525222222
8888888888880	252525525252	525552225222	552222552525	222225252225	225252222552	22222225552	225225552252	252225225222
8888888888880	222225552525	225252225225	252525222552	525552525252	552222225222	525525252222	552552222525	222222525225
8888888888880	525552222552	552222525252	222225225222	225252552525	252525252225	225225525225	252252225552	525525552252
8888888888880	225252225222	252525552525	525552252225	552222222552	222225525252	552552552252	222222252222	225225222525
8888888888880	552222252225	222225222552	225252525252	252525225222	525552552525	252252222525	525525525225	552552225552
8888888888880	225552552225	252222252552	525225222252	552252525222	222525225525	552225252525	222252222225	225525525552
8888888888880	552252222252	222525525222	225552225525	252222552225	525225252552	252552525552	525222225252	552225552222
8888888888880	252222225525	525225552225	552225225552	222525222252	225552525222	222225255222	225525252525	252552222225
8888888888880	222525252552	225552222252	252222525222	525225225525	552225255225	525222222225	552225525552	222252222525
8888888888880	525225525222	552252225525	222525552225	225552252552	252222222252	225525225252	252552552222	525222252525
	8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8

8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880
225222252225	252225222552	225552225552	252222552252	525225252222	552252222525	222525525225	552225552225
552525525252	222552225222	552252252222	222525222525	225552525225	252222225552	525225552252	252552222252
252225552525	525252252225	252222525225	525225225552	552252552252	222525252222	225552222525	222252225525
222552222552	225222525252	222525552252	225552252222	252222222525	525225525225	552252225552	525222252552
525252225222	552525552525	525225222525	552252525225	222525225552	225552552252	252222252222	225525525222
222225525222	225252225525	222222252525	225225222225	252252525552	525525225252	552552552222	525252222222
525552552225	552222252552	525525525552	552552225252	222222552222	225225252525	252252222225	225222225225
225252222252	252525525222	225225552222	252252252525	525525222225	552552525552	222222225252	552525252252
552222225525	222225552225	552552222225	222222525552	225225225252	252252552222	525525252525	252225525525
252525252552	525552222252	252252225252	525525552222	552552252525	222222222225	225225525552	222552552552
552252552552	222525252252	552225525252	222252225222	225525552525	252552225225	525222222552	252525225552
252222222222	525225525525	252552552525	525222225225	552225222552	222252525252	225525225222	222225252222
222525225225	225552552552	222252222552	225525525252	252552225222	525222552525	552225252225	525552525225
525225252252	552252222222	525222225222	552225552525	222252225225	225525222552	252552525252	225252552252
225552525525	252222225225	225525252225	252552222552	525222525252	552225225222	222252552525	552222222525
525525222525	552552525225	525252552225	552525252552	222552222252	225222525222	252225225525	225552252525
225225225552	252252552252	225222222252	252225525222	525252225525	552525552225	222552225252	552252525552
552552252222	222222222525	552525225525	222552552225	225222252552	252225222252	525252525222	252222552222
252252525225	525525225552	252222525252	525252222252	552525525222	222552225525	225222552225	222525222225
222222552252	225225252222	222552525222	225222225525	252225552225	525252225552	552525222252	525225222525
252552225252	525222552222	252525222222	525552525525	552222225225	222225552552	225252252252	222222525252
222252252525	225525222225	222225225225	225252552552	252525252252	525552222222	552222525525	525525552525
525222525552	552225225252	525552225225	552222222222	222225525525	225252225225	252525552552	225225222552
225525552222	252552225252	225252525525	252525225225	525552552552	552222225225	222225222222	552552225222
552225222225	222252525552	552222552552	222225252252	225252222222	252525525525	525552225225	252252225225
8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880
9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16

8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880
22225225252	22525222225	25255252522	52522222525	25252525252	52552222225	55222252552	22225225252	22525255222	8888888888880
52522252522	55222522552	22225255222	22552525252	22225525552	22525222525	25252555222	52552252525	55222222225	8888888888880
22552555222	25255225252	52522222225	55222552522	52552552222	55222252525	22225222225	22525255552	25252522525	8888888888880
55222522225	22225252522	22552522552	25255255222	22525222225	25252552552	52552225252	55222552222	22225252525	8888888888880
25255222552	52522255222	55222525252	22225222225	55222225252	22225552222	22525225252	25252522225	52552525552	8888888888880
55252552552	22255222522	22522255252	25222525225	22552525252	25222225222	52522555252	55225225222	22252522252	8888888888880
25222555252	52525225225	55252522222	22255252525	55225255252	22252525222	22552222552	25222525252	52522522522	8888888888880
22255222222	22522252525	25222522522	52525255252	25222222552	52522552525	55225222522	22252555252	22552252225	8888888888880
52525222522	55252552552	22255222522	22522222222	22252522522	22552552525	25222252225	52522522552	55225252525	8888888888880
22522225225	25222522222	52525252525	55252522522	52522525222	55225222552	22252552525	22552222522	25222255252	8888888888880
52552552225	55222252222	22225222525	22525252522	22222552225	22522525252	25225222225	52552552522	55252225225	8888888888880
22525222225	25252552522	52552222552	55222255222	52552522222	55252525222	22222225525	22522555222	25225225252	8888888888880
55222225552	22222555222	22525225222	25252522225	22522522525	25225255222	52552525252	55252222225	22222525222	8888888888880
25252525222	52552222525	55222252522	22222522552	55252252552	22222222225	25225255222	25225222525	52552552225	8888888888880
22222552522	22525222552	25252555222	52552225222	25225252522	52552522525	55252525222	22222252552	22522522225	8888888888880
25222222225	52522552552	55225222522	22252555222	55222522222	22225252525	22552522522	25252552552	52522225225	8888888888880
22252522225	22552552222	25222225225	52522522222	25252225225	52522252552	55222525222	22225222222	22552525225	8888888888880
52522525225	55225222225	22252552552	22552225252	22225222522	22552522222	25252525252	52522225225	55222552552	8888888888880
22552525552	25222225252	52522555222	55225225225	52522252525	55222522525	22225255252	22552525222	25252222222	8888888888880
55225255222	22252525225	22552222225	25222252552	22552555252	25252225225	52522222222	55222552525	22225222522	8888888888880
22522522222	25225255225	52552525222	55252522225	52525222552	55252555222	22252522222	22522222225	25222525225	8888888888880
55252252225	22222222552	22522552522	25222522222	22522225222	25222522225	52525252522	55252225552	22252552225	8888888888880
25225252522	52552522522	55252525225	22222225222	55252552522	22255222552	22522255222	25222525222	52525222225	8888888888880
22222552525	22522525222	25225222252	52552552522	25222555222	52525222222	55252522225	22252525222	22522225552	8888888888880
52552522252	55252525225	22222222522	22522555225	22252222522	22522252522	25222522552	52525252222	55252525222	8888888888880
8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880	8888888888880
17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	

It is based on the 2 by 2 combinations of 25 numbers of 6-digits:

$$\{222222, 222225, 222252, 222525, 222552, 225222, 225225, 225252, 225525, 225552, 252222, 252225, 252252, 252525, 252552, 525222, 525225, 525252, 525525, 525552, 552222, 552225, 552252, 552525, 552552\}.$$

Let's check the sum of these numbers in three situations:

Numbers used:

$$8888880 := 222222 + 222225 + 222252 + 222525 + 222552 + 225222 + 225225 + 225252 + 225525 + \\ + 225552 + 252222 + 252225 + 252252 + 252525 + 252552 + 525222 + 525225 + \\ + 525252 + 525525 + 525552 + 552222 + 552225 + 552252 + 552525 + 552552$$

Upside-down:

$$8888880 := 222222 + 522222 + 252222 + 525222 + 255222 + 222522 + 522522 + 252522 + 525522 + \\ + 255522 + 222252 + 522252 + 252252 + 525252 + 255252 + 222525 + 522525 + \\ + 252525 + 525525 + 255525 + 222255 + 522255 + 252255 + 525255 + 255255$$

Mirror looking:

$$1055545 := 555555 + 555552 + 555525 + 555255 + 555252 + 552555 + 552552 + 552525 + 552255 + \\ + 552252 + 525555 + 525552 + 525525 + 525255 + 525252 + 255555 + 255552 + \\ + 255525 + 255255 + 255252 + 252555 + 252552 + 252525 + 252255 + 252252.$$

Using 2 by 2 combinations of these 25 numbers, the **magic sums** are given by

$$S_{25 \times 25} := 8888888888880 = 1000000 \times 8888880 + 8888880 \quad (22)$$

and

$$S_{25 \times 25} := 1055565055545 = 100000 \times 1055545 + 1055545. \quad (23)$$

The **original magic square** and **upside-down** cases, the **magic sums** are the same as given in (22). In case of **mirror looking**, the **magic sum** is as given in (23). Even though the **magic sums** are different but the magic square given in Example 2.16 is a **universal pandiagonal magic square** of order 25. Moreover, It is **block-wise pandiagonal magic square** order 25 and also **bimagic**, where each block of order 5 is also a **pandiagonal magic square** with equal **magic sums**. Below are bimagic sum and sum of magic square of order 5.

The magic square given by Example 2.16 is a **pandiagonal bimagic square** of order 25, where each block of order 5 is also a **pandiagonal** with equal **magic sums**:

$$S_{b_{25 \times 25}} := 3725028391688737374070710 \quad (24)$$

and

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 1777777777776 \quad (25)$$

The **bimagic** and **magic sums** given in equations (24) and (25) respectively refers only for the cases of **original numbers** and **upside-down** cases. The similar kinds of sums for the **mirror looking** case shall be seen later on. Moreover, the numbers chosen for constructing bimagic square of order 5 is also a **universal pandiagonal magic square** of order 5 with magic sum $S_{5 \times 5} := 177776$.

	177776	177776	177776	177776	177776	177776
	222222	225225	252252	525525	552552	177776
177776	525252	552525	222552	225222	252225	177776
177776	225552	252222	525225	552252	222525	177776
177776	552225	222252	225525	252552	525222	177776
177776	252525	525552	552222	222225	225252	177776
	177776	177776	177776	177776	177776	177776

Remark 2.2. Whole the work is 10-digits distributions of two numbers 2 and 5. This is only work where we used 12-digits distributions of two numbers 2 and 5 in order to get a **pandiagonal bimagic square** of order 25 given in Example 2.16. The Example 2.15 is with 10-digits distributions of two numbers 2 and 5. It is **pandiagonal bimagic square**. In both the examples the blocks of order 5 are **pandigonal magic squares**. In case of Example 2.15 these are of different magic sums while for the Example 2.16 these are of equal magic sums.

2.10 Magic Square of Order 26

Example 2.17. The **universal magic square** of order 26 for the digits 2 and 5 written in digital form is given below in three parts:

26x26	mgc							
2555225552	2222525222	2255255525	2525552222	5225555552	5255222552	5225252522	5552255252	2255525522
2522222225	5222552225	5222225222	5525255525	5252225555	5225222252	2552555252	2522555225	2222525255
5552522552	2522252222	2225522255	2555525222	2525555525	5522555552	2522525552	2552225255	5255252255
5222225255	5552555252	2522225555	5522255222	5555225222	5252255525	5225522252	5255252225	2255252522
5555252255	2555552522	5552525255	2522255552	2255522555	2225225222	5522555525	5225225552	2552522255
2255252552	2225252252	5555255225	5552552522	2522222252	5552255522	2555225222	5225555525	2522552225
5252252252	5525225525	2555225225	2225252255	5552555225	2522225552	2222522225	5222525222	5225255525
5525255522	5522525225	2525525522	5222552552	2555252252	5552552255	2522252225	5222252222	2225525222
2552222555	2525522225	5225552552	5252222552	2225525525	5222525225	5552552252	2522222255	2555525555
2552555525	2255255522	5252252222	5225225525	5522555252	5522225522	2225552552	5552525225	2522255222
5552225222	2552255525	5525222225	5522525555	2522525522	5225525255	2255522552	5522225525	5552552552
5522252225	2255522255	5552255222	2222522555	5222255522	2555522225	5555252222	2225225555	2555255552
5225555225	5225252255	2522552252	5255225225	2552552552	2552225525	2255225522	5525222552	2525555252
5522522255	5225555222	5225222555	2522555522	5255222225	2552552222	2552225555	2255255552	5525222252
2255555222	5552222555	2222555522	5222222225	2555552222	5555225555	2225255552	2555222252	5222525552
5255252222	5555222525	2552552555	5225555252	2552222255	2555222555	5222225225	2222525522	5255555522
2555522525	5255252555	5522522552	2552552225	2225255222	2222552252	5552225525	5255522555	2252525225
2522552555	5252225522	5255225552	5555222255	5552252255	2255552552	5255555222	2252552252	2225255225
2525525525	2522522252	2555552225	2255555225	5522225225	5255522255	2252552255	5555252522	5225522555
5225255552	5222225552	5522252522	2225552252	5255552225	2252555225	2555525255	5522555222	5552222525
2222522252	2225525255	5222552255	5255525552	2252552522	5222255252	5252222255	2255522525	5522552555
5222555252	2555255225	5255522252	2252525255	2222522552	2525552225	5522222525	5252225255	2552252252
2225252522	5255555552	2252555252	5552225522	5525225552	2225522525	2525552555	2552552255	5252222225
5255525555	2252522552	2255525525	2255222252	5222522525	5525252555	5255255225	2525555522	5522252222
2252525522	5522252552	2552255552	2555222252	2255252555	2522552522	5525222555	2225522225	5555225525
2225525225	2552525555	2225222525	2552252555	5225225255	2255255222	5222555522	2555552552	5222222552
10111111101	10111111101	10111111101	10111111101	10111111101	10111111101	10111111101	10111111101	10111111101
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9

5552525525	2522255522	5222555222	5522552255	2225555225	5522222555	5222252552	2252525555	5255525225
5552222552	5552525522	2225522555	5225552252	5522252255	2255555522	2252555552	5255552552	2552252522
5222252522	2222555252	5522255522	5225225225	2255552252	5552222225	5255525525	2255255225	2555252552
2552552252	2555555225	2255522225	2522552552	5552225225	2222552222	5525252255	5222525525	2225555552
5525255225	2552225225	5552252222	5255225525	2222552552	5222225555	2225525522	5522222252	5225555522
2552255222	2525552255	2222525555	2552525522	5222225525	2555555552	2255525552	5225222225	5255222555
5255222255	2255222555	5222255552	2552222552	2555525522	5555222252	2522552222	2552555522	5522252555
2522555525	2552555222	2555522252	2255255252	5555222552	2225225552	2552222225	2255552555	5225222525
5522225222	5255255525	5555225552	5525225255	2225255252	2555252225	5552252555	2522522525	5522522252
5555255552	2255525222	2225252225	2525552522	2555225255	5222522255	5255222525	5225525552	5552252252
2522222555	2225222252	2555222255	5252255225	5222552522	2225555222	5225252225	2222525225	2252552222
5222522252	2225525552	2522225222	2252552555	5552522525	5255555525	5522552252	5252252255	2525555225
5252225255	5522552522	5255522525	5552555525	2252525222	2522252555	2555255222	2225222255	5555252225
2525525552	5252252225	2252555525	2522222525	5255552555	5552525222	5222555225	2555252522	2225225255
2225552225	5522222255	5552552555	5255525222	2522255525	2252522525	5225522552	5522525522	5252225525
2252552552	5222552252	5225255225	5522225552	5522552225	2255252255	5252252522	2522222552	5552522225
2555252255	2522522225	5225552522	2225522252	5252225552	2552255225	2255225222	2525525255	2522225522
5225255522	5222222525	5522525255	5222555552	2525522252	2552552522	2222555525	2552225222	5525255252
2222522525	5225252555	5252255252	2555225555	5525255552	5255225255	2225255522	5552255525	2552525222
5225552555	5525252552	2525522552	2225252222	2255225555	2522555252	2552522252	5555222555	2255555525
2255225225	5225525555	5525225522	5555222225	2552252222	5225222552	2525522555	5255255552	2555555222
5522552222	5552255552	2255225525	2555555522	2552522225	5225525522	5555225225	5525255222	2522525555
2255525555	2555222552	2552252552	5222222555	5255255522	5522525525	5522225255	2555552252	2255222255
2225225522	5555225255	2552525225	2222555222	2522522555	5252252552	2555522255	2225555252	5222252255
2555555252	5255552222	5255252252	5552222255	5225255222	2525525225	5552525555	5222252225	5222522552
5255522225	2252525525	2522552255	2255552225	5225522255	5525252252	2522255252	5552552222	2222525552
10111111101	10111111101	10111111101	10111111101	10111111101	10111111101	10111111101	10111111101	10111111101
10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18

								10111111101
2552525255	5552522252	2225222225	5525252225	5252222252	2555552555	2552222525	2522522255	10111111101
2225225225	2555252222	2525522255	5522525552	5555252555	2255222525	5255255222	2555525525	10111111101
5222525555	5252255222	5225552225	2225252555	5525222525	2552522555	5555225522	2252522252	10111111101
5522522555	5225222255	2555252555	2525522525	2552255522	2225222552	2252525552	5255525522	10111111101
2522555222	5222552555	5252222525	2255222225	2555255252	2252552225	5255522552	2525552252	10111111101
2225552555	5522522525	5525252222	5222525255	2252522255	5255555252	5252225225	5522222552	10111111101
5225522525	2525525555	2225552522	2252555222	5255525255	5522552552	2255555252	5552252225	10111111101
5252255552	5522255225	2252522555	5255552522	5225525525	5552225255	2222522255	5255225555	10111111101
2255552255	2252555522	5255555225	5225225522	2222552522	5222255222	2552555552	2255252222	10111111101
2252522225	5255552255	2522522552	5222255225	2555522555	2552222252	5525225555	2222552555	10111111101
5255552252	5255255252	2555552255	5555255522	2255225552	2525555552	5222252555	2552522525	10111111101
5525252522	2255225255	2552255252	2552522552	5255225522	2522525525	5225252552	5225525225	10111111101
2555525552	5222222252	2222555552	5552225555	2255552222	5522222225	2225555522	5222522555	10111111101
5555255252	2555522552	5222225522	2222525525	5552252552	2255525225	5522252252	2225552255	10111111101
2525552552	5525225225	2255252252	2552252255	2552555225	5255252522	2522525255	5225255252	10111111101
5552222252	2225225525	2255525255	2522555552	2525555222	2225525555	2555555525	5525225222	10111111101
5552555522	2255555552	5555252552	5522255252	5225225555	5525222255	5222552222	5222255525	10111111101
2522225525	5552522555	5522225555	2555525225	2225522552	5225552222	2255252225	2555222225	10111111101
2255222552	2522252552	5552555222	2225552222	5222252252	5222525522	5522522225	2552225552	10111111101
5255225222	2552225522	2522225225	5552522255	5222522225	2222552255	2555225525	5252255522	10111111101
5522255525	2522525222	2552525525	2522252252	5552552225	2555255522	5552255225	2225252552	10111111101
5222222255	2225555525	5225225222	5255252552	2522252255	5552525552	2225222555	2255552522	10111111101
5225252222	2222552225	5222555525	5225525222	2522525225	2522255225	5552522252	5555255222	10111111101
2552252225	5225522225	5552225552	2555255525	5522525222	5225252252	2522252522	5552555552	10111111101
2222555225	2552525552	5522555522	2255522252	2225255525	5252225222	5225552255	2522225255	10111111101
2555225522	5552252522	5255222252	5252222555	5522255552	5555255525	2525525222	5522555225	10111111101
10111111101	10111111101	10111111101	10111111101	10111111101	10111111101	10111111101	10111111101	10111111101
19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	

It is based on the 2 by 2 combinations of 26 numbers:

{22225, 22252, 22255, 22525, 22552, 22555, 25222, 25225, 25255, 25522, 25525, 25552, 25555, 52222, 52225, 52252, 52255, 52522, 52552, 52555, 55222, 55225, 55252, 55522, 55525, 55552}.

Let's check the sum of these numbers in three situations:

Numbers used:

$$1011101 := 22225 + 22252 + 22255 + 22525 + 22552 + 22555 + 25222 + 25225 + 25255 + \\ + 25522 + 25525 + 25552 + 25555 + 52222 + 52225 + 52252 + 52255 + 52522 + \\ + 52552 + 52555 + 55222 + 55225 + 55252 + 55522 + 55525 + 55552$$

Upside-down:

$$1011101 := 52222 + 25222 + 55222 + 52522 + 25522 + 55522 + 22252 + 52252 + 55252 + \\ + 22552 + 52552 + 25552 + 55552 + 22225 + 52225 + 25225 + 55225 + 22525 + \\ + 25525 + 55525 + 22255 + 52255 + 25255 + 22555 + 52555 + 25555$$

Mirror looking:

$$1011101 := 25555 + 52555 + 22555 + 25255 + 52255 + 22255 + 55525 + 25525 + 22525 + \\ + 55225 + 25225 + 52225 + 22225 + 55552 + 25552 + 52552 + 22552 + 55252 + \\ + 52252 + 22252 + 55522 + 25522 + 52522 + 55222 + 25222 + 52222.$$

Using 2 by 2 combinations of these 26 numbers, the **magic sums** are given by

$$S_{26 \times 26} := 101111111101 = 100000 \times 1011101 + 1011101. \quad (26)$$

Thus in all the three cases, the magic sum is same as given in (26). Thus the magic square given in Example 2.17 is **universal magic square** of order 26.

2.11 Magic Square of Order 27

2.11.1 Without Block

Example 2.18. *The universal magic square of order 27 for the digits 2 and 5 written in digital form is given below in three parts:*

27x27	mgc							
2555225552	5222555552	2225522552	5522255525	2255552552	5552255222	2222552255	5222222225	2555552522
5555252225	2225222252	2522225522	5552552555	5255525225	2252522555	5252255225	2525552222	5525225255
2255222255	2552225222	2552525525	5255222525	2522552252	5225255522	5225555555	5522525555	5555552522
5552555222	5255555525	2252552552	5252252522	2525552255	5525222225	5555222552	2225225552	2522255552
5255222555	2522552555	5225225225	5225525255	5522555225	5555552222	2255225522	2552252225	2552522252
5522255522	2255522525	5552252252	2222555252	5222255555	2555525555	2555225525	5222522255	2225525222
5225522225	5522552522	5555552255	2255255552	2552222552	2552525552	5255252552	2522555222	5225255525
2222552222	5222225255	2555555225	2555222252	5222525522	2225552225	5522225225	2255522555	5552252555
5252225555	2525555252	5525255555	5555225222	2225225525	2522222255	5552552252	5255555522	2252522525
2255555552	5552222552	5522225552	5222252552	2555555222	2222555525	5222522225	2225552522	2555252255
5255522252	2252525522	5552552225	2525525225	5525222555	5252252555	2225252222	2522225255	5555255225
2522525222	5225225525	5255222255	5522552252	5555555522	5225522525	2552225555	2552555252	2255255555
2525555525	5525252552	5252255222	2225252255	2522222225	5555252522	5255525552	2252555552	5552522552
5522552555	5555525225	5225522555	2552255225	2552552222	2255225255	2522552225	5225222252	5255225522
5222222525	2555552252	2222555522	5222555555	2225525555	2555255252	2255522255	5552225222	5522225525
2552252522	2552552255	2255222225	2522522552	5225225552	5255255552	5522555222	5555555525	5225552552
5222525255	2225555225	2555252222	2255525522	5552252225	5522222252	5222222555	2555552555	2222525225
2225255252	2522255555	5555225555	5255525525	2252522255	5552525222	2525555522	5525222525	5252252252
2555522552	2222525552	5222255552	2225555222	2555255525	5222552552	5552252522	5522252255	2255522225
5525225522	5252252225	2525522252	2522222555	5555252555	2225225225	2252525255	5552555225	5255552222
5555525525	5225522255	5522525222	2552555522	2255222525	2552252252	5225255252	5255255555	2522525555
2522252552	5555255222	2225255525	2252522225	5552552522	5255552255	5525255552	5252222552	2525525552
2552525225	2255222555	2552252555	5225252222	5255225255	2522555225	5555222522	5225525522	5522552225
2225552252	2555255522	5222522525	5552225555	5522255252	2255555555	2555525222	2222525525	5222222255
5225252255	5255222225	2522552522	5555525552	5225555552	5522522552	2552555525	2255252552	2552255222
5552255225	5522252222	2255525255	2555552225	2222522252	5222225522	2225552555	2555225225	5222522555
2252555555	5552525555	5255555252	5525222255	5252225222	2525525525	2522222525	5555252252	2225255522
10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9

5555222555	2225252555	2522225225	5552525255	5255555225	2252552222	5252225522	2525552225	5525222252
2255255522	2552222525	2552552252	5255255252	2522555555	5225225555	5225525525	5522522255	5555252222
2555255222	5222555525	2225552552	5522252522	2255552255	5552222225	2222522552	5222225552	2555555552
5255252222	2522525255	5225255225	5225522252	5522525522	5555552225	2255225225	2552222555	2552552555
5522225555	2255555252	5552255555	2222525222	5222225525	2555522255	2555252252	5222555522	2225522525
5552522225	5255552522	2252552255	5252255552	2525522552	5525225552	5555252552	2225255222	2522255525
2222552225	5222222252	2555525522	2555252555	5222525225	2225522555	5522255225	2255552222	5552225255
5252222255	2525525222	5525225525	5555222525	2225252252	2522255522	5552555555	5255525555	2252555252
5225525552	5522555552	5555522552	2255255525	2552252552	2552555222	5255252255	2522522225	5225252522
5255552555	2252525225	5552522555	2525555225	5525252222	5252225255	2225252225	2522222252	5555225522
2522522525	5225252252	5255255522	5522555555	5555525555	5225555252	2552222255	2552525222	2255225525
2255555525	5552252552	5522255222	5222252255	2555522225	2222552522	5222525552	2225555552	2555222552
5522525255	5555555225	5225552222	2552225522	2552552225	2255222252	2522522555	5225252555	5255225225
5222255252	2555555555	2222525555	5222525525	2225522255	2555225222	2255555522	5552222525	5522252252
2525552522	5525252255	5252222225	2225222552	2522225552	5555255552	5255555222	2252555525	5552552552
5222522252	2225525522	2555252225	2255525225	5552222555	5522252555	5222252222	2555525255	2222555225
2225225222	2522225525	5555222255	5255552252	2252555522	5552522525	2525525555	5525255252	5252255555
2552255552	2552522552	2255225552	2522552552	5225255222	5255255525	5522522225	5555525222	5225552255
5525225225	5252222555	2525552555	2522252222	5555225255	2225255225	2252522252	5552525522	5255552225
5555552252	5225555522	5522522525	2552525555	2255255252	2552255555	5225225222	5255225525	2522522255
2555552552	2222555222	5222255525	2225522225	2555252522	5222552255	5552255552	5522222552	2255525552
2552555225	2255252222	2552225255	5225252225	5255222252	2522252552	5555525555	5225525225	5522522555
2225555555	2555225555	5222555252	5552222255	5522225222	2255525525	2555522525	2222552252	5222255522
2522252255	5555222225	2225252522	2252525552	5552555552	5255522552	5525255525	5252252552	2525555222
5552225522	5522252225	2255522252	2555522555	2222552555	5222225225	2225525255	2555255225	5222552222
2252525525	5552522255	5255525222	5525255522	5252222525	2525552252	2522255252	5555255555	2225225555
5225222552	5255225552	2522555552	5555555222	5225555525	5522552552	2552552522	2255252255	2552222225
10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656
10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18

									10666666656
2255225555	2552255252	2552555555	5255225222	2522525525	5225222255	5225552252	5522555522	555522525	10666666656
2555222225	5222552522	2225552255	5522255552	2255522552	5552225552	2222552552	5222255222	2555555525	10666666656
5555252222	2225225255	2522255225	5552522252	5255525522	2252552225	5252225225	2525522555	5525252555	10666666656
5522222255	2255525222	5552225525	2222522525	5222252252	2555555522	2555255555	5222525555	2225555252	10666666656
5552525552	5255555552	2252522552	5252255525	2525552552	5525255222	5555252255	2225222225	2522252522	10666666656
5255252225	2522522252	5225225522	5225552555	5522525225	5555522555	2255255225	2552252222	2552525255	10666666656
5252255522	2525522525	5525252252	5555255252	2225255555	2522225555	5552525525	5255522255	2252525222	10666666656
5225555222	5522555525	5555552552	2255252522	2552252255	2552522225	5255222552	2522525552	5225255552	10666666656
2222522555	5222252555	2555525225	2555225255	5222555225	2225552222	5522225522	2255552225	5552222252	10666666656
2522555252	5225255555	5255225555	5522525525	5555522255	5225525222	2552255522	2552522525	2255252252	10666666656
2255552522	5552252255	5522222225	5222222552	2555525552	2222555552	5222555222	2225555525	2555252552	10666666656
5255525255	2252555225	5552552222	2525525522	5525252225	5252222252	2225222555	2522252555	5555225225	10666666656
5222225222	2555525525	2222522255	5222552252	2225555522	2555222525	2255525555	5552255252	5522255555	10666666656
2525555552	5525222552	5252225552	2225252552	2522255222	5555255525	5255522225	2252552522	5552552255	10666666656
5522522252	5555525522	5225552225	2552225225	2552522555	2255252555	2522552222	5225225255	5255255225	10666666656
2225222525	2522252252	5555255522	5255555555	2252525555	5552555252	2525522255	5525225222	5252225525	10666666656
2552255525	2552552552	2255255222	2522552255	5225222225	5255252522	5522525552	5555555552	5225522552	10666666656
5222552555	2225525225	2555222555	2255555225	5552252222	5522225255	5222252225	2555522252	2222525522	10666666656
5555555555	5225525555	5522555252	2552522255	2255225222	2552225525	5225222525	5255252252	2522555522	10666666656
2555552255	2222522225	5222252522	2225525552	2555255552	5222522552	5552255525	5522252552	2255555222	10666666656
5525255225	5252252222	2525525255	2522252225	5555222252	2225225522	2252552555	5552525225	5255522555	10666666656
2225525525	2555222255	5222525222	5552255522	5522222525	2255552252	2555555252	2222555555	5222225555	10666666656
2522222552	5555225552	2225255552	2252555222	5552555525	5255552552	5525252522	5252252255	2525522225	10666666656
2552525522	2255252225	2552222252	5225222555	5255252555	2522525225	5555525255	5225555225	5522552222	10666666656
2252552252	5552555522	5255522525	5525225555	5252255252	2525555555	2522225222	5555225525	2225222255	10666666656
5225252552	5255255222	2522555525	5555522225	5225552522	5522552255	2552555552	2255222552	2552225552	10666666656
5552225225	5522222555	2255552555	2555552222	2222525255	5222255225	2225522252	2555225522	5222552225	10666666656
10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656
19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	

It is based on the 2 by 2 combinations of 27 numbers:

$$\{22225, 22252, 22255, 22525, 22552, 22555, 25222, 25225, 25255, 25522, 25525, 25552, 25555, 52222, 52225, 52252, 52255, 52522, 52552, 52555, 55222, 55225, 55252, 55522, 55525, 55552, 55555\}.$$

Let's check the sum of these numbers in three situations:

Numbers used:

$$1066656 := 22225 + 22252 + 22255 + 22525 + 22552 + 22555 + 25222 + 25225 + 25255 + \\ + 25522 + 25525 + 25552 + 25555 + 52222 + 52225 + 52252 + 52255 + 52522 + \\ + 52552 + 52555 + 55222 + 55225 + 55252 + 55522 + 55525 + 55552 + 55555$$

Upside-down:

$$1066656 := 52222 + 25222 + 55222 + 52522 + 25522 + 55522 + 22252 + 52252 + 55252 + \\ + 22552 + 52552 + 25552 + 55552 + 22225 + 52225 + 25225 + 55225 + 22525 + \\ + 25525 + 55525 + 22255 + 52255 + 25255 + 22555 + 52555 + 25555 + 55555$$

Mirror looking:

$$1033323 := 25555 + 52555 + 22555 + 25255 + 52255 + 22255 + 55525 + 25525 + 22525 + \\ + 55225 + 25225 + 52225 + 22225 + 55552 + 25552 + 52552 + 22552 + 55252 + \\ + 52252 + 22252 + 55522 + 25522 + 52522 + 55222 + 25222 + 52222 + 22222.$$

Using 2 by 2 combinations of these 27 numbers, the **magic sums** are given by

$$S_{27 \times 27} := 10666666656 = 100000 \times 1066656 + 1066656 \quad (27)$$

and

$$S_{27 \times 27} := 10333333323 = 100000 \times 1033323 + 1033323. \quad (28)$$

The cases of **original magic square** and **upside-down**, the **magic sums** are same as given in (27). In case of **mirror looking**, the **magic sum** is different, and is as given in (?). Even though the **magic sums** are different, but the magic square given in Example 2.18 is a **universal magic square** of order 27.

2.11.2 Block of Order 9

Example 2.19. *The universal semi-magic square of order 27 for the digits 2 and 5 written in digital form is given below in three parts:*

27x27	semi-mgc							
2225255522	5225225552	5255522555	5225555222	2552252222	5222522255	2552555552	5552525555	2522222225
5222522225	5225555552	2552225555	2522222555	2552555522	5552525552	5255522255	2225255222	5225252222
5552552222	2522222255	2552555222	5225225555	5255522225	2225255552	2552225552	5222522555	5225555522
2522225555	2552522225	5552555552	5255525552	2225222555	5225255522	5222552222	5225522255	2552255222
5225255222	5255552222	2225222255	2552255552	5222525555	5225522225	5552555522	2522225552	2552522555
5225522555	2552255522	5222525552	2552522255	5552555222	2522252222	2225222225	5225255552	5255525555
2552222255	5222555222	5225552222	5552522225	2522255552	2552525555	5225222555	5255555522	2225225552
2552525552	5552522555	2522255522	2225252222	5225222255	5255555222	5225525555	2552222225	5222555552
5255555552	2225225555	5225222225	5222555522	5225525552	2552222555	2522255222	2552552222	5552522255
2222555252	5222225255	5552225225	5522255225	2255552552	2555522552	2555255555	5555252522	2225522525
2555522525	5522255555	2255552522	2225525225	2555255252	5555225255	5552222552	2222555225	5222252552
5555252552	2225522552	2555255225	5222252522	5552222525	2222555555	2255525255	2555525225	5522255252
2225552522	2555222525	5555255555	5552225255	2222525225	5222255252	2555552552	5522222552	2255555225
5222255225	5552252552	2222522552	2255555555	2555552522	5522222525	5555255252	2225525255	2555225225
5522225225	2255555252	2555525255	2555222552	5555255225	2225552552	2222522525	5222255555	5552252522
2255522552	2555555225	5522252552	5555222525	2225555555	2555252522	5222225225	5552255252	2222525255
2555225255	5555225225	2225555252	2222552552	5222222552	5552255225	5522252522	2255522525	2555555555
5552255555	2222552522	5222222525	2555555252	5522222525	2255525225	2225555225	2555252552	5555222552
2252552555	5255225525	5525225522	5522552255	2522552252	5252225222	2525555525	5555552225	2255222252
5252222252	5522555525	2522552225	2255225522	2525552555	5555525525	5525225222	2252552255	5255252252
5555552252	2255225222	2525552255	5255252225	5525222252	2252555525	2522525525	5252225522	5522552555
2255252225	2525522252	5555555525	5525225525	2252525522	5255252555	5252252252	5522525222	2522552255
5255252255	5525252252	2252525222	2522555525	5252252225	5522522252	5555552555	2255225525	2525525522
5522525522	2522552555	5252225525	2525525222	5555552255	2255252252	2252522252	5255255525	5525252225
2522525222	5252252255	5522552252	5555522252	2255255525	2525552225	5255225522	5525252555	2252525525
2525525525	5555525522	2255252555	2252552252	5255225222	5525252255	5522552225	2522522252	5252255525
5525255525	2252552225	5255222252	5252252555	5522525525	2522525522	2255252255	2525552252	5555525222
10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9

2252555252	5255225255	5525225225	5522555225	2522552552	5252222552	2525555555	5555552522	2255222525
5252222525	5522555555	2522552522	2255225225	2525555252	5555525255	5525222552	2252555225	5255252552
5555552552	2255222552	2525555225	5255252522	5525222525	2252555555	2522525255	5252225225	5522555252
2255252522	2525522525	5555555555	5525225255	2252525225	5255255252	5252252552	5522522552	2522555225
5255255225	5525252552	2252522552	2522555555	5252252522	5522522525	5555552522	2255225255	2525525225
5522525225	2522555252	5252225255	2525522552	5555552225	2255252552	2252522525	5255255555	5525252522
2522522552	5252255225	5522552552	5555522525	2255255555	2525552522	5255225225	5525255252	2252525255
2525525255	5555525225	2255255252	2252552552	5255222552	5525255225	5522552522	2522522525	5252255555
5525255555	2252552522	5255222525	5252255252	5522525255	2522525225	2255255225	2525552552	5555522552
2225252555	5225225525	5255525522	5225552255	2552252252	5222525222	2552555525	5552552225	2522222252
5222522252	5225555525	2552252225	2522225522	2552552555	5552525525	5255525222	2225252255	5225252252
5552552252	2522225222	2552552255	5225252225	5255522252	2225255525	2552225525	5222525522	5225552555
2522252225	2552522252	5552555525	5255525525	2225225522	5225252555	5222552252	5225525222	2552252255
5225252255	5255552252	2225225222	2552255525	5222552225	5225522252	5552552555	2522225525	2552525522
5225525522	2552252555	5222525525	2552525222	5552552255	2522252252	2225222252	5225255525	5255552225
2552225222	5222552255	5225552252	5552522252	2522255525	2552552225	5225225522	5255552555	2225225525
2552525525	5552525522	2522252555	2225252252	5225225222	5255552255	5225552225	2552222252	5222555525
5255555525	2225252225	5225222252	5222552555	5225525525	2552225522	2522252255	2552552252	5552525222
2222555522	5222225552	5552222555	5522255222	2255552222	2555522255	2555255552	5555225555	2225522225
2555522225	5522255552	2255525555	2225522555	2555255522	5555225552	5552222255	2222555222	5222252222
5555252222	2225522255	2555255222	5222225555	5552222225	2222555552	2255525552	2555522555	5522255522
2225525555	2555222225	5555255552	5552225552	2222522555	5222255522	2555552222	5522222255	2255555222
5222255222	5552252222	2222522255	2255555552	2555525555	5522222225	5555255522	2225525552	2555222555
5522222555	2255555522	2555525552	2555222255	5555255222	2225552222	2222522225	5222255552	5552225555
2255522225	2555555222	5522252222	5555222225	2225555552	2555225555	5222222555	5552255522	2222525552
2555225552	5555222555	2225555522	2222552222	5222222255	5552255222	5522225555	2255522225	2555555552
5552255552	2222525555	5222222225	2555555522	5522225552	2255522555	2225555222	2555252222	5555222255
10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656
10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18

									106666689999
2222552555	5222225525	5552225522	5522252255	2255552252	2555525222	2555255525	5555252225	2225522252	10666666656
2555522252	5522255525	2255552225	2225525522	2555252555	5555225525	5552225222	2222552255	5222252252	10666666656
5555252252	2225525222	2555252255	5222252225	5552222252	2222555525	2255525525	2555525522	5522252555	10666666656
2225552225	2555222252	5555255525	5552225525	2222525522	5222252555	2555552252	5522225222	2255552255	10666666656
5222252255	5552252252	2222525222	2255555525	2555552225	5522222252	5555252555	2225525525	2555225522	10666666656
5522225522	2255552555	2555525525	2555225222	5555252255	2225552252	2222522252	5222255525	5552252225	10666666656
2255525222	2555552255	5522252252	5555222252	2225555525	2555252225	5222225522	5552252555	2222525525	10666666656
2555225525	5555225522	2225552555	2222552252	5222225222	5552252255	5522252225	2255522252	2555555525	10666666656
5552255525	2222552225	5222222252	2555552555	5522225525	2255525522	2225552255	2555252252	5555225222	10666666656
2252555522	5255225552	5525222555	5522555222	2522552222	5252222255	2525555552	5555525555	2255222225	10666666656
5252222225	5522555552	2522525555	2255222555	2525555522	5555525552	5525222255	2252555222	5255252222	10666666656
5555552222	2255222255	2525555222	5255225555	5525222225	2252555552	2522525552	5252222555	5522555522	10666666656
2255225555	2525522225	5555555552	5525225552	2252522555	5255255522	5252252222	5522522255	2522555222	10666666656
5255255222	5525252222	2252522255	2522555552	5252225555	5522522225	5555555522	2255225552	2525522555	10666666656
5522522555	2522555522	5252225552	2525522255	5555555222	2255252222	2252522225	5255255552	5525225555	10666666656
2522522255	5252255222	5522555222	5555522225	2255255552	2525525555	5255222255	5525255522	2252525552	10666666656
2525525552	5555522555	2255255522	2252552222	5255222255	5525255222	5522525555	2522522225	5252255552	10666666656
5525255552	2252525555	5255222225	5252255522	5522525552	2522522555	2255255222	2525552222	5555522255	10666666656
2225255252	5225225255	5255525225	5225555225	2552252552	5222522552	2552555555	5552552522	2522222525	10666666656
5222522525	5225555555	2552252522	2522225225	2552555252	5552525255	5255522552	2225255225	5225252552	10666666656
5552552552	2522222552	2552555225	5225252522	5255522525	2225255555	2552225255	5222525225	5225555252	10666666656
2522252522	2552522525	5552555555	5255525255	2225225225	5225255252	5222552552	5225522552	2552255225	10666666656
5225255225	5255552552	2225222552	2552255555	5222552522	5225522525	5552555252	2522225255	2552525225	10666666656
5225525225	2552255252	5222525255	2552522552	5552555225	2522252552	2225222525	5225255555	5255552522	10666666656
2552222552	5222555225	5225552552	5552522525	2522255555	2552552522	5225225225	5255555252	2225225255	10666666656
2552525255	5552525225	2522255252	2225252552	5225222552	5255555225	5225552522	2552222525	5222555555	10666666656
5255555555	2225252522	5225222525	5222555252	5225525255	2552225225	2522255225	2552552552	5552522552	10666666656
10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10666666656	10900096656
19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	

This magic square is constructed with the same numbers as of Example 2.18. These numbers lead us to a **universal semi-magic square** with **semi-magic sums** as given in (27) and (28). The magic square given in Example 2.19 is constructed based on blocks of order 9. These 9 blocks are **magic squares** with different **magic sums** resulting in a **semi-magic square** of order 27.

2.12 Magic Square of Order 28

2.12.1 Blocks of Order 4

Example 2.20. *The magic square of order 28 for the digits 2 and 5 written in digital form is given below in three parts:*

28x28	pan	108888888878	108888888878	108888888878	108888888878	108888888878	108888888878	108888888878	108888888878
	2255555222	5522255522	2225522255	5552222555	2255552222	5522255552	2225522225	5552225555	2255552555
108888888878	2225522555	5552222255	2255555522	5522255222	2225525555	5552222225	2255555552	5522252222	2225525222
108888888878	5552255522	2225555222	5522222555	2255522255	5552255552	2225552222	5522225555	2255522225	5552255525
108888888878	5522222255	2255522555	5552255222	2225555522	5522222225	2255525555	5552252222	2225555552	5522222252
108888888878	2555555222	5222255522	2222522255	5552225555	2555552222	5222255552	2222522225	5552255555	2555552555
108888888878	2222522555	5555222255	2555555522	5222255222	2222525555	5555222225	2555555552	5222252222	2222525222
108888888878	5555255522	2222555222	5222222555	2555522255	5555255552	2222552222	5222225555	2555522225	5555255525
108888888878	5222222255	2555522555	5555255222	2222555522	5222222225	2555525555	5555252222	2222555552	5222222252
108888888878	2522255222	5255555522	2225222255	5552522555	2522252222	5255555552	2225222225	5552525555	2522252555
108888888878	2225222555	5552522255	2522255522	5255555222	2225225555	5552522225	2522255552	5255552222	2225225222
108888888878	5552555522	2225255222	5255522555	2522222255	5552555552	2225252222	5255525555	2522222225	5552555525
108888888878	5255522255	2522222555	5552555222	2225255522	5255522225	2522225555	5552552222	2225255552	5255522252
108888888878	2552255222	5225555522	2255222255	5522522555	2552252222	5225555552	2255222225	5522525555	2552252555
108888888878	2255222555	5522522255	2552255522	5225555222	2255225555	5522522225	2552255552	5225552222	2255225222
108888888878	5522555522	2255255222	5225522555	2552222255	5522555552	2255252222	5225525555	2552222225	5522555525
108888888878	5225522255	2552222555	5522555222	2255255522	5225522225	2552225555	5522552222	2255255552	5225522252
108888888878	2525555222	5252255522	2252522255	5525222555	2525552222	5252255552	2252522225	5525225555	2525552555
108888888878	2252522555	5525222255	2525555522	5252255222	2252525555	5525222225	2525555552	5252252222	2252525222
108888888878	5525255522	2252555222	5252222555	2525522255	5525255552	2252552222	5252225555	2525522225	5525255525
108888888878	5252222255	2525522555	5525255222	2252555522	5252222225	2525525555	5525252222	2252555552	5252222252
108888888878	2552555222	5222555522	2525222255	5252522555	2552522222	5222555552	2525222225	5252525555	2552525555
108888888878	2525222555	5255222255	2552555522	5225255222	2525225555	5255222225	2552555552	5225252222	2525225222
108888888878	5252555522	2252555222	5252222555	2525522255	5525255552	2252552222	5252225555	2525522225	5525255525
108888888878	5225222255	2552522555	5255255222	2522555522	5225222225	2552525555	5255252222	2522555552	5225222252
108888888878	2555255222	5222555522	2525222255	5252522555	2555252222	5222555552	2525222225	5252525555	2555252555
108888888878	2525222555	5252522255	2552555522	5222555222	2525225555	5252522225	2552555552	5222552222	2525225222
108888888878	5252555522	2252555222	5252222555	2525522255	5525255552	2252552222	5252225555	2525522225	5525255525
108888888878	5225222255	2552522555	5255255222	2522555522	5225222225	2552525555	5255252222	2522555552	5225222252
108888888878	2555255222	5222555522	2525222255	5252522555	2555252222	5222555552	2525222225	5252525555	2555252555
108888888878	2525222555	5252522255	2552555522	5222555222	2525225555	5252522225	2552555552	5222552222	2525225222
108888888878	5252555522	2252555222	5252222555	2525522255	5525255552	2252552222	5252225555	2525522225	5525255525
108888888878	5225222255	2552522555	5255255222	2522555522	5225222225	2552525555	5255252222	2522555552	5225222252
	108888888878	108888888878	108888888878	108888888878	108888888878	108888888878	108888888878	108888888878	108888888878
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9

10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878
5522255525	2225522252	5552225222	2255552255	5522255225	2225522552	5552225522	2255552522	5522255252	2225522525
5552222252	2255555525	5522252555	2225525522	5552222552	2255555225	5522252255	2225525255	5552222525	2255555252
2225552555	5522225222	2255522252	5552255225	2225552255	5522225522	2255522552	5552255252	2225552522	5522225255
2255525222	5552252555	2225555525	5522222552	2255525522	5552252255	2225555225	5522222525	2255525255	5552252522
5222255525	2222522252	5555225222	2555552255	5222255225	2222522552	5555225522	2555552522	5222255252	2222522525
5555222252	2555555525	5222252555	2222525522	5555222552	2555555225	5222252255	2222525255	5555222525	2555555252
2222552555	5222225222	2555522252	5555255225	2222552255	5222225522	2555522552	5555255252	2222552522	5222225255
2555525222	5555252555	2222555525	5222222552	2555525522	5555252255	2222555225	5222222525	2555525255	5555252522
5255555525	2225222252	5552525222	2522252255	5255555225	2225222552	5552525522	2522252522	5255555252	2225222525
5552522252	2522255525	5255552555	2225225522	5552522552	2522255225	5255552255	2225225255	5552522525	2522255252
2225252555	5255525222	2522222252	5552555225	2225252255	5255525522	2522222552	5552555252	2225252522	5255525255
2522225222	5552552555	2225255525	5255522552	2522225522	5552552255	2225255225	5255522525	2522225255	5552552522
5225555525	2255222252	5522525222	2552252255	5225555225	2255222552	5522525522	2552252522	5225555252	2255222525
5522522252	2552255525	5225552555	2255225522	5522522552	2552255225	5225552255	2255225255	5522522525	2552255252
2255252555	5225525222	2552222252	5522555225	2255252255	5225525522	2552222552	5522555252	2255252522	5225525255
2552225222	5522552555	2252555525	5225522552	2552225522	5522552255	2252555225	5225522525	2552225255	5522552522
5225255525	2522522252	5255225222	2552552255	5225255225	2522522552	5255225522	2552552522	5225255252	2522522525
5255222252	2552555525	5225252555	2522525522	5255222552	2552555225	5225252255	2522525255	5255222525	2552555252
2522552555	5225225222	2552522252	5255255225	2522552255	5225225522	2552522552	5255255252	2522552522	5225225255
2552525222	5255252555	2522555525	5225222552	2552525522	5255252255	2522555225	5225222525	2552525255	5255252522
5222555525	2525222252	5252525222	2555252255	5222555225	2525222552	5252525522	2555252522	5222555252	2525222525
5252522252	2555255525	5222552555	2525225522	5252522552	2555255225	5222552255	2525225255	5252522525	2555255252
2525252555	5222525222	2555222252	5252555225	2525252255	5222525522	2555222552	5252555252	2525252522	5222525255
2555225222	5252552555	2522555525	5222522552	2555225522	5252552255	2522555225	5222522525	2555225255	5252552522
10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878
10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19

10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878
5552225255	2255552252	5522252552	2225525225	5552225525	2255552225	5522252525	2225525252	5552225552	10888888878
5522252522	2225525525	5552225225	2255552552	5522252252	2225525552	5552225252	2255552525	5522252225	10888888878
2255522525	5552252552	2225552252	5522225525	2255525225	5552252525	2225552225	5522225552	2255525252	10888888878
2225555252	5522225225	2255525525	5552252252	2225552552	5522225252	2255525552	5552252225	2225552525	10888888878
5555225255	2555552252	5222252552	2222525225	5555225525	2555552225	5222252525	2222525252	5555225552	10888888878
5222252522	2222525525	5555225225	2555552552	5222252252	2222525552	5555225252	2555552525	5222252225	10888888878
2555522525	5555252552	2222552252	5222225525	2555525225	5555252525	2222552225	5222225552	2555525252	10888888878
2222555252	5222225225	2555525525	5555252252	2222552552	5222225252	2555525552	5555252225	2222552525	10888888878
5552525255	2522252252	5255552552	2225225225	5552525525	2522252225	5255552525	2225225252	5552525552	10888888878
5255552522	2225225525	5552525225	2522252552	5255552252	2225225552	5552525252	2522252525	5255552225	10888888878
2522222525	5552552552	2225252252	5255525525	2522225225	5552552525	2225252225	5255525552	2522225252	10888888878
2225255252	5255525225	2522225525	5552552252	2225252552	5255525252	2522225552	5552552225	2225252525	10888888878
5522525255	2552252252	5225552552	2255225225	5522525525	2552252225	5225552525	2255225252	5522525552	10888888878
5225552522	2255225525	5522525225	2552252552	5225552252	2255225552	5522525252	2552252525	5225552225	10888888878
2552222525	5522552552	2255252252	5225525525	2552225225	5522552525	2255252225	5225525552	2552225252	10888888878
2255255252	5225525225	2552225525	5522552252	2255252552	5225525252	2552225552	5522552225	2255252525	10888888878
5525225255	2525552252	5252252552	2252525225	5525225525	2525552225	5252252525	2252525252	5525225552	10888888878
5252252522	2252525525	5525225225	2525552552	5252252252	2252525552	5525225252	2525552525	5252252225	10888888878
2525522525	5525252552	2252552252	5252225525	2525525225	5525252525	2252552225	5252225552	2525525252	10888888878
2252555252	5252225225	2525525525	5525252252	2252552552	5252225252	2525525552	5525252225	2252552525	10888888878
5255225255	2552552252	5225252552	2522525225	5255225525	2552552225	5225252525	2522525252	5255225552	10888888878
5225252522	2522525525	5255225225	2552552552	5225252252	2522525552	5255225252	2552552525	5225252225	10888888878
2552522525	5252552552	2525252252	5222525525	2555225225	5252552525	2522552225	5222525552	2555225252	10888888878
2522555252	5222525225	2555225525	5255252252	2522552552	5222525252	2552525552	5255252225	2522552525	10888888878
5252525255	2555252252	5222552552	2525225225	5252525525	2555252225	5222552525	2525225252	5252525552	10888888878
5222552522	2525225525	5252525225	2555252552	5222552252	2525225552	5252525252	2555252525	5222552225	10888888878
2555222525	5252552552	2525252252	5222525525	2555225225	5252552525	2525252225	5222525552	2555225252	10888888878
2525255252	5222525225	2555225525	5252552252	2525252552	5222525252	2555225552	5252552225	2525252525	10888888878
10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878
20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	

It is based on the 2 by 2 combinations of 28 numbers:

{22225, 22252, 22255, 22525, 22552, 22555, 25222, 25225, 25252, 25255, 25522, 25525, 25552, 25555, 52222, 52225, 52252, 52255, 52522, 52525, 52552, 52555, 55222, 55225, 55252, 55522, 55525, 55552}.

Let's divide these 28 numbers in 7 parts of 4 each with equal sums.

$$\begin{aligned}
 A &:= 22225 + 25555 + 52222 + 55552 = 155554 \\
 B &:= 22255 + 22555 + 55222 + 55522 = 155554 \\
 C &:= 22552 + 25522 + 52255 + 55225 = 155554 \\
 D &:= 22252 + 25222 + 52555 + 55525 = 155554 \\
 E &:= 25252 + 25552 + 52225 + 52525 = 155554 \\
 F &:= 22525 + 25255 + 52522 + 55252 = 155554 \\
 G &:= 25225 + 25525 + 52252 + 52552 = 155554
 \end{aligned}$$

These 7 groups of 4 each are written in such a way that each group is already **upside-down** in itself. Let's check the sum of each group only for **mirror looking** case:

$$\begin{aligned}
 A &:= 55552 + 52222 + 25555 + 22225 = 155554 \\
 B &:= 55522 + 55222 + 22555 + 22255 = 155554 \\
 C &:= 55225 + 52255 + 25522 + 22552 = 155554 \\
 D &:= 55525 + 52555 + 25222 + 22252 = 155554 \\
 E &:= 52525 + 52225 + 25552 + 25252 = 155554 \\
 F &:= 55252 + 52522 + 25255 + 22525 = 155554 \\
 G &:= 52552 + 52252 + 25525 + 25225 = 155554
 \end{aligned}$$

We observe that in all the three situations the sum remains the same. Using 2 by 2 combinations of these 28 numbers, the magic sum is given by

$$S_{28 \times 28} := 108888888878 = 100000 \times 1088878 + 1088878, \quad (29)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
 1088878 &:= 22225 + 22252 + 22255 + 22525 + 22552 + 22555 + 25222 + 25225 + 25252 + 25255 + \\
 &+ 25522 + 25525 + 25552 + 25555 + 52222 + 52225 + 52252 + 52255 + 52522 + \\
 &+ 52525 + 52552 + 52555 + 55222 + 55225 + 55252 + 55522 + 55525 + 55552
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we have a **block-wise pandiagonal universal magic square** of order 28 with magic sum given in (29), where each block of order 4 is a **pandiagonal universal magic square** with equal magic sums given given in (8).

2.12.2 Blocks of Order 7

Example 2.21. *The univerrsal pandiagonal magic square of order 28 for the digits 2 and 5 written in digital form is given below in three parts:*

28x28	mgc							
5555255552	2255522555	2255222552	2522225222	5252552525	2252522525	5255252552	5222222225	5552255222
2252552525	5255222525	5555252552	2255555552	2255222555	2522222552	5252525222	2525525252	2552552522
2522222555	5252522552	2252525222	5255252525	5555222525	2255552552	2255255552	2225255222	2555255225
2255522525	2255252552	2522255552	5252522555	2252522552	5255225222	5555252525	5552252522	5225525225
5255222552	5555225222	2255552525	2255222525	2522252552	5252555552	2252522555	2552555225	5222252555
5252552552	2252555552	5255222555	5555222552	2255525222	2255252525	2522222525	2555225225	2525522225
2255225222	2522252525	5252522525	2252552552	5255255552	5555222555	2255522552	5225552555	2225225252
2222552222	5522255522	5522552255	5255522252	2525225552	5252225255	2522525525	2555525555	2225522255
5252225552	2522525255	2222525525	5522252222	5522555522	5255552255	2525222252	5525252225	5225255252
5255555522	2525252255	5252222252	2522525552	2222525255	5522225525	5522552222	5552522255	5222525522
5522225255	5522525525	5255552222	2525255522	5252225255	2522522252	2222525552	2225555252	2552252252
2522552255	2222522252	5522225552	5522525255	5255525525	2525252222	5252255522	5225225522	2555555252
2525225525	5252252222	2522555522	2222552255	5522222252	5522525552	5255525255	5222552252	5525225555
5522522252	5255525552	2525225255	5252225525	2522552222	2222555522	5522252255	2552255525	5552552225
2555522225	2225555222	2552255225	5552552555	5222525252	5525252522	5225225225	2222555552	5522222555
5525225252	5225252522	2555525225	2225522225	2552255222	5552555225	5222552555	5252252525	2522522525
5552555222	5222555225	5525252555	5225225252	2555552522	2225525225	2552222225	5255522555	2525222552
2225552522	2552225225	5552522225	5222555222	5525255225	5225252555	2555525252	5522222525	5522552552
5225255225	2555552555	2225525252	2552252522	5552525225	5222522225	5525255222	2522522552	2222525222
5222525225	5525222225	5225255222	2555555225	2225552555	2552225252	5552552522	2525252552	5252255552
2552252555	5552525252	5222552522	5525225225	5225222225	2555555222	2225555225	5522525222	5255552525
5222225555	5552222255	5225525522	2225255525	2555252225	2525555252	2552552252	5555252222	2255555522
2525552225	2552555252	5222252252	5552225555	5225522255	2225225522	2555255525	2252525552	5255225255
2225222255	2555225522	2525555525	2552552225	5222255252	5552252252	5225525555	2522255522	5252552255
5552255252	5225552252	2225225555	2555222255	2525525522	2552555525	5222252225	2255525255	2255225525
2552525522	5222255525	5552252225	5225555252	2225252252	2555225555	2525522255	5255252255	5552222522
2555252252	2525525555	2552522255	5222225522	5552255525	5225552225	2225255252	5252525525	2252552222
5225555525	2225252225	2555255252	2525552252	2552525555	5222222255	5552225522	2255222252	2522225552
108888888878	108888888878	108888888878	108888888878	108888888878	108888888878	108888888878	108888888878	108888888878
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9

5225555225	2225252555	2555225252	2525552522	2552525225	2222525555	5522222255	5522525522	5255555525	2525252225
5222225225	5552222225	5225555222	2225255225	2555252555	5252252225	2522555252	2222552252	5522225555	5522522255
2525552555	2552525252	5222252522	5552225225	5225522225	5255522255	2525225522	5252255525	2522552225	2222555252
2225222225	2555255222	2525555225	2552552555	5222225252	5522255252	5522552252	5255525555	2525222255	5252225522
5552225252	5225552522	2225225225	2555222225	2525555222	2522525522	2222555525	5522252225	5522555252	5255552252
2552555222	5222255225	5552252555	5225525252	2225252522	2525252252	5252225555	2522522255	2222525522	5522255525
2555252522	2525525225	2552522225	5222255222	5552255225	5522555525	5255552225	2525255252	5252252252	2522525555
2552225522	5552555525	5222552225	5525255252	5225252252	5555222225	2255555222	2255255225	2522252555	5252525252
2555552252	2225525555	2552222255	5552525522	5222555525	2252525252	5255252522	5555225225	2255522225	2255255222
5525255525	5225252225	2555555252	2225552252	2552225555	2522255222	5252555225	2252552555	5255225252	5555252522
5552525555	5222522255	5525225522	5225255525	2555552225	2255552522	2255225225	2522222225	5252555222	2252555225
2225552225	2552255252	5552552252	5222525555	5525222255	5255255225	5555252555	2255525252	2255252522	2522225225
5225222255	2555525522	2225555525	2552252225	5552555252	5252525225	2252522225	5255255222	5555255225	2255552555
5222555252	5525252252	5225225555	2555522255	2225525522	2255252555	2522225252	5252552522	2252525225	5255222225
5522522552	5255525222	2525252525	5252222525	2522552552	5222252222	5552255522	5225552255	2225222252	2555225552
2222552552	5522255552	5522522555	5255522552	2525225222	2525525552	2552525255	5222225525	5552252222	5225555522
5252225222	2522552525	2222522525	5522252552	5522555552	2225255522	2555252255	2525522252	2552525552	5222225255
5255555552	2525222555	5252222552	2522525222	2222552525	5552225255	5225525525	2225252222	2555255522	2525552255
5522252525	5522522525	5255552552	2525255552	5252222555	2552552255	5222222252	5552225552	5225525255	2225225525
2522522555	2222522552	5522225222	5522552525	5255522525	2555225525	2525552222	2552555522	5222252255	5552222252
2525222525	5252252552	2522555552	2222522555	5522222552	5225522252	2225225552	2555225255	2525525525	2552552222
2255252255	2522222252	5252525552	2252525255	5255225525	2555555552	2225522555	2552222552	5552525222	5222552525
5555225525	2255552222	2255255522	2522252255	5252522252	5525252525	5225222525	2555552552	2225555552	2552222555
2252522252	5255225552	5555225255	2255525525	2255252222	5552522555	5222522552	5525225222	5225252525	2555522525
2522252222	5252555522	2252552255	5255222252	5555225552	2225522525	2552252552	5552555552	5222522555	5525222552
2255525552	2255225255	2522225525	5252552222	2252555522	5225222552	2555525222	2225552525	2552222525	5552552552
5255255522	5555252255	2255522252	2255225552	2522225255	5222552552	5525255552	5225222555	2555522552	2225525222
5252525255	2252525525	5255252222	5555255522	2255552255	2552225222	5552552525	5222522525	5525252552	5225255552
10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878
10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19

									10888888878
5252255252	2522552252	2555552222	2225555522	2552252255	5552522252	5222525552	5525225255	5225225525	10888888878
5255525522	2525255525	5525225552	5225225255	2555525525	2225552222	2552255522	5552552255	5222522252	10888888878
5522252252	5522525555	5552555522	5222552255	5525222252	5225225552	2555525255	2225525525	2552252222	10888888878
2522555525	2222552225	2225525255	2552225525	5552552222	5222555522	5525252255	5225222252	2555525552	10888888878
2525225555	5252222255	5225252255	2555522252	2225525552	2552225255	5552525525	5222552222	5525255522	10888888878
5522552225	5255552252	5222525525	5525252222	5225255522	2555522255	2225522252	2552225552	5552525255	10888888878
2222522255	5522225522	2552222252	5552525552	5222525255	5525225525	5222525222	2555555522	2225552255	10888888878
2252552522	5255225225	5222555522	5552222555	5225522552	2225225222	2555252525	2525522525	2552552552	10888888878
2522255225	5252552555	2525552525	2552522525	5222252552	5552255552	5225522555	2225222552	2555225222	10888888878
2255525225	2255222225	2225222555	2555222552	2525525222	2552552525	5222222525	5552252552	5225555552	10888888878
5255252555	5555225252	5552222525	5225552552	2225255552	2555222555	2525522552	2552525222	5222252525	10888888878
5252522225	2252555222	2552522552	5222225222	5552252525	5225522525	2225252552	2555255552	2525522555	10888888878
2255225252	2522252522	2555252552	2525555552	2552522555	5222222552	5552225222	5225552525	2225222525	10888888878
5555255222	2255555225	5225525222	2225252525	2555222525	2525552552	2552555552	5222222555	5552222552	10888888878
2525525255	2552525525	5555225555	2255522255	2255225522	2522255525	5252552225	2252555252	5255252252	10888888878
2225252255	2555222252	2252552225	5255255252	5555252252	2255525555	2255222255	2522225522	5252555525	10888888878
5552225525	5225552222	2522222255	5252525522	2252555525	5255252225	5555252525	2255552252	2255225555	10888888878
2552522252	5222225552	2255555252	2255252252	2522225555	5252522255	2252525522	5255255525	5555252225	10888888878
2555252222	2525555522	5255225522	5555255525	2255552225	2255255252	2522252252	5252525555	2252522255	10888888878
5225525552	2225225255	5252552252	2252525555	5255222255	5555225522	2255555525	2255252225	2522255252	10888888878
5222255522	5552252255	2255255525	2522252225	5252555252	2252552252	5255225555	5555222255	2255525522	10888888878
5525222525	5225252552	2222522225	5522255222	5522555225	5255552555	2525225252	5252252522	2522525225	10888888878
5552522552	5222525222	5252225252	2522552522	2222525225	5522222225	5522555222	5255555225	2525252555	10888888878
2225552552	2552255552	5255555222	2525255225	5252252555	2522525252	2222552522	5522225225	5522522225	10888888878
5225225222	2555552525	5522252522	5522525225	5255522225	2525255222	5252255225	2522552555	2222525252	10888888878
5222555552	5525222555	2522555225	2222552555	5522225252	5522552522	5255525225	2525222225	5252255222	10888888878
2552252525	5552522525	2525225225	5252222225	2522555222	2222555225	5522252555	5522525252	5255552522	10888888878
2555522555	2225522552	5522552555	5255525252	2525252522	5252225225	2522522225	2222555222	5522255225	10888888878
10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878	10888888878
20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	

This magic square is also constructed with the same number as of Example 2.20. These numbers lead us to a **universal pandiagonal magic square** order 28 with same magic sum as given in (29). This magic square is constructed with blocks of order 7. These blocks are **pandiagonal magic squares** of order 7 with different magic sums resulting in a **magic square** of order 28.

2.13 Magic Square of Order 29

Example 2.22. *The universal pandiagonal magic square of order 29 for the digits 2 and 5 written in digital form is given below in three parts:*

29x29	pan	114414444133	114414444133	114414444133	114414444133	114414444133	114414444133	114414444133	114414444133
	2555225552	5525522255	2222222555	5555522225	5522525555	5225522252	5225255525	2522522525	5255225255
11441444133	2225555255	5222552225	2555255222	5525555522	2222252222	5555555552	5522525222	5225552555	5225252522
11441444133	2255522222	5522225552	2225522255	5222522555	2555222225	5525525555	222222252	5555555525	5522522525
11441444133	2222555555	5552255255	2255552225	5522252222	2225555522	5222552222	2555255552	5525525222	2222252555
11441444133	2555555225	5222222222	2222525552	5552222255	2255522555	5522222225	2225525555	5222522252	2555255525
11441444133	2225252255	5555255555	2555555255	5222252225	2222555222	5552255522	2255552222	5522255552	2225525222
11441444133	5552552252	2522255225	2225222222	5555225552	2555522255	5222222555	2222522225	5552225555	2255522252
11441444133	2252525225	5255552255	5552555555	2522255255	2225252225	5555255222	2555555522	5222252222	2222555552
11441444133	2525552552	5252252252	2252555225	5255522222	5552525552	2522222255	2225222555	5555222225	2555525555
11441444133	2255225525	5525225225	2525552255	5252255555	2252555255	5255552225	5552555222	2522255522	2225252222
11441444133	2552525522	2552252552	2255252252	5525255225	2525522222	5252225552	2252522255	5255522555	5552522225
11441444133	2522522552	5255225525	2552525225	2552252255	2255255555	5525255255	2525552225	5252255222	2252555522
11441444133	5225555252	5225225522	2522552552	5255252252	2552555225	2552222222	2255225552	5525222255	2525522555
11441444133	5555525255	5522522552	5225525525	5225225225	2522552255	5255255555	2552555255	2552252225	2255255222
11441444133	5525552522	2222255252	5555525522	5522552552	5225552252	5225255225	2522522222	5255225552	2552522255
11441444133	5222522525	2555225255	5525522552	2222225525	5555525225	5522552255	5225555555	5225255255	2522552225
11441444133	5522252555	2225552522	5222555252	2555225522	5525552552	2222252252	5555555225	5522522222	5225525552
11441444133	5552255525	2255522525	5522225255	2225522552	5222525525	2555225225	5525552255	2222255555	5555555255
11441444133	5222225222	2222552555	5552252522	2255555252	5522225522	2225552552	5222552252	2555255225	5525522222
11441444133	5555222252	2555555525	5222222525	2222525255	5552222552	2255525525	5522225225	2225552255	5222555555
11441444133	2522255552	2225225222	5555252555	2555552522	5222255252	2222525522	5552252552	2255552252	5522255225
11441444133	5255525555	5552522252	2522255525	2225222525	5555225255	2555522552	5222225525	2222525225	5552252255
11441444133	5252252222	2252555552	5255525222	5552552555	2522252522	2225255252	5555225522	2555552552	5222252252
11441444133	5525222225	2525525555	5252222252	2252555525	5255522525	5552525255	2522222552	2225225525	5555225225
11441444133	2552255522	2255252222	5525255552	2525525222	5252252555	2252552522	5255555252	5552525522	2522252552
11441444133	5255222555	2552522225	2552225555	2255222252	5525255525	2525522525	5252225255	2252522552	5255525525
11441444133	5225255222	2522555522	5255252222	2552555552	2552225222	2255252555	5525252522	2525555252	5252225522
11441444133	5522522255	5225522555	5225222225	2522525555	5255222252	2552555525	2552222252	2255225255	5525222552
11441444133	2222252225	5555555222	5522555522	5225552222	5225255552	2522525222	5255252555	2552552522	2552255252
	11441444133	11441444133	11441444133	11441444133	11441444133	11441444133	11441444133	11441444133	11441444133
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9

114414444133	114414444133	114414444133	114414444133	114414444133	114414444133	114414444133	114414444133	114414444133	114414444133	114414444133
2552522552	2552225525	2255225225	5525252255	2525555555	5252255255	2252552225	5255555222	5552555522	2522252222	2225255552
2522555252	5255225522	2552552552	2552252252	2255255225	5525222222	2525525552	5252222255	2252522555	5255522225	5552525555
5225525255	5225222552	2522525525	5255225225	2552552255	2552255555	2255255255	5525252225	2525555222	5252255522	2252552222
5555552522	5522555252	5225525522	5225252552	2522552252	5255255225	2552522222	2552225552	2255222255	5525222555	2525522225
5525522525	2222225255	5555522552	5522525525	5225525225	5225252255	2522555555	5255255255	2552552225	2552255222	2255255522
5222552555	2555252522	5525555252	2222225522	555552552	5522552252	5225555225	5225222222	2522525552	5255222255	2552522555
5522255525	2225522525	5222525255	2555222552	5525525525	2222225225	5555552255	5522555555	5225555255	5225252225	2522555222
5552225222	2255552555	5522252522	2225555252	5222525522	2555252552	5525552252	2222255225	5555522222	5522525552	5225522255
5222222252	2222555525	5552222525	2255525255	5522222552	2225525525	5222525225	2555252255	5525555555	2222255255	5555522225
5555255552	2555525222	5222252555	2222552522	5552255252	2255525522	5522252552	2225552252	5222555225	2555222222	5525525552
2522225555	2225222252	5555255525	2555522525	5222225255	2222522552	5552225525	2255525225	5522252255	2225555555	5222555255
5255552222	5552555552	2522225222	2225252555	5555252522	2555555252	5222225522	2222552552	5552252252	2255555225	5522222222
5252222225	2252525555	5255522252	5552555525	2522222525	2225225255	5555222552	2555525525	5222225225	2222552255	5552255555
5525255522	2525552222	5252255552	2252525222	5255552555	5552552522	2522255252	2225225522	5555252552	2555552252	5222255225
2552222555	2255222225	5525225555	2525522252	5252255525	2252522525	5255525255	5552522552	2522225525	2225225225	5555252255
5255255222	2552555522	2552252222	2255255552	5525225222	2525552555	5252252522	2252555252	5255525522	5552552552	2522252252
5225222255	2522522555	5255222225	2552525555	2552222252	2255255525	5525222525	2525525255	5252222552	2252525525	5255525225
5522552225	5225555222	5225255522	2522552222	5255255552	2552525222	2552252555	2255252522	5525255252	2525525522	5252252552
2222225552	5555522255	5522522555	5225522225	5225225555	2522522252	5255255525	2552522525	2552225255	2255222552	5525225525
2555255255	5525552225	2222255222	5555555522	5522552222	5225555552	5225225222	2522552555	5255252522	2552555252	2552225522
2225522222	5222525552	2555222255	5525522555	2222222225	5555525555	5522522252	5225555525	5225222525	2522525255	5255222552
2255555555	5522255255	2225552225	5222555222	2555255522	5525552222	2222255552	5555525222	5522552555	5225552522	5225255252
2222555225	5552222222	2255525552	5522222255	2225522555	5222522225	2555225555	5525522252	2222255525	5555522525	5522525255
2555552255	5222255555	2222555255	5552252225	2255555222	5522255522	2225552222	5222555552	2555225222	5525552555	2222252522
2225252252	5555255225	2555522222	5222225552	2222522255	5552222555	2255522225	5522225555	2225522252	5222555525	2555222525
5552525225	2522252255	2225255555	5555255255	2555552225	5222255222	2222555522	5552252222	2255555552	5522225222	2225552555
2252552552	5255552252	5552555225	2522222222	2225225552	5555222255	2555522555	5222222225	2222252555	5552222252	2255555525
2525525525	5252225225	2252552255	5255555555	5552555255	2522252225	2225255222	5555255522	2555552222	5222255552	2222525222
2255225522	5525252552	2525552252	5252255225	2252522222	5255525552	5552522255	2522222555	2225222225	5555225555	2555522252
114414444133	114414444133	114414444133	114414444133	114414444133	114414444133	114414444133	114414444133	114414444133	114414444133	114414444133
10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20

11441444133	11441444133	11441444133	11441444133	11441444133	11441444133	11441444133	11441444133	11441444133	11441444133
5555225222	2555552555	5222252522	2222555252	5552225522	2255552552	5522252252	2225555225	5222522222	11441444133
2522222252	2225255525	5555222525	2555525255	5222222552	2222525525	5552225225	2255552255	5522255555	11441444133
5255555552	5552525222	2522252555	2225252522	5555255252	2555525522	5222252552	2222552252	5552255225	11441444133
5252225555	2252522252	5255555525	5552522525	2522225255	2225222552	5555225525	2555525225	5222252255	11441444133
5525252222	2525555552	5252225222	2252552555	5255552522	5552555252	2522225522	2225252552	5555252252	11441444133
2552222225	2255225555	5525222252	2525555525	5252222525	2252525255	5255522552	5552525525	2522225225	11441444133
5255255522	2552552222	2552255552	2255225222	5525252555	2525552522	5252255252	2252525522	5255552552	11441444133
5225222555	2522522225	5255225555	2552522252	2552255525	2255222525	5525225255	2525522552	5252225525	11441444133
5522555222	5225555522	5225252222	2522555552	5255225222	2552552555	2552225222	2255255252	5525225522	11441444133
2222222255	5555522555	5522522225	5225525555	5225222252	2522555525	5255222525	2552525255	2552222552	11441444133
2555252225	5525555222	2222255522	5555552222	5522555552	5225525222	5225252555	2522552522	5255255252	11441444133
2225525552	5222522255	2555222555	5525522225	2222225555	5555522252	5522555525	5225522525	5225225255	11441444133
2255555255	5522252225	2225555222	5222555522	2555252222	5525555552	2222225222	5555525555	5522552522	11441444133
2222522222	5552225552	2255522255	5522222555	2225522225	5222525555	2555222252	5525555525	2222222525	11441444133
2555555555	5222255255	2222552225	5552255222	2255555522	5522252222	2225555552	5222525222	2555252555	11441444133
2225255225	5555222222	2555525552	5222222255	2222522555	5552222225	2255525555	5522222252	2225555525	11441444133
5552552255	2522255555	2225255255	5555252225	2555555222	5222255522	2222552222	5552255552	2255525222	11441444133
2252552252	5255555225	5552522222	2522225552	2225222255	5555222555	2555522225	5222225555	2222522252	11441444133
2525525225	5252252255	2252555555	5255555255	5552552225	2522255222	2225255522	5555252222	2555555552	11441444133
2255252552	5525252252	2525555225	5252222222	2252525552	5255522255	5552522555	2522222225	2225225555	11441444133
2552525525	2552225225	2255252255	5525255555	2525555255	5252252225	2252555222	5255555522	5552552222	11441444133
2522525522	5255252552	2552552252	2552255225	2255222222	5525225552	2525522255	5252222555	2252522225	11441444133
5225522552	5225225525	2522525225	5255252255	2552555555	2552255255	2255252225	5525255222	2525555522	11441444133
5555555252	5522525522	5225552552	5225252252	2522555225	5255222222	2552525552	2552222255	2255222555	11441444133
5525525255	2222222552	5555525525	5522525225	5225552255	5225255555	2522555255	5255252225	2552555222	11441444133
5222552522	2555255252	5525525522	2222252552	5555552252	5522555225	5225522222	5225225552	2522522255	11441444133
5522222525	2225525255	5222522552	2555225525	5525525225	2222252255	5555555555	5522555255	5225552225	11441444133
5552252555	2255552522	5522255252	2225525522	5222552552	2555252252	5525555225	2222222222	5555525552	11441444133
5222255525	2222522525	5552225255	2255522552	5522225525	2225525225	5222552255	2555255555	5525555255	11441444133
11441444133	11441444133	11441444133	11441444133	11441444133	11441444133	11441444133	11441444133	11441444133	11441444133
21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	

It is based on the 2 by 2 combinations of 29 numbers:

{22222, 22225, 22252, 22255, 22525, 22552, 22555, 25222, 25225, 25255, 25522, 25525, 25552, 25555, 52222, 52225, 52252, 52255, 52522, 52552, 52555, 55222, 55225, 55252, 55255, 55522, 55525, 55552, 55555}.

Let's check the sum of these numbers in three situations:

Numbers used:

$$1144133 := 22222 + 22225 + 22252 + 22255 + 22525 + 22552 + 22555 + 25222 + 25225 + 25255 + \\ + 25522 + 25525 + 25552 + 25555 + 52222 + 52225 + 52252 + 52255 + 52522 + 52552 + \\ + 52555 + 55222 + 55225 + 55252 + 55255 + 55522 + 55525 + 55552 + 55555$$

Upside-down:

$$1144133 := 22222 + 52222 + 25222 + 55222 + 52522 + 25522 + 55522 + 22252 + 52252 + 55252 + \\ + 22552 + 52552 + 25552 + 55552 + 22225 + 52225 + 25225 + 55225 + 22525 + 25525 + \\ + 55525 + 22255 + 52255 + 25255 + 55255 + 22555 + 52555 + 25555 + 55555$$

Mirror looking:

$$1111400 := 55555 + 25555 + 52555 + 22555 + 25255 + 52255 + 22255 + 55525 + 25525 + 22525 + \\ + 55225 + 25225 + 52225 + 22225 + 55552 + 25552 + 52552 + 22552 + 55252 + 52252 + \\ + 22252 + 55522 + 25522 + 52522 + 22522 + 55222 + 25222 + 52222 + 22222.$$

Using 2 by 2 combinations of these 29 numbers, the **magic sums** are given by

$$S_{29 \times 29} := 91111111102 = 100000 \times 1144133 + 1144133 \tag{30}$$

and

$$S_{29 \times 29} := 111141111400 = 100000 \times 1111400 + 1111400. \tag{31}$$

The cases of **original magic square** and **upside-down**, the **magic sums** are the same as given in (30). In case of **mirror looking**, the **magic sum** is different, and as given in (31). Even though the **magic sums** are different but the magic square given in Example 2.22 is a **universal pandiagonal magic square** of order 29.

2.14 Magic Square of Order 30

2.14.1 Blocks of Order 6

Example 2.23. *The magic square of order 30 for the digits 2 and 5 written in digital form is given below in three parts:*

30x30-mgc									
2225222252	5552555522	5552555222	5552522555	2225222255	2225255525	2522222225	5255555255	5255552222	5255525555
5552255525	2225522255	5552255222	2225522555	2225555522	5552222252	5255255552	2522522522	5255252222	2522525555
5522255525	5522255522	2255522555	2255555222	5522222255	2255522252	5225255552	5225255255	2552525555	2552552222
2255555525	2255522255	5522222555	5522255222	2255555522	5522222252	2552555552	2552522522	5225225555	5225252222
2225522252	5552222255	2225555222	5552222555	5552255522	2225555525	2522522225	5255222522	2522552222	5255225555
5552522252	2225255522	2225222555	2225255222	5552522255	5552555525	5255522225	2522255255	2522225555	2522252222
2222525222	5555252552	5555252252	5555225525	2222525225	2222552555	2252522525	5525252525	5525252522	5525225255
5525552555	2252225225	5525552252	2252225525	2252252552	5525525222	5252555252	2525225252	5252552522	2525225255
5222252555	5222252552	2555525525	2555552252	5222225225	2555525222	5252255252	5252252525	2525525255	2525552522
2555552555	2555525225	5222225525	5222252252	2555552552	5222225222	2525555252	2525525252	5252225255	5252252522
2252225222	5525525225	2252252252	5525525525	5525552552	2252252555	2525222525	5252525252	2525252522	5252525255
5555225222	2222552552	2222525525	2222552252	5555225225	5555252555	5525222525	2252552525	2252525255	2252552522
2522222222	5255555225	5255552255	5255525522	2522222552	2522255555	2222222252	5555555522	5555555222	5555522555
5255255555	2522522552	5255252255	2522525522	2522555225	5255222222	5522555525	2255222255	5522555222	2255222555
5225255555	5225255225	2552525522	2552552255	5225222552	2552522222	5225555525	5225555522	2552222555	2552255222
2552555555	2552522552	5225225522	5225252255	2552555225	5225222222	2552255525	2552222255	5225522555	5225555222
2522522222	5255222552	2522552255	5255225522	5255255225	2522555555	2255222252	5522522255	2255255222	5522522555
5255522222	2522255225	2522225522	2522252255	5255522552	5255555555	5555522252	2222255522	2222222555	2222255222
2252522225	5525255255	5525252222	5525225555	2252522522	2252555552	2225225222	5552552552	5552552252	5552525525
5252555552	2525222522	5252552222	2525225555	2525255255	5252522225	5552252555	2225525225	5552252252	2225525525
5252255552	5252255255	2525525555	2525552222	5252222522	2525522225	5522252555	5522252552	2255525525	2255552252
2525555552	2525522522	5252225555	5252252222	2525555255	5252222225	2255552555	2255525225	5522225525	5522252252
2525222225	5252522522	2525252222	5252525555	5252555255	2525255552	2225525222	5552225225	2225552252	5552225525
5525222225	2252555255	2252525555	2252552222	5525222522	5525255552	5552525222	2225252552	2225225525	2225252252
2222222252	5555555522	5555555222	5555522555	2222222255	2222255525	2222522222	5555255225	5555252255	5555225522
5522555525	2255222255	5522555222	2255222555	2255255522	5522522252	5525555555	2252222552	5525552255	2252225522
5225555525	5225555522	2552222555	2552255222	5225522255	2552222252	5222255555	5222255225	2555525522	2555552255
2552255525	2552222255	5225522555	5225555222	2552255522	5225522252	2555555555	2555522552	5222225522	5222252255
2255222252	5522522255	2255255222	5522522555	5522555522	2255255525	2252222222	5525522552	2252252255	5525525522
5555522252	2222255522	2222222555	2222255222	5555522255	5555555525	5555222222	2222555225	2222525522	2222552255
11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10

2522222522	2522255552	2222225222	555552552	555552252	555525525	2222225225	2222252555	2222522525	5555252525
2522555255	5255222225	5522552555	2255225225	5522552252	2255225525	2255252552	5522525222	5525555252	2252225252
5225222522	2552522225	5225552555	5225552552	2552225525	2552252252	5225525225	2552225222	5222255252	5222252525
2552555255	5225222225	2552252555	2552225225	5225525525	5225552252	2552252552	5225525222	2555555252	2555525252
5255255255	2522555552	2255225222	5522525225	2255252252	5522525525	5522552552	2255252555	2252222525	5525525252
5255522522	5255555552	5555525222	2222252552	2222225525	2222252252	5555525225	5555525555	5555222525	2222552525
2252525252	2252555252	2225222222	5552555225	5552552255	5552525522	2225222552	2225255555	2522222522	5255555522
2525252525	5252522525	5552255555	2225522552	5552252255	2225525522	2225555225	5552222222	5255255525	2522522255
5252225252	2525522525	5522255555	5522255225	2255525522	2255552255	5522222552	2255522222	5225255525	5225255522
2525552525	5252222525	2255555555	2255522552	5522225522	5522252255	2255555225	5522222222	2552555525	2552522255
5252552525	2525255252	2225522222	5552222552	2225552255	5552225522	5552255225	2225555555	2522522522	5255222255
5525225252	5525255252	5552522222	2225255225	2225225522	2225252255	5552522552	5552555555	5255522252	2522255522
2222222255	2222255525	2222522225	5555255255	5555252222	5555225555	2222522522	2222555552	2252525222	5525252552
2255255522	5522522252	5525555552	2252222522	5525552222	2252225555	2252255255	5525522225	5252552555	2525225225
5225522255	2552222252	5222255552	5222255255	2555525555	2555552222	5222222522	2555522225	5252252555	5252252552
2552255522	5225522252	2555555552	2555522522	5222225555	5222252222	2555555255	5222222225	2525552555	2525525225
5522555522	2255255525	2252222225	5525522522	2252252222	5525525555	5525555255	2252255552	2525225222	5252525225
5555522255	5555555525	5555222225	2222555255	2222525555	2222555222	5555222522	5555255552	5525225222	2252552552
2225225225	2225252555	2522222525	5255552525	5255552522	5255525255	2522225252	2522255252	2222222222	5555555225
2225552552	5552225222	5255255252	2522525252	5255252522	2522525255	2522552525	5255222525	5522555555	2255222552
5522225225	2255525222	5225255252	5225252525	2552525255	2552552522	5225225252	2552522525	5225555555	5225555225
2255552552	5522225222	2552555252	2552525252	5225225255	5225252522	2552552525	5225222525	2552255555	2552222552
5552252552	2225552555	2522522525	5255225252	2522552522	5255225255	5255252525	2522555252	2255222222	5522522552
5552525225	5552552555	5255522525	2522252525	2522225255	2522252522	5255525252	5255555252	5555522222	2222255225
2222522552	2222555555	2252522252	5525255522	5525255222	5525222555	2252522255	2252555525	2225222225	5552555255
2252255225	5525522222	5252555525	2525222255	5252555222	2525222555	2525255522	5252522252	5552255552	2225522522
5222222552	2555522222	5252255525	5252255522	2525522555	2525555222	5252222255	2525522252	5522255552	5522255255
2555555225	5222222222	2525555525	2525522255	5252222555	5252255222	2525555522	5252222252	2255555552	2255522522
5525555225	2252255555	2525222252	5252522255	2525255222	5252522555	5252555522	2525255525	2225522225	5552222522
5555222552	5555255555	5525222252	2252555522	2252522555	2252555222	5525222255	5525255525	5552522225	2225255255
11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655
11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20

										11666666655
5555252522	5555225255	2222525252	2222555252	2252522222	5525255225	5525252255	5525225522	2252522552	2252555555	11666666655
5525552522	2252225255	2252252525	5525522525	5252555555	2525222552	5252552255	2525225522	2525255225	5252522222	11666666655
2555525255	2555552522	5222225252	2555522525	5252255555	5252255225	2525525522	2525552255	5252222552	2525522222	11666666655
5222225255	5222252522	2555552525	5222222525	2525555555	2525522552	5252225522	5252252255	2525555225	5252222222	11666666655
2252252522	5525525255	5525552525	2252255252	2525222222	5252522552	2525252255	5252525522	5252555225	2525255555	11666666655
2222525255	2222552522	5555225252	5555255252	5525222222	2252555225	2252525522	2252552255	5525222552	5525255555	11666666655
5255555222	5255522555	2522222255	2522255525	2222222225	5555555255	5555552222	5555525555	2222222522	2222255552	11666666655
5255255222	2522252255	2522255522	5255222252	5522255552	2255222522	5522255222	2255225555	2255255255	5522252225	11666666655
2552522555	2552555222	5225222255	2552522252	5225555552	5225555255	2552225555	2552252222	5225522522	2552222225	11666666655
5225222555	5225255222	2552555522	5225222252	2552255552	2552222522	5225525555	5225552222	2552255255	5225522225	11666666655
2522555222	5255222555	5255255522	2522555525	2255222225	5522252252	2255252222	5522252555	5522555255	2255255552	11666666655
2522222555	2522255222	5255522255	5255555255	5555222225	2222255255	2222225555	2222252222	5555225222	5555555552	11666666655
5525252252	5525225525	2252525225	2252552555	2225222525	5552552525	5552552522	5552525255	2225222525	2225255252	11666666655
5252552252	2525225525	2525252552	5252525222	5552255252	2225525252	5552252522	2225525255	2225552525	5552222525	11666666655
2525525525	2525552252	5252225225	2525525222	5522255252	5522252525	2255525255	2255552522	5522225252	2255522525	11666666655
5252225525	5252252252	2525552552	5252225222	2255555252	2255525252	5522225255	5522252522	2255552525	5522222525	11666666655
2525252252	5252525525	5252552552	2525252555	2225522525	5552225252	2225552522	5552225255	5552252525	2225555252	11666666655
2252525525	2252552252	5525225225	5525252555	5552522525	2225252525	2225225255	2225252522	5552525252	5552555252	11666666655
5555552255	5555525522	2222222552	2222255555	2222522252	5555255522	5555255222	5555222555	2222522255	2222555525	11666666655
5522552255	2255225522	2255255225	5522522222	5525555525	2252222255	5525555222	2252222555	2252255522	5525522252	11666666655
2552225522	2552252255	5225522552	2552222222	5222255525	5222255522	2555522555	2555555222	5222222555	2555522252	11666666655
5225525522	5225552255	2552255225	5225522222	2555555525	2555522255	5222222555	5222255222	2555555522	5222222252	11666666655
2255252255	5522252552	5522555225	2255255555	2252222252	5525522255	2252255222	5525522555	5525555522	2252255525	11666666655
2222225522	2222252255	5555522552	5555555555	5555222252	2222555522	2222522555	2222555222	5555222255	5555255525	11666666655
5552552222	5552525555	2225222522	2225255552	2522225222	5255552552	5255552252	5255525525	2522225225	2522252555	11666666655
5552252222	2225525555	2225555255	5552222225	5255252555	2522252225	5255252252	2522252525	2522552552	5255225222	11666666655
2255525555	2255552222	5522222522	2255522225	5225252555	5225252552	2552525525	2552552252	5225225225	2552525222	11666666655
5522225555	5522252222	2255555255	5522222225	2552552555	2552525225	5225225525	5225252252	2552552552	5225225222	11666666655
2225552222	5552225555	5552255255	2225555552	2522252222	5255222525	2522552252	5255225525	5255252552	2522552555	11666666655
2225225555	2225252222	5552522522	5552555552	5255525222	2522252552	2522225525	2522252252	5255525225	5255552555	11666666655
11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655
21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	

It is based on the 2 by 2 combinations of 30 numbers:

{22222, 22225, 22252, 22255, 22522, 22525, 22552, 22555, 25222, 25225, 25252, 25255, 25522, 25525, 25555, 52222, 52252, 52255, 52522, 52525, 52552, 52555, 55222, 55225, 55252, 55255, 55522, 55525, 55552, 55555}.

Let's divide the above 30 numbers in five groups of 6 each with **equal sums**:

$$A := 22255 + 55522 + 22555 + 55222 + 22252 + 55525 = 233331$$

$$B := 25222 + 52555 + 25525 + 52252 + 25225 + 52552 = 233331$$

$$C := 22222 + 55555 + 22552 + 55225 + 25522 + 52255 = 233331$$

$$D := 22522 + 55255 + 22225 + 55552 + 25555 + 52222 = 233331$$

$$E := 22525 + 55252 + 52522 + 25255 + 25252 + 52525 = 233331$$

These groups are considered in such a way that they are upside-down in itself. Let's check only the **Mirror looking** case:

$$A := 55522 + 22255 + 55222 + 22555 + 55525 + 22252 = 233331$$

$$B := 52555 + 25222 + 52252 + 25525 + 52552 + 25225 = 233331$$

$$C := 55555 + 22222 + 55225 + 22552 + 52255 + 25522 = 233331$$

$$D := 55255 + 22522 + 55552 + 22225 + 52222 + 25555 = 233331$$

$$E := 55252 + 22525 + 25255 + 52522 + 52525 + 25252 = 233331$$

We observe that in all the three situations the sum remains the same. Using 2 by 2 combinations of these 30 numbers, the magic sum is given by

$$S_{30 \times 30} := 116666666655 = 100000 \times 1166655 + 1166655, \quad (32)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} 1166655 := & 22222 + 22225 + 22252 + 22255 + 22522 + 22525 + 22552 + 22555 + 25222 + 25225 + \\ & + 25252 + 25255 + 25522 + 25525 + 25555 + 52222 + 52252 + 52255 + 52522 + 52525 + \\ & + 52552 + 52555 + 55222 + 55225 + 55252 + 55255 + 55522 + 55525 + 55552 + 55555. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we have a **block-wise universal magic square** of order 30 with magic sum given in (32), where each block of order 6 is a **universal magic square** with equal **magic sums** given in eqrefeq18a2.

2.14.2 Blocks of Order 5

Example 2.24. *The magic square of order 30 for the digits 1 and 8 is given below in three parts:*

30X30-mgc									
2555225552	2522552555	5225522525	2522252222	5225255552	2222225222	5525552225	2555552552	2222525522	5552222222
5255525225	5222552225	5255252555	5225222525	5552525555	2522522252	555555525	2222222255	5555225525	5222222552
2252552255	5255552552	2225522255	2552552555	2522522525	2555255552	5255225222	5522525552	5555552222	2225225522
5222225222	2252552252	5255525525	5522255222	2552252555	5255222525	5222522252	2552555525	5225552225	5522522555
5555252252	255555525	2252525225	5255525522	2255522555	2255252555	2552522525	2225525222	2552225552	5225222255
2522222222	2225225225	5555225552	2252552552	5255522552	5552255522	5525252555	2552222525	5522255525	2255252225
5222555255	5552555555	2522252552	2225252225	2252525525	5255555252	2222522225	2252252555	2255222525	2255525552
5255225555	2225522222	2555255225	5552525525	2522222255	2252525522	5255522522	5222252222	5525552555	5525222525
2552222225	2552555552	5522255555	5222552255	2555225522	5552555222	2252522552	525555255	2555525555	2222252555
2222255522	2255252222	2552222252	2255555225	2225552252	5222522552	2555222555	2252555252	5255522222	5555255552
2555522555	5555522225	5525225555	2255225222	5552252255	5522225225	2225555252	5222555522	2252522522	5255555555
5555522525	5555255522	5522552222	2252255552	5525255525	2222552252	2255552552	5522222522	2225522225	2252555255
5225252555	5522522525	2225222225	5225525555	5525522252	2252225552	5222225225	5552225525	225555255	5522252222
5522252225	2255522255	5552255222	2222522555	5222255522	2555522225	5555252222	2225225555	2522255552	5552522252
5525522522	2222255255	5555522222	5522555555	5225555225	5225252255	2522552252	5255225225	2552552552	2552225525
2252222255	5525555222	2222222555	5555555522	5522522225	5225552222	5225225555	2522555552	5255222252	2552525222
2255555222	5552222555	2222555522	5222222225	2555552222	5555225555	2225255552	2522222252	5552525222	2555255525
2522525255	2552252522	5225222552	5525555525	2225255222	2225525525	2522255555	2222552255	2252225225	5255255225
2552552522	5225525522	2252225222	5555222255	5222552552	2225222222	5552255225	5525252252	2522555555	5252222225
5522525525	5525222252	2555552225	2555225225	5555255255	2255555555	2255252255	5225222222	5252255522	2525555222
2255255552	5222225552	5552552252	2555522522	5522222222	2552255225	5225555255	5252222555	2525522255	2522255252
2222555525	2522252255	5222255252	2225555255	2552555555	5522522522	5252255222	2525552225	2225222552	5555525255
2225255225	2222522552	5222522522	5255222222	5555555252	5252222255	2525525552	5555225522	2222225255	5225552522
5552225522	2555255252	2522555255	2222222552	5252252225	2525555525	2555525525	5525525255	5522552522	2252252255
5552522552	5225222522	5525525522	5252225552	2525525222	5222225252	2252225255	5555525222	5525255225	2522555522
5225555252	2252225525	5252255525	2525522252	2222252225	5525225255	2222252522	2255255555	5225222555	2225525555
5525252552	5252225222	2525555552	5552252252	2255225255	5525552522	2552222222	5225555222	5222552222	2222522522
5252222252	2525525555	2255552255	2552225255	2252252522	2552555255	5522522255	2555222225	5552255252	5222552252
2525552222	5522255225	2552525255	5525252522	5255222522	5555552225	5552555522	2255522552	2555252255	2555525225
2225555555	5255225255	2255252522	2522555252	2222225552	2522222555	5522225522	5552555225	5222252252	5525552552
11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10

2255525555	2252555555	5255552252	5222555222	2252255255	2225522522	5522222555	2525525225	5252225525	2552555225
2222555555	5552255552	2252555225	2225522555	5525522222	5522255255	2255555522	5252225522	2552252255	2225255252
2555555252	5222255225	2222522252	5522255522	2222255555	2255522222	5552222225	2255252252	2522222522	5222525555
2522222552	5555222522	2555552255	2255522225	5555555225	5552255555	2222552222	5552555255	2225555552	2522525552
5225555522	5552555252	2225255255	5552252222	5522552255	2222555225	5222225555	5522222252	5255252225	5525555552
2522555222	5225222225	2555222522	2222525555	5225552252	5222252255	2555555552	2552522255	2222222252	5555522555
5525222255	5255222555	2522552222	5222255552	5225225225	2555552252	5555222252	5555525222	5522555522	5225522552
5552252225	2252255222	2552555522	2555522252	2522552552	5555225225	2225225222	5225522225	5225255252	2222252252
2252222525	2222522255	5525522555	5555225222	5255225525	2225252552	2522255525	2522522522	5555525225	5552252522
5555552555	5525522525	5222255222	2225255525	2552525522	2522225525	5552525552	5522552552	2222552522	5522225255
2225222252	5522552555	2222222525	2522225552	2552222552	5552525522	2555252225	5222252522	2255525255	2252255525
5255555225	2522225222	5225552555	5552552225	2255255252	2555222552	5222522255	5552225255	5525525552	2525552255
2252522222	5255552255	5552555525	2555222255	5525222522	5222555252	2225555222	2222252225	2525552252	5252252552
2555225222	5222555525	2225525552	5255552555	5252225255	2525522525	2252552522	2252222222	5525255255	2255222522
2255225522	5525222552	2252255252	2525552522	2252522525	5255525255	5252252555	2225555522	5222522555	2555255222
2552255525	2255225552	5525252225	2252525255	2525552555	5252252522	5255522525	5222525525	2555252552	5552525225
5222525552	2225552225	5522222255	5252222525	5255552522	2252552555	2525525255	5525555225	2252255555	5525222222
5252252222	2525555522	5222522222	2222222522	5552222255	2552552225	5522555255	5525255252	5255522225	2252525222
2525522555	2555255255	5225225255	5525555252	2255552225	5255225552	5555522522	2222552555	2255222552	5255555522
5552522522	5225525255	5255252522	2252222552	5522225552	2522555525	2222255252	2522222525	5552252555	2552225522
5522525255	2522552522	5555552552	5525225522	2225555525	5225225222	5525522552	5555252255	2225222525	2255552555
5225252522	2222225225	2552225555	2255225525	5222525222	5225522252	2252225522	2255555552	2555555225	5555222525
5525552252	2552552222	5552225222	2552252552	2555222252	5522555552	5525225525	5225255222	5522225555	5222255555
5255222225	2255522252	5555255555	2552525225	5552555552	5555525555	2255252552	2552222555	5225522255	2225552222
5522255552	2555522222	2255525525	5255252252	2522225555	2222252222	2552225225	2225255555	2552555222	5522552225
5222255255	5522252552	2522225522	2522552255	2225252222	5525522225	2552552252	2555522552	5555222222	5255222255
2225525225	2225225525	5522522552	5225255225	5555222225	2252255522	5255252255	2555225555	5222225522	2555552555
5555252552	5555525522	2255225225	5225555555	2555555522	5525222555	2522555225	5255255525	5552552222	2222525525
2222225525	2552252252	5252255552	5522522222	5222222555	2255255222	5225255555	2252525552	2522525222	2522222225
2552552255	5252225555	2525522225	5555555255	2222555222	2552222255	5225522222	5255552222	2252555525	5225222252
11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655
11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20

										11666666655
5555222552	5552522225	5522522252	2552255522	2255255525	5525252255	5255255252	2225252522	5222225255	5555522255	11666666655
2555252222	5225525222	2255222225	5525225552	2252252252	2552522522	2522252522	2555525255	5522555222	2525552552	11666666655
5225255525	5525252222	2252252225	5525525225	2552255255	5552552522	5555225255	5225522555	2525525525	5252222552	11666666655
2252225555	5525522255	2222252552	2255222222	2555252522	2225225255	5225255522	2525525522	5252255252	5525225225	11666666655
2222255222	5555525525	5525255555	5222552522	2522225255	2522522225	2525522552	5252222522	2252252552	2555222222	11666666655
5522525522	2252255225	2225552522	5552525255	5255252222	2525555252	5252255255	5525525525	5222555555	2255525222	11666666655
5525552255	5522252522	2555225255	2552525555	2525522522	5252222222	2222225522	2225555225	5552255525	2552255222	11666666655
2255552522	5222525255	2552255552	2525555255	5252255555	5555522552	5522252255	2222525552	2255222555	5522555525	11666666655
2225525255	2255222252	2525522222	5252255225	5522555252	2255552252	5222252225	5525255522	5225525552	5225252222	11666666655
5525225222	2525555555	5252252255	5225522522	5552225225	2555522255	2252222225	5225252225	2522525555	5255255255	11666666655
2525555225	5252252252	5225255255	2222552552	5555255222	5525552222	2522522255	5255255552	2552522222	5225525525	11666666655
5252225225	2522522222	5222225525	2225222555	2222225555	5255255222	2552522252	2552255555	5225225522	2555525222	11666666655
5255255555	2555525522	2522255522	5555555552	2552522555	2552225222	2255255225	2522522552	5555252522	2222525255	11666666655
2552255252	2552522552	5255225522	2522525525	5225252552	5225525225	5522552252	5555522555	2222255225	5525555555	11666666655
5552522255	2522252225	2225225552	5555255525	2555525222	5222222252	2222555552	5552225555	2255552222	5522222225	11666666655
2522252252	2225252255	5555255225	2555555555	5222222222	2222555255	5552222522	2255555252	5522222552	2225525522	11666666655
2255255255	2552222522	2552555252	5255222552	2522525522	5225225525	5225552552	5522525225	5555552252	2222252255	11666666655
5225555552	5555222555	5522252252	2255525522	5555522252	2255225555	2555525552	5552552552	2555222525	5222252555	11666666655
2252522252	5522525555	2555555222	2225552255	5522225525	2222255552	2552252222	5222255525	2522225225	5552522525	11666666655
5255522555	2252555552	5555552222	5222222255	5222555225	2225552552	5525525555	2552522225	2222525222	2225252252	11666666655
2552525525	5255555222	2252525555	2222222225	2222552225	2555255555	5222525225	2252252222	5255255522	5552222252	11666666655
5522252555	5255252552	5255522255	2252552222	5525555522	5552225552	5552522222	2555252252	5525222225	2522522555	11666666655
2555522525	22255552555	2522525225	5255552225	2252522225	2252222555	2255555525	2522255255	5552552255	2255255522	11666666655
2222522222	5222222525	5222552555	5225252252	5255525552	2252555522	5525255222	5522225222	2225222522	2522255225	11666666655
5222522225	5552255255	2222522525	2555252555	5225552255	5255555525	2252522555	2255222255	2225522252	5555255252	11666666655
5555525552	2555255522	2255522522	5552222525	5552552555	5522555225	5255525222	2252555222	2552252225	5222555552	11666666655
2522552225	2222255525	5552522555	5522252522	2255522525	2522252555	5555555555	5255522252	2252522255	2552525552	11666666655
5222222522	5225225552	5525525222	2522255222	2225522552	5522222525	2225252555	2222222222	5255555552	2252552225	11666666655
5552252552	2222555252	5225555525	2252222252	2225222255	5222525522	2225522525	5555252555	5525555255	5255525555	11666666655
2225255522	2255525225	5552222552	5522525222	5525255552	5555252225	2555225525	5222522525	2555552555	2252222522	11666666655
11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655	11666666655
21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	

This magic square is also constructed with the same number as of Example ???. These numbers lead us to a **universal magic square** with same **magic sum** as given in (32). The magic square given in Example 2.24 is constructed based on blocks of order 5. These blocks are **pandiagonal magic squares** of order 5 with different magic sums resulting in a **magic square** of order 30.

2.15 Magic Square of Order 31

Example 2.25. *The magic square of order 31 for the digits 2 and 5 written in digital form is given below in three parts:*

31x31	pan	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180
121919219180	2555225552	5252522255	2252222555	5525522225	2222225555	5555522225	5522555525	5225522525	5225225255	2522522552
121919219180	2225552525	5222552225	2555255222	5252555522	2252252222	5525555552	2222225222	5555525555	5522552522	5225555252
121919219180	2255522522	5522225552	2225522255	5222522555	2555222225	5252525555	2252222252	5525555525	2222222525	5555525255
121919219180	2222555255	5552252525	2255552225	5522255222	2225555522	5222552222	2555255552	5252525222	2252252555	5525552522
121919219180	2555522222	5222222522	2222525552	5552222255	2255522555	5522222225	2225525555	5222522252	2555255525	5252522525
121919219180	2225255555	5555255255	2555552525	5222252225	2222555222	5552255522	2255552222	5522255552	2225525222	5222552555
121919219180	5552555225	2522222222	2225222522	5555225552	2555522255	5222222555	2222522225	5552225555	2255522252	5522255525
121919219180	2252552255	5255555555	5552555255	2522252525	2225252225	5555255222	2555555522	5222252222	2222555552	5552225222
121919219180	2525552252	5252255225	2252522222	5255522522	5552525552	2522222255	2225222555	5555222225	2555525555	5222222252
121919219180	2255225225	5525252255	2525555555	5252255255	2252552525	5255552225	5552555222	2522255522	2225252222	5555255552
121919219180	252552552	2552252252	2255255225	5525222222	2525522522	5252225552	2252522255	5255522555	5552522225	2522225555
121919219180	2522525525	5255225225	2552552255	2552255555	2255255255	5525252525	2525552225	5252255222	2252555222	5255522222
121919219180	5225525522	5225252552	2522552252	5255255225	2552522222	2552222522	2255225552	5525222255	2525522555	5252222225
121919219180	5555522552	5522525525	5225525225	5225252255	2522555555	5255255255	2552552525	2552252225	2255255222	5525255522
121919219180	5525555252	2222225522	5555525552	5522552252	5225555225	5225222222	2522522522	5255225552	2552222555	2552222555
121919219180	5252525255	2252222552	5525525525	2222225225	5555522555	5522555555	5225555255	5225252525	2522552225	5255255222
121919219180	5222552522	2555255252	5252525522	2252252552	5525552252	2222255225	5555522222	5522522522	5225525552	5225222255
121919219180	5522222525	2225525255	5222522552	2555225525	5252525225	2252252255	5525555555	2222255255	5555525255	5522552225
121919219180	5552252555	2255552522	5522255252	2225525522	5222552552	2555252252	5252555225	2252222222	5525522522	2222225552
121919219180	5222255525	2222522525	5552225255	2255522552	5522225525	2225525225	5222552255	2555255555	5252555255	2252252525
121919219180	5555225222	2555552555	5222252522	2222555252	5552225522	2255552552	5522252252	2225555225	5222522222	2555222522
121919219180	2522222252	2225255525	5555222525	2555525255	5222222552	2222255225	5552225225	2255552255	5522255555	2225555255
121919219180	5255555552	5552525222	2522252555	2225252522	5555255252	2555525522	5222252552	2222552252	5552255225	2255522222
121919219180	5252225555	2252522252	5255555525	5552522525	2522225255	2225222552	5555225525	2252222222	5525522525	2222255555
121919219180	5525252222	2525555552	5252225222	2252552555	5255552522	5552555252	2522225522	2225252552	5555252252	2555555225
121919219180	2552222225	2255225555	5525222252	2525555525	5252222525	2252525255	5255522552	5552525525	2522225225	2225252255
121919219180	5255255522	2552552222	2552255552	2255225222	5525252555	2525552522	5252255252	2252525522	5255552552	5552552252
121919219180	5225222555	2522522225	5255225555	2552522252	2552255525	2255222525	5525225255	2525522552	5252225525	2252525225
121919219180	5522555222	5225555522	5225252222	2522555552	5255225222	2552552555	2552252522	2255255252	5525225522	2525552552
121919219180	2222222255	5555522555	5522522225	5225525555	5225222252	2522555525	5255222525	2552222552	2552222552	2255225525
	2252252225	5525555222	2222255522	5555552222	5522555552	5225525222	5225252555	2522552522	5255255252	2552525522
	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10

121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180
5255225525	2552525225	2552252255	2255255555	5525255255	2525552525	5252252225	2252555222	5255555522	5552552222	2522255552
5225225522	2522552552	5255252252	2552555225	2552222222	2255222522	5525225552	2525522255	5252222555	2252522225	5255525555
5522522552	5225525525	5225225225	2522552255	5255255555	2552555255	2552252525	2255252225	5525255222	2525555522	5252252222
2222255252	5555525522	5522552552	5225552252	5225255225	2522522222	5255222522	2552525552	2552222255	2255222555	5525222225
2252225255	5525522552	2222225525	5555525225	5522552255	5225555555	5225255255	2522552525	5255252225	2552555222	2552255522
2555252522	5252555252	2252225522	5525552552	2222252252	5555555225	5522522222	5225522522	5225225552	2522522255	5255222555
2225522525	5222525255	2555222552	5252525525	2252225225	5525552255	2222255555	5555555255	5522552525	5225552225	5225255222
2255552555	5522252522	2225555252	5222525522	2555252552	5252552252	2252255225	5525522222	2222222522	5555525552	5522522255
2222555525	5552222525	2255525255	5522222552	2225525525	5222525225	2555252255	5252555555	2252255255	5525552525	2222252225
2555525222	5222252555	2222552522	5552255252	2255525522	5522252552	2225552252	5222555225	2555222222	5252522522	2252225552
2225222252	5555255525	2555522525	5222222525	2222522552	5552225525	2255525225	5522252255	2225555555	5222555255	2555252525
5552555552	2522225222	2225252555	5555252522	2555555252	5222225522	2222552552	5552252252	2255555225	5522222222	2225522522
2252525555	5255522252	5552555525	2522222525	2225225255	5555222552	2555525525	5222225225	2222255225	5552255555	2255555255
2525552222	5252255552	2252525222	5255552555	5552552522	2522255252	2225225522	5555252552	2555552252	5222255225	2222522222
2255222225	5525225555	2525522252	5252255525	2252522525	5255525255	5552522552	2522225525	2225225225	5555252255	2555555555
2552555522	2552252222	2255255552	5525225222	2525552555	5252252522	2252555252	5255525522	5552552552	2522252252	2225255225
2522522555	5255222225	2552525555	2552222252	2255255525	5525222525	2525525255	5252222552	2252525525	5255525225	5552552255
5225555222	5225255522	2522552222	5255255552	2552525222	2552225255	2255252522	5525255252	2525525522	5252252552	2252552252
5555522255	5522522555	5225522225	5225225555	2522522252	5255255525	2552522525	2552225255	2255222552	5525225525	2525525225
5525552225	2222255222	5555555522	5522552222	5225555552	5225225222	2522552555	5255252522	2552555252	2552225522	2255252552
5252525552	2252222255	5525522555	2222222225	5555525555	5522522252	5225555525	5225222525	2522525255	5255222552	2552525525
5222552525	2555252225	5252555222	2252255522	5525552222	2222255552	5555525222	5522552555	5225552522	5225255252	2522525522
5522222522	2225525552	5222522255	2555222555	5252522225	2252225555	5525522252	2222255525	5555522525	5522525255	5225522552
5552252525	2255552525	5522252225	2225555222	5222555522	2555252222	5252555552	2252225222	5525552555	2222252522	5555555252
5222222222	2222522252	5552225552	2255522255	5522222555	2225522225	5222525555	2555222252	5252555525	2252222525	5525525255
5555255555	2555555255	5222252525	2222552225	5552255222	2255555522	5522252222	2225555552	5222525222	2555252555	5252552522
2522255225	2225222222	5555222522	2555525552	5222222255	2222522555	5552222225	2255525555	5522222252	2225555525	5222522525
5255552255	5552555555	2522255255	2225252525	5555252225	2555555222	5222255522	2222555222	5552255552	2255525222	5522252555
5252252252	2252555225	5255522222	5552522522	2522225552	2225222255	5555222555	2555522225	5222225555	2222522252	5552255525
5525225225	2525552255	5252255555	2252555255	5255552525	5552552225	2522255222	2225255522	5555252222	2555555552	5222225222
2552252552	2255252252	5525255225	2525522222	5252222522	2252525552	5255522255	5552522555	2522222225	2225225555	5555222252
121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180
11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21

121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180
2225225222	5555252555	2555552522	5222255252	2222525522	5552252552	2255552252	5522255225	2225522222	5222522522	121919219180
5552522252	2522255525	2225222525	5555225255	2555522552	5222225525	2222525225	5552252255	2255555555	5522255255	121919219180
2252555552	5255525222	5552552555	2522252522	2225255252	5555225522	2555552552	5222252252	2222555225	5552222222	121919219180
2525525555	5252222252	2252555525	5255522525	5552525255	2522222552	2225225525	5555225225	2555552255	5222255555	121919219180
2255252222	5525255552	2525525222	5252252555	2252552522	5255555252	5552525522	2522252552	2225252252	5555255225	121919219180
2552522225	2552225555	2255222252	5525255525	2525522525	5252225255	2252522552	5255525525	5552525225	2522252255	121919219180
2522555522	5255252222	2552555552	2552225222	2255252555	5525252522	2525555252	5252225522	2252552552	5255552252	121919219180
5225522555	5225222225	2522525555	5255222252	2552555525	2552222525	2255225255	5525222552	2525525525	5252225225	121919219180
5555552222	5522555522	5225552222	5225255552	2522525222	5255252555	2552552522	2552255252	2255225522	5525252552	121919219180
5525522255	2222222555	5555522225	5522525555	5225522252	5225255525	2522522525	5255225255	2552522552	2552225525	121919219180
5252552225	2252255222	5525555522	2222252222	5555555552	5522525222	5225552555	5225252522	2522555252	5255225522	121919219180
5222525552	2555222255	5252522555	2252222225	5525525555	2222222252	5555555525	5522522525	5225525255	5225222552	121919219180
5522252525	2225552225	5222555222	2555255522	5252552222	2252255552	5525525222	2222252555	5555552522	5522555252	121919219180
5552225222	2255525552	5522222255	2225522555	5222522225	2555225555	5252522252	2252255525	5525522525	2222252255	121919219180
5222255255	2222552525	5552252225	2255555222	5522255522	2225552222	5222555552	2555225222	5252552555	2252252222	121919219180
5555222222	2555522522	5222225552	2222522255	5552222555	2255522225	5522225555	2225522252	5222555525	2555222525	121919219180
2522255555	2225255255	5555252525	2555552225	5222255222	2222555522	5552252222	2255555552	5522225222	2225552555	121919219180
5255555225	5552522222	2522222522	2225225552	5555222255	2555522555	5222222225	2222525555	5552222252	225555525	121919219180
5252252255	2252555555	5255555255	5552552525	2522252225	2225255222	5555255522	2555552222	5222255552	2222525222	121919219180
5525252252	2525555225	5252222222	2252522522	5255525552	5552522255	2522222555	2225222225	5555225555	2555522252	121919219180
2552225225	2255252255	5525255555	2525555255	5252252525	2252552225	5255555222	5552555522	2522252222	2225255552	121919219180
5255252552	2552552252	25522255225	2255222222	5525222522	2525525552	5252222255	2252522555	5255522225	5552525555	121919219180
5225225525	2522252225	5255252255	2552555555	2552255255	2255252525	5525252225	2525555222	5252255522	2252552222	121919219180
5522525522	5225552552	5225252252	2522555225	5255222222	2552522522	2552225552	2255222255	5525222555	2525522225	121919219180
2222222552	5555525525	5522525225	5225552255	5225255555	2522555255	5255252525	2552552225	2552255222	2255255522	121919219180
2252255252	5525525522	2222252552	5555552252	5522555225	5225522222	5225222522	2522255552	5255222255	2552522555	121919219180
2555225255	5252522552	2252225525	5525525225	2222252255	5555555555	5522555255	5225552525	5225252225	2522555222	121919219180
2225552522	5222555252	2555225522	5252552552	2252252252	5525555225	2222222222	5555522522	5522525552	5225522255	121919219180
2255522525	5522225255	2225522552	5222525525	2555225225	5252552255	2252255555	5525555255	2222252525	5555552225	121919219180
2222552555	5552252522	2255555252	5522225522	2225552552	5222552252	2555255225	5252522222	2252222522	5525525552	121919219180
2555555525	5222222525	2222525255	5552222552	2255525525	5522225225	2225552255	5222555555	2555255255	5252552525	121919219180
121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180	121919219180
22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	

It is based on the 2 by 2 combinations of 31 numbers:

{22222, 22225, 22252, 22255, 22522, 22525, 22552, 22555, 25222, 25225, 25255, 25522, 25525, 25552, 25555, 52222, 52225, 52252, 52255, 52522, 52525, 52552, 52555, 55222, 55225, 55252, 55255, 55522, 55525, 55552, 55555}.

Let's check the sum of these numbers in three situations:

Numbers used:

$$1219180 := 22222 + 22225 + 22252 + 22255 + 22522 + 22525 + 22552 + 22555 + 25222 + 25225 + 25255 + 25522 + 25525 + 25552 + 25555 + 52222 + 52225 + 52252 + 52255 + 52522 + 52525 + 52552 + 52555 + 55222 + 55225 + 55252 + 55255 + 55522 + 55525 + 55552 + 55555$$

Upside-down:

$$1219180 := 22222 + 52222 + 25222 + 55222 + 22522 + 52522 + 25522 + 55522 + 22252 + 52252 + 55252 + 22552 + 52552 + 25552 + 55552 + 22225 + 52225 + 25225 + 55225 + 22525 + 52525 + 25525 + 55525 + 22255 + 52255 + 25255 + 55255 + 22555 + 52555 + 25555 + 55555$$

Mirror looking:

$$1191907 := 55555 + 25555 + 52555 + 22555 + 55255 + 25255 + 52255 + 22255 + 55525 + 25525 + 22525 + 55225 + 25225 + 52225 + 22225 + 55552 + 25552 + 52552 + 22552 + 55252 + 25252 + 52252 + 22252 + 55522 + 25522 + 52522 + 22522 + 55222 + 25222 + 52222 + 22222.$$

Using 2 by 2 combinations of these 29 numbers, the **magic sums** are given by

$$S_{31 \times 31} := 121919219180 = 100000 \times 1219180 + 1219180 \tag{33}$$

and

$$S_{31 \times 31} := 119191891907 = 100000 \times 1191907 + 1191907. \tag{34}$$

The cases of **original magic square** and **upside-down**, the **magic sums** are the same as given in (33). In case of **mirror looking**, the **magic sum** is different, and it is given in (34). Even though the **magic sums** are different but the magic square given in Example 2.25 is a **universal pandiagonal magic square** of order 31.

2.16 Magic Square of Order 32

2.16.1 Blocks of Order 4

Example 2.26. *The block-wise pandiagonal universal magic square of order 32 for the digits 2 and 5 written in digital form is given below in four parts:*

32x32	pan	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432
12444444432	2555252225	5222555555	2222222222	5555525552	2525252225	5252555555	2252222222	5525525552
12444444432	2222255552	5555522222	2555255555	5222552225	2252225552	5525522222	2525255555	5252552225
12444444432	5555555555	2222252225	5222525552	2555222222	5525555555	2252252225	5252525552	2525222222
12444444432	5222522222	2555225552	5555552225	2222255555	5252522222	2525225552	5525552225	2252255555
12444444432	2555252525	5222555255	2222222522	5555525252	2525252525	5252555255	2252222522	5525525252
12444444432	2222225252	5555522522	2555255255	5222552525	2252225252	5525522522	2525255255	5252552525
12444444432	5555555255	2222252525	5222525252	2555222522	5525555255	2252252525	5252525252	2525222522
12444444432	5222522522	2555225252	5555552525	2222255255	5252522522	2525225252	5525552525	2252255255
12444444432	2555552225	5222255555	2222522222	5555225552	2255552225	5522255555	2225522222	5552225552
12444444432	2222525552	5555222222	2555555555	5222252225	2225525552	5552222222	2255555555	5522252225
12444444432	5555255555	2222552225	5222225552	2555522222	5552255555	2225552225	5522225552	2255522222
12444444432	5222222222	2555525552	5555252225	2222555555	5522222222	2255525552	5552252225	2225555555
12444444432	2555552525	5222255255	2222522522	5555225252	2255552525	5522255255	2225522522	5552225252
12444444432	2222525252	5555222522	2555555255	5222252525	2225525252	5552222522	2255555255	5522252525
12444444432	5555255255	2222552525	5222225252	2555522522	5552255255	2225552525	5522225252	2255522522
12444444432	5222222522	2555525252	5555252525	2222555255	5522222522	2255525252	5552252525	2225555255
12444444432	2525552225	5252255555	2225222222	5552525552	2522252225	5255555555	2252522222	5525225552
12444444432	2225225552	5552522222	2525555555	5252252225	2252525552	5525222222	2522255555	5255552225
12444444432	5552555555	2225252225	5252225552	2525522222	5525255555	2252552225	5255525552	2522222222
12444444432	5252222222	2525525552	5552552225	2225255555	5255522222	2522225552	5525252225	2252555555
12444444432	2525552525	5252255255	2225222522	5552525252	2522252525	5255555255	2252522522	5525225252
12444444432	2225225252	5552522522	2525555255	5252252525	2252525252	5525222522	2522255255	5255552525
12444444432	5552555255	2225252525	5252225252	2525522522	5525255255	2252552525	5255525252	2522222522
12444444432	5252222522	2525525252	5552552525	2225255255	5255522522	2522225252	5525252525	2252555255
12444444432	2552552225	5225255555	2255222222	5522525552	2552252225	5225555555	2522522222	5255225552
12444444432	2255225552	5522522222	2552555555	5225252225	2522525552	5255222222	2552255555	5225552225
12444444432	5522555555	2255252225	5225225552	2552522222	5255255555	2522552225	5225525552	2552222222
12444444432	5225222222	2552525552	5522552225	2255255555	5225522222	2552225552	5255252225	2522555555
12444444432	2552552525	5225255255	2255222522	5522525252	2552252525	5225555255	2522522522	5255225252
12444444432	2255225252	5522522522	2552555255	5225252525	2522525252	5255222522	2552255255	5225552525
12444444432	5522555255	2255252525	5225225252	2552522522	5255255255	2522552525	5225525252	2552222522
	5225222522	2552525252	5522552525	2255255255	5225522522	2552225252	5255252525	2522555255
	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8

12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432
2555252222	5222555552	2222222225	5555525555	2525252222	5252555552	2252222225	5525525555
2222225555	5555522225	2555255552	5222552222	2252225555	5525522225	2525255552	5252552222
555555552	2222252222	5222525555	2555222225	552555552	2252252222	5252525555	2525222225
5222522225	2555225555	5555552222	2222255552	5252522225	2525225555	5525552222	2252255552
2555255222	5222555522	2222222255	5555522555	2525255222	5252555522	2252222255	5525522555
2222222555	5555522255	2555255522	5222555222	2252222555	5525522255	2525255522	5252555222
5555555522	2222255222	5222522555	2555222255	5525555522	2252255222	5252522555	2525222255
5222522255	2555222555	5555555222	2222255522	5252522255	2525222555	5525555222	2252255522
2555552222	5222255552	2222522225	5555225555	2255552222	5522255552	2225522225	5552225555
2222525555	5555222225	255555552	5222252222	2225525555	5552222225	225555552	5522252222
5555255552	2222552222	5222225555	2555522225	5552255552	2225552222	5522225555	2255522225
5222222225	2555525555	5555252222	2222555552	5522222225	2255525555	5552252222	2225555552
2555555222	5222255522	2222522255	5555222555	2255555222	5522255522	2225522255	5552222555
2222522555	5555222255	2555555522	5222255222	2225522555	5552222255	2255555522	5522255222
5555255522	2222555222	5222222555	2555522255	5552255522	2225555222	5522222555	2255522255
5222222255	2555522555	5555255222	2222555522	5522222255	2255522555	5552255222	2225555522
2525552222	5252255552	2225222225	5552525555	2522252222	525555552	2252522225	5525225555
2225225555	5552522225	252555552	5252252222	2252525555	5525222225	2522255552	5255552222
5552555552	2225252222	5252225555	2525522225	5525255552	2252552222	5255525555	2522222225
5252222225	2525525555	5552552222	2225255552	5255522225	2522225555	5525252222	2252555552
2525555222	5252255522	2225222255	5552522555	2522255222	5255555522	2252522255	5525222555
2225222555	5552522255	2525555522	5252255222	2252522555	5525222255	2522255522	5255555222
5552555522	2225255222	5252222555	2525522255	5525255522	2252555222	5255522555	2522222255
5252222255	2525522555	5552555222	2225255552	5225522225	2522225555	5525252222	2252555552
2552555222	5225255522	2225222255	5522522555	2552255222	5225555522	2522522255	5255222555
2255222555	5522522255	2552555522	5225255222	2522522555	5255222255	2552255522	5225555222
5522555522	2255255222	5225222555	2552522255	5255255522	2522555222	5225522555	2552222255
5225222225	2552522555	5522555222	2255255552	5225522225	2522225555	5255252222	2522555552
2552555222	5225255522	2225222255	5522522555	2552255222	5225555522	2522522255	5255222555
2255222555	5522522255	2552555522	5225255222	2522522555	5255222255	2552255522	5225555222
5522555522	2255255222	5225222555	2552522255	5255255522	2522555222	5225522555	2552222255
5225222225	2552522555	5522555222	2255255552	5225522225	2522225555	5255252222	2522555552
12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432
9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16

12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432
2555252522	5222555525	2222222252	5555525255	2525252522	5252555525	2252222252	5525525255
2222225255	5555522252	2555255525	5222552522	2252225255	5525522252	2525255525	5252552522
555555525	2222252522	5222525255	2555222252	552555525	2252252522	5252525255	2525222252
5222522252	2555225255	555552522	2222255525	5252522252	2525225255	5525552522	2252255525
2555252555	5222555252	2222222525	5555525222	2525252555	5252555252	2252222525	5525525222
2222225222	5555522525	2555255252	5222552555	2252225222	5525522525	2525255252	5252552555
555555252	2222252555	5222525222	2555222252	5525555252	2252252555	5252525222	2525222252
5222522525	2555225222	555552555	2222255252	5252522525	2525225222	5525552555	2252255252
255552522	5222255525	2222522252	5555225255	225552522	5522255525	2225522252	5552225255
2222525255	5555222252	255555525	5222252522	2225525255	5552222252	225555525	5522252522
5555255525	2222552522	5222225255	2555522252	5552255525	2225552522	5522225255	2255522252
5222222252	2555525255	5555252522	2222555525	5522222252	2255525255	5552252522	2225555525
255552555	5222255252	2222522252	5555225222	225552555	5522255252	2225522252	5552225222
2222525222	5555222252	2555555252	5222252555	2225525222	5552222252	2255555252	5522252555
5555255252	2222525255	5222225222	2525522252	5525255252	2225552555	5255525222	2522222252
5252222252	2525525222	5552552555	2222555252	5255522252	2522225222	5525252555	2252555252
252552522	522255525	2255222252	5522252555	2552225222	522555525	2522252252	5255222252
2255222252	5522252252	255255525	5222525222	2522252555	5255222252	255225525	5225552522
552255525	2255252522	5222225255	2552522252	5255255525	2522252522	5225525255	2552222252
5222222252	2552525255	5522552522	2255255525	5225522252	2552225255	5255252522	2522555525
2552552555	5222525252	2255222252	5522252522	2552225255	5225555252	2522252252	5255222252
2255222252	5522252252	2552555252	5222525255	2522252522	5255222252	2552255252	5225552555
5522555252	2255252555	5222225222	2552522252	5255255252	2522252555	5225525222	2552222252
5222222252	2552525255	5522552522	2255255252	5225522252	2552225222	5255252555	2522555252
12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432
17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24

12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432
2555252252	5222555225	2222222552	5555525525	2525252252	5252555225	2252222552	5525525525	12444444432
2222225525	5555522552	2555255225	5222552252	2252225525	5525522552	2525255225	5252552252	12444444432
5555552252	2222252252	5222525525	2555222552	5525555225	2252252252	5252525525	2525222552	12444444432
5222522552	2555225525	5555552252	2222255225	5252522552	2525225525	5525552252	2252255225	12444444432
2555252255	5222552552	2222225225	5555525522	2525252255	5252552552	2252225225	5525525522	12444444432
2222225522	5555525225	2555252552	5222552255	2252225522	5525525225	2525252552	5252552255	12444444432
5555552552	2222252255	5222525522	2555225225	5525552552	2252252255	5252525522	2525225225	12444444432
5222525225	2555225522	5555552255	2222252552	5252525225	2525225522	5525552255	2252252552	12444444432
2555552252	5222255225	2222522552	5555225525	2255552252	5522255225	2225522552	5552225525	12444444432
2222525525	5555222552	2555555225	5222252252	2225525525	5552222552	2255555225	5522252252	12444444432
5555255225	2222552252	5222225525	2555522552	5552255225	2225552252	5522225525	2255522552	12444444432
5222222552	2555525525	5555252252	2222555225	5522222552	2255525525	5552252252	2225555225	12444444432
2555552255	5222252552	2222525225	5555225522	2255552255	5522252552	2225525225	5552225522	12444444432
2222525522	5555225225	2555552552	5222252255	2225525522	5552225225	2255552552	5522252255	12444444432
5555252552	2222552255	5222225522	2555525225	5552252552	2225552255	5522225522	2255525225	12444444432
5222225225	2555525522	5555252255	2222552552	5522225225	2255525522	5552252255	2225552552	12444444432
2525552252	5252255225	2225222552	5552525525	2522252252	5255555225	2252522552	5525225525	12444444432
2225225525	5552522552	2525555225	5252252252	2252525525	5525222552	2522255225	5255552252	12444444432
5552555225	2225252252	5252225525	2525522552	5525255225	2252552252	5255525525	2522222552	12444444432
5252222552	2525525525	5552552252	2225255225	5255522552	2522225525	5525252252	2252555225	12444444432
2525552255	5252252552	2225225225	5552525522	2522252255	5255552552	2252525225	5525225522	12444444432
2225225522	5552525225	2525552552	5252252255	2252525522	5525225225	2522252552	5255552255	12444444432
5552552552	2225252255	5252225522	2525525225	5525252552	2252552255	5255525522	2522225225	12444444432
5252225225	2525525522	5552552255	2225252552	5255525225	2522225522	5525252255	2252552552	12444444432
2552552252	5225255225	2255222552	5522525525	2552252252	5225555225	2522522552	5255225525	12444444432
2255225525	5522522552	2552555225	5225252252	2522525525	5255222552	2552255225	5225552252	12444444432
5522555225	2255252252	5225225525	2552522552	5255255225	2522552252	5225525525	2552222552	12444444432
5225222552	2552525525	5522552252	2255255225	5225522552	2552225525	5255252252	2522555225	12444444432
2552552255	5225252552	2255225225	5522525522	2552252255	5225552552	2522525225	5255225522	12444444432
2255225522	5522525225	2552552552	5225252255	2522525522	5255225225	2552252552	5225552255	12444444432
5522552552	2255252255	5225225522	2552525225	5255252552	2522552255	5225525522	2552225225	12444444432
5225225225	2552525522	5522552255	2255252552	5225525225	2552225522	5255252255	2522552552	12444444432
12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432	12444444432
25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	

It is based on the 2 by 2 combinations of 32 numbers:

{22222, 22225, 22252, 22255, 22522, 22525, 22552, 22555, 25222, 25225, 25252, 25255, 25522, 25525, 25552, 25555, 52222, 52225, 52252, 52255, 52522, 52525, 52552, 52555, 55222, 55225, 55252, 55255, 55522, 55525, 55552, 55555}.

Let's divide these 28 numbers in 8 parts of 4 each with equal sums.

$$A := 22225 + 25555 + 52222 + 55552 = 155554$$

$$B := 22255 + 22555 + 55222 + 55522 = 155554$$

$$C := 22552 + 25522 + 52255 + 55225 = 155554$$

$$D := 22252 + 25222 + 52555 + 55525 = 155554$$

$$E := 25252 + 25552 + 52225 + 52525 = 155554$$

$$F := 22525 + 25255 + 52522 + 55252 = 155554$$

$$G := 25225 + 25525 + 52252 + 52552 = 155554$$

$$H := 22222 + 22522 + 55255 + 55555 = 155554$$

These 8 groups of 4 each are written in such a way that each group is already **upside-down** in itself. Let's check the sum of each group only for **mirror looking** case:

$$A := 55552 + 52222 + 25555 + 22225 = 155554$$

$$B := 55522 + 55222 + 22555 + 22255 = 155554$$

$$C := 55225 + 52255 + 25522 + 22552 = 155554$$

$$D := 55525 + 52555 + 25222 + 22252 = 155554$$

$$E := 52525 + 52225 + 25552 + 25252 = 155554$$

$$F := 55252 + 52522 + 25255 + 22525 = 155554$$

$$G := 52552 + 52252 + 25525 + 25225 = 155554$$

$$H := 55555 + 55255 + 22522 + 22222 = 155554$$

We observe that in all the three situations the sum remains the same. Using 2 by 2 combinations of these 32 numbers, the magic sum is given by

$$S_{32 \times 32} := 1244433244432 = 1000000 \times 1244432 + 1244432, \tag{35}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} 1244432 := & 22222 + 22225 + 22252 + 22255 + 22522 + 22525 + 22552 + 22555 + \\ & + 25222 + 25225 + 25252 + 25255 + 25522 + 25525 + 25552 + 25555 + \\ & + 52222 + 52225 + 52252 + 52255 + 52522 + 52525 + 52552 + 52555 + \\ & + 55222 + 55225 + 55252 + 55255 + 55522 + 55525 + 55552 + 55555. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we have a **block-wise pandiagonal universal magic square** of order 32 with magic sum given in (35), where each block of order 4 is a **pandigonal universal magic square** with equal **magic sums** given given in (8).

2.16.2 Bimagic Square

Example 2.27. *The universal pandiagonal bimagic square of order 32 for the digits 2 and 5 written in digital form is given below in four parts:*

32x32-bi	pan	1244444444432	1244444444432	1244444444432	1244444444432	1244444444432	1244444444432	1244444444432
	222525552555	555225225222	555222225255	222522552522	222555225252	555255552525	555252552552	222552225225
1244444444432	222555225225	555255552552	555252552525	222552225252	222525552522	555225225255	555222225222	222522552555
1244444444432	222522225222	555222552555	555225552522	222525225255	222552552525	555252225252	555255225225	222555552552
1244444444432	222552552552	555252225225	555255225252	222555552525	222522225255	555222552522	555225552555	222525225222
1244444444432	555222552525	222522225252	222525225225	555225552552	555252225222	222552552555	222555552522	555255225255
1244444444432	555252225255	222525552522	222555552555	555255225222	555222552552	222522225225	222525225252	555225552525
1244444444432	555225225252	222525552525	222522552552	555222225225	555255552555	222555225222	222552225255	555252552522
1244444444432	555255552522	222555225255	222552225222	555252552555	555225225225	222525552552	222522552525	555222225252
1244444444432	222225552555	555525225222	555522225255	222222552522	222255225252	555555552525	555525552552	222252225225
1244444444432	222255225225	555555552552	555525552225	222252225252	222225552222	555525225255	555522225222	222222552555
1244444444432	222222225222	555522552555	555525552222	222225225255	222252552225	555552225252	555555225225	222255552552
1244444444432	222252552552	555552225225	555555225252	222255552225	222222225255	555522552222	555525552555	222225225222
1244444444432	555522552225	222222225252	222225225225	555525552552	555552225222	222252552555	222255552222	555555225255
1244444444432	555552225255	222252552222	222255552555	555555225222	555522552552	222222225225	222252225252	555525552225
1244444444432	555525225252	222225552225	222222552552	555522225225	555555552555	222255225222	222252225255	555552552222
1244444444432	555555552222	222255225255	222252225222	555552552555	555525225225	222225552552	222222552225	555522225252
1244444444432	225525552255	552225225522	552222225555	225522552222	225555225552	552255552225	552252552252	225552225525
1244444444432	225555225525	552255552252	552252552225	225552225552	225525552222	552225225555	552222225522	225522552255
1244444444432	225522225522	552222552255	552225552222	225525225555	225552552225	552252225552	552255225525	225555552252
1244444444432	225552552252	552252225525	552255225552	225555552225	225522225555	552222552222	552225552255	225525225522
1244444444432	552222552225	225522225552	225525225525	552225552252	552252225522	225552552255	225555552222	552255225555
1244444444432	552252225555	225552552222	225555552255	552255225522	552222552252	225522225525	225525225552	552225552225
1244444444432	552225225552	225525552225	225522552252	552222225525	552255552255	225555225522	225552225555	552252552222
1244444444432	552255552222	225555225555	225552225522	552252552255	552225225525	225525552252	225522552225	552222225552
1244444444432	225225555555	552525222222	552522222255	225222555522	225255222252	552555555525	552552555552	225252222225
1244444444432	225255222225	552555555552	552552555525	225252222252	225225555522	552525222255	552522222222	225222555555
1244444444432	225222222222	552522555555	552525555522	225225222255	225252555525	552552222252	552555222225	225255555552
1244444444432	225252555552	552552222225	552555222252	225255555525	225222222255	552522555522	552525555555	225225222222
1244444444432	552522555525	225222222252	225225222225	552525555552	552552222222	225252555555	225255555522	552555222255
1244444444432	552552222255	225252555522	225255555555	552555222222	552522555552	225222222225	225225222252	552525555525
1244444444432	552525222252	225225555525	225222555552	552522222225	552555555555	225255222222	225252222255	552552555522
1244444444432	552555555522	225255222255	225252222222	552552555555	552525222225	225222555552	225222555525	552522222252
	1244444444432	1244444444432	1244444444432	1244444444432	1244444444432	1244444444432	1244444444432	1244444444432
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8

1244444444432	1244444444432	1244444444432	1244444444432	1244444444432	1244444444432	1244444444432	1244444444432
225225552255	552525225522	552522225555	225222552222	225255225552	552555552225	552552552252	225252225525
225255225525	552555552252	552552552225	225252225552	225225552222	552525225555	552522225522	225222552255
225222225522	552522552255	552525552222	225225225555	225252552225	552552225552	552555225525	225255552252
225252552252	552552225525	552555225552	225255552225	225222225555	552522552222	552525552255	225225225522
552522552225	225222225552	225225225525	552525552252	552552225522	225252552255	225255552222	552555225555
552552225555	225252552222	225255552255	552555225522	552522552252	225222225525	225225225552	552525552225
552525225552	225225552225	225222552252	552522225525	552555552255	225255225522	225252225555	552552225522
552555552222	225255225555	225252225522	552552552255	552525225525	225225552252	225222552225	552522225552
225525555555	552225222222	552222222255	225522555522	225555222252	552255555525	552252555552	225552222225
225555222225	552255555552	552252555525	225552222252	225525555522	552225222255	552222222222	225522555555
225522222222	552222555555	552225555522	225525222255	225552555525	552252222252	552255222225	225555555552
225552555552	552252222225	552255222252	225555555525	225522222255	552222555522	552225555555	225525222222
552222555525	225522222252	225525222225	552225555552	552252222222	225552555555	225555555552	552255222255
552252222255	225552555522	225555555555	552255222222	552222555552	225522222225	225525222252	552225555525
552225222252	225525555525	225522555552	552222222225	552255555555	225555222222	225552222255	552252555522
552255555522	225555222255	225552222222	552252555555	552225222225	225525555552	225522555525	552222222252
222225552555	555525225222	555522225255	222222552522	222255225252	555555552525	55552552552	222252225225
222255225225	555555552552	555552552525	222252225252	222222555252	555525225255	555522225222	222222552555
222222225222	555522552555	555525552522	222225225255	222252552525	555552225252	555555225225	222255552552
222252552552	555552225225	555555225252	222255552525	222222225255	555522552522	555525552555	222225225222
555522552525	222222225252	222225225225	555525552552	555552225222	222252552555	222255552522	555555225255
555552225255	222252552522	222255552555	555555225222	555522552552	222222225225	222225225252	555525552525
555525225252	222222555255	222222552552	555522225225	555555552555	222255225222	222252225255	555552552522
555555552522	222255225255	222252225222	555552552555	555525225225	2222225552552	222222552525	555522225252
222525555255	555225222522	555222222555	222522555222	222555222552	555255555225	555252555252	222552222525
222555222525	555255555252	555252555225	222552222552	222525555222	555225222555	555222222522	222522555255
222522222522	555222555255	555225555222	222525222555	222552555225	555252222552	555255222525	222555555252
222552555252	555252222525	555255222552	222555555225	222522222555	555222555222	555225555255	222525222522
555222555225	222522222552	222525222525	555225555252	555252222522	222552555255	222555555222	555255222555
555252222555	222552555222	222555555255	555255222522	555222555252	222522222525	222525222552	555225555225
555225222552	222525555225	222522555252	555222222525	555255555255	222555222522	222552222555	555252555222
555255555222	222555222555	222552222522	555252555255	555225222525	222525555252	222522555225	555222222552
1244444444432	1244444444432	1244444444432	1244444444432	1244444444432	1244444444432	1244444444432	1244444444432
9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16

1244444444432	1244444444432	1244444444432	1244444444432	1244444444432	1244444444432	1244444444432	1244444444432
222225555555	555525222222	555522222255	222225555522	222255222252	555555555525	555552555552	222252222225
222255222225	555555555552	555552555525	222252222252	222225555522	555525222255	555522222222	222225555555
222222222222	555522555555	555525555522	222225222255	222252555525	555552222252	555555222225	222255555552
222252555552	555552222225	555555222252	222255555525	222222222255	555522555522	555525555555	222225222222
555522555525	222222222252	222225222225	555525555552	555552222222	222252555555	222255555522	555555222255
555552222255	222252555522	222255555555	555555222222	555522555552	222222222225	222225222252	555525555525
555525222252	222225555525	222222555552	555522222225	555555555555	222255222222	222252222255	555552555522
555555555522	222255222255	222252222222	555552555555	555525222225	222225555552	222222555525	555522222252
222252555525	555225222522	555222225555	222252255222	222255225552	555255552225	555252552252	2222552225525
222255225525	555255552252	555252552225	222255225552	222252555222	555225225555	555222225522	2222522552255
222252225522	555222552255	555225552222	222252255555	222252555222	555252225552	555255225525	222255552252
222255225522	555252225525	555255225552	222255552225	222252225555	555222552222	555225552255	2222525225522
555222552225	222252225552	222252255225	555225552252	555252225522	222255225525	222255552222	555255225555
555252225555	222255225522	222255552255	555255225522	555222552252	222252225525	222252255552	555225552225
555225225552	222252555222	222252255225	555222225525	555255552255	222255225522	222255225555	555252552222
555255552222	222255522555	222255225522	555252552255	555225225525	222252555222	222252255225	555222225552
225225555255	552252225222	552222225555	225222555222	225225222552	552255555225	552252555252	225222225225
225225222525	552255555252	552255225522	225222225552	225222555222	552252225555	552252222522	2252225552255
225222222522	552252255225	552255552222	225222522555	225225222555	5522552222552	5522555222252	225225555252
225225225522	552255222252	552255552255	225225555225	225222222555	552252255522	5522525555255	2252225222522
552252255225	225222222552	225222522255	552252555252	552255222252	225225225525	225225555222	5522555222555
552255222255	225225225522	225225555255	552255522252	552252255525	225222222525	2252225222552	5522525555225
552252225552	225222555225	225222555252	552252222255	552255555255	225225222252	225222222555	552252555222
552255555222	225225222255	225222222522	552252555255	552252222255	2252225555252	225222555225	5522522222552
225225555255	552222522252	552222225255	225222555252	225225552252	552255552252	552252555252	225222225225
225225552252	552225555255	552225225225	225222225252	225225555252	552222522255	552222222522	2252225552555
225222225222	552222552255	552225552252	225225225255	225225225255	552225222252	552225522225	2252255552552
225225225522	552225222255	552225522252	225225555252	225222222555	552222555252	552225552555	225225225222
552222552252	225222225252	225222522255	552225552552	552225222222	2252225552555	225225555252	5522255222555
552225222255	225225222252	225225555255	552225522222	552222255255	225222225225	225222522252	5522255522525
552222522252	225225555252	225222555252	552222225225	552225555255	225222225222	225222225255	5522255522522
552225555252	225225552255	225222225222	552225225555	552222522225	2252255552552	225222555225	552222225252
1244444444432	1244444444432	1244444444432	1244444444432	1244444444432	1244444444432	1244444444432	1244444444432
17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24

124444444432	124444444432	124444444432	124444444432	124444444432	124444444432	124444444432	124444444432	124444444432
225525555255	552225222522	552222222555	225522555222	225555222552	552255555225	552252555252	225552222525	124444444432
225555222525	552255555252	552252555225	225552222552	225525555222	552225222555	552222222522	225522555255	124444444432
225522222522	552222555255	552225555222	225525222555	225552555225	552252222552	552255222525	225555555252	124444444432
225552555252	552252222525	552255222552	225555555225	225522222555	552222555222	552225555255	225525222522	124444444432
552222555225	225522222552	225525222525	552225555252	552252222522	225552555255	225555555222	552255222555	124444444432
552252222555	225552555222	225555555255	552255222522	552222555252	225522222525	225525222552	552225555225	124444444432
552225222552	225525555225	225522555252	552222222525	552255555255	225555222522	225552222555	552252555222	124444444432
552255555222	225555222555	225552222522	552252555255	552225222522	225525555255	225522555225	552222222552	124444444432
225225555255	552525222522	552522222525	225222552522	225255222525	552555555252	55252552552	225252222525	124444444432
225255222522	552555555252	55252552525	225252222522	225225552522	552525222525	552522222522	225222552555	124444444432
225222222522	552522552555	552525552522	225225222525	225252552525	552552222522	552555222525	22525552552	124444444432
225252552552	552552222525	552555222525	225255552525	225222222525	552522552522	552525552555	225225222522	124444444432
552522552525	225222222522	225225222525	552525552552	552552222522	225252552555	225255552522	552555222525	124444444432
552552222525	225252552522	225255552555	552555222522	552522552552	225222222525	225225222522	552525552525	124444444432
552525222522	225222552525	225225552552	552522222525	552555552555	225255222522	225252222525	552525552522	124444444432
552525222522	225225552525	225222552552	552522222525	552555552555	225255222522	225252222525	552525552522	124444444432
552525222522	225225552525	225222552552	552522222525	552555552555	225255222522	225252222525	552525552522	124444444432
222525555555	555225222222	555222222255	222522555522	222555222252	55525555525	555252555552	222552222225	124444444432
222555222225	555255555552	555252555525	222552222252	222525555522	555225222255	555222222222	222522555555	124444444432
222522222222	555222555555	555225555522	222525222255	222552555525	555252222252	555255222225	222555555552	124444444432
222552555552	555252222225	555255222252	222555555525	222522222255	555222555522	555225555555	222525222222	124444444432
555222555525	222522222252	222525222225	555225555552	555252222222	222552555555	222555555522	555255222255	124444444432
555252222255	222525555522	222555555555	555255222222	555222555552	222522222225	222525222252	555225555525	124444444432
555225222252	222525555525	222522555552	555222222225	555255555555	222555222222	222552222255	555225555522	124444444432
555225222252	222525555525	222522555552	555222222225	555255555555	222555222222	222552222255	555225555522	124444444432
555225222252	222525555525	222522555552	555222222225	555255555555	222555222222	222552222255	555225555522	124444444432
555225222252	222525555525	222522555552	555222222225	555255555555	222555222222	222552222255	555225555522	124444444432
555225222252	222525555525	222522555552	555222222225	555255555555	222555222222	222552222255	555225555522	124444444432
555225222252	222525555525	222522555552	555222222225	555255555555	222555222222	222552222255	555225555522	124444444432
555225222252	222525555525	222522555552	555222222225	555255555555	222555222222	222552222255	555225555522	124444444432
555225222252	222525555525	222522555552	555222222225	555255555555	222555222222	222552222255	555225555522	124444444432
124444444432	124444444432	124444444432	124444444432	124444444432	124444444432	124444444432	124444444432	124444444432
25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	

It is based on the 2 by 2 combinations of 32 numbers of 6-digits given by

{222222, 222225, 222252, 222255, 555522, 555525, 555552, 555555, 222522, 222525, 222552, 222555, 555222, 555225, 555252, 555255, 225222, 225225, 225252, 225255, 552522, 552525, 552552, 552555, 225522, 525522, 255522, 555522, 222255, 522255, 252255, 552255}.

Let's divide the above 32 numbers in four parts with 8 each with equal sums:

$$A := 222222 + 222225 + 222252 + 222255 + 555522 + 555525 + 555552 + 555555 = 3111108$$

$$B := 222522 + 222525 + 222552 + 222555 + 555222 + 555225 + 555252 + 555255 = 3111108$$

$$C := 225222 + 225225 + 225252 + 225255 + 552522 + 552525 + 552552 + 552555 = 3111108$$

$$C := 225522 + 225525 + 225552 + 225555 + 552222 + 552225 + 552252 + 552255 = 3111108$$

Let's see how they become **upside down** and **mirror looking**:

Upside-down:

$$A := 222222 + 522222 + 252222 + 552222 + 225555 + 525555 + 255555 + 555555 = 3111108$$

$$B := 225222 + 525222 + 255222 + 555222 + 222555 + 522555 + 252555 + 552555 = 3111108$$

$$C := 222522 + 522522 + 252522 + 552522 + 225255 + 525255 + 255255 + 555255 = 3111108$$

$$D := 225522 + 525522 + 255522 + 555522 + 222255 + 522255 + 252255 + 552255 = 3111108$$

Mirror looking:

$$A := 555555 + 255555 + 525555 + 225555 + 552222 + 252222 + 522222 + 222222 = 3111108$$

$$B := 552555 + 252555 + 522555 + 222555 + 555222 + 255222 + 525222 + 225222 = 3111108$$

$$C := 555255 + 255255 + 525255 + 225255 + 552522 + 252522 + 522522 + 222522 = 3111108$$

$$E := 552255 + 252255 + 522255 + 222255 + 555522 + 255522 + 525522 + 225522 = 3111108$$

We observe that in all the three situations the sum remains the same. Using 2 by 2 combinations of these 32 numbers, the **magic sum** is given by

$$S_{32 \times 32} := 124444444444432 = 1000000 \times 124444432 + 12444432 \quad (36)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
 12444432 := & 222222 + 222225 + 222252 + 222255 + 555522 + 555525 + 555552 + 555555 + \\
 & + 222522 + 222525 + 222552 + 222555 + 555222 + 555225 + 555252 + 555255 + \\
 & + 225222 + 225225 + 225252 + 225255 + 552522 + 552525 + 552552 + 552555 + \\
 & + 225522 + 525522 + 255522 + 555522 + 222255 + 522255 + 252255 + 552255.
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we have a **block-wise universal square** of order 32 with **magic sum** given in (35). Moreover, it is **bimagic square** of order 32 with **bimagic sum** given by

$$Sb_{32 \times 32} := 5710778900102698433221104. \quad (37)$$

All the blocks of order 8 are also **pandiagonal bimagic squares** with **equal magic sums** as given (19). The **bimagic sums** of order 8 are different in each case.

3 Final Comments

- (i) All the blocks of order 4 are of equal magic sums given in magic squares of orders 20, 24, 28 and 32.
- (ii) All the blocks of order 6 are of equal magic sums given in magic squares of orders 18, 24 and 30.
- (ii) All the blocks of order 8 are of equal magic sums given in magic squares of orders 24 and 32. In case of order 24 the magic square is semi-bimagic, and in case of order, the magic square of order 32 is bimagic.
- (iv) Whole the work is 10-digits distributions of two numbers 2 and 5. There are only three magic squares of orders 24, 25 and 32 are with 12-digits distributions of two numbers 2 and 5. In the first case, i.e., magic square of order 24 it is **semi-bimagic**, while other two of orders 25 and 32, the magic squares are **bimagic squares**. These three magic squares are given in Examples 2.14, 2.16 and 2.27.
- v) In many case the **mirror looking** sums are different from the **original numbers** and **upside-down sum**. This can be brought to same sum by using the numbers with different combinations as given in Examples 2.1, 2.3, 2.6, 2.7, 2.8, 2.9, 2.10, 2.15, 2.16, 2.18, 2.19, 2.22 and 2.25. By considering different combinations, may be we can get the same sum in all the three situations. This shall be studied in near future.

4 Appendix

Let's consider two letters a and b . Below are the combinations of these two letters:

2 – digits : $2^2 := 4$

aa, ab, ba, bb

3 – digits : $2^3 := 8$

$aaa, aab, aba, abb, baa, bab, bba, bbb$

4 – digits : $2^4 := 16$

$aaaa, aaab, aaba, aabb, abaa, abab, abba, abbb, baaa, baab, baba, babb, bbaa, bbab, bbba, bbbb$

5 – digits : $2^5 := 32$

$aaaaa, aaaab, aaaba, aaabb, aabaa, aabab, aabba, aabbb, abaaa, abaab, ababa, ababb, abbaa, abbab, abbba, abbbb, baaaa, baaab, baaba, baabb, babaa, babab, babba, babbb, bbaaa, bbaab, bbaba, bbabb, bbbaa, bbbab, bbbba, bbbbb$

6 – digits : $2^6 := 64$

$aaaaaa, aaaaaab, aaaaaba, aaaaabb, aaabaa, aaabab, aaabba, aaabbb, aabaaa, aababa, aababb, aabbaa, aabbab, aabbba, aabbbb, abaaaa, abaaab, abaaba, abaabb, ababaa, ababab, ababba, ababbb, abbaaa, abbaab, abbaba, abbabb, abbbba, abbbbb, baaaaa, baaaaab, baaaba, baaabb, baabaa, baabab, baabba, baabbb, babaaa, babaab, bababa, bababb, babbaa, babbab, babbba, babbbb, bbaaaa, bbaaab, bbaaba, bbaabb, bbabaa, bbabab, bbabba, bbabbb, bbbaaa, bbbaab, bbbaba, bbbabb, bbbbba, bbbbba, bbbbb$

7 – digits : $2^7 := 128$

$aaaaaaa, aaaaaab, aaaaaba, aaaaabb, aaabaa, aaabab, aaabba, aaabbb, aabaaa, aabaab, aababa, aababb, aaabba, aaabbb, aabaaa, aabaab, aabaaba, aabaabb, aababaa, aababab, aababba, aababbb, aabbaaa, aabbaab, aabbaba,$

*aabbabb, aabbbaa, aabbbab, aabbbaa, aabbbbb, abaaaaa, abaaaab, abaaaba, abaaabb,
abaabaa, abaabab, abaabba, abaabbb, ababaaa, ababaab, abababa, abababb, ababbaa,
ababbab, ababbba, ababbbb, abbaaaa, abbaaab, abbaaba, abbaabb, abbabaa, abbabab,
abbabba, abbabbb, abbbaaa, abbbbaa, abbbaba, abbbabb, abbbbaa, abbbbab, abbbbba,
abbbbb, baaaaaa, baaaaab, baaaaba, baaaabb, baaabaa, baaabab, baaabba, baaabbb,
baabaaa, baabaab, baababa, baababb, baabbaa, baabbab, baabbba, baabbbb, babaaaa,
babaaab, babaaba, babaabb, bababaa, bababab, bababba, bababbb, babbaaa, babbbaab,
babbaba, babbabb, babbbaa, babbbaab, babbbaa, babbbbb, bbaaaaa, bbaaaab, bbaaaba,
bbaaabb, bbaabaa, bbaabab, bbaabba, bbaabbb, bbabaaa, bbabaab, bbababa, bbababb,
bbabbaa, bbabbab, bbabbba, bbabbbb, bbbaaaa, bbbaaab, bbbaaba, bbbaabb, bbbabaa,
bbbabab, bbbabba, bbbabbb, bbbbbaa, bbbbbaab, bbbbaba, bbbbabb, bbbbbaa, bbbbbaab,
bbbbbaa, bbbbbbb*

8 – digits : $2^8 := 256$

*aaaaaaaa, aaaaaaab, aaaaaaba, aaaaaabb, aaaaabaa, aaaaabab, aaaaabba, aaaaabbb,
aaaabaaa, aaaabaab, aaaababa, aaaababb, aaaabbaa, aaaabbab, aaaabbba, aaaabbbb,
aaabaaaa, aaabaaab, aaabaaba, aaabaabb, aaababaa, aaababab, aaababba, aaababbb,
aaabbaaa, aaabbaab, aaabbaba, aaabbabb, aaabbbaa, aaabbbab, aaabbbaa, aaabbbb,
aabaaaaa, aabaaaab, aabaaaba, aabaaabb, aabaabaa, aabaabab, aabaabba, aabaabbb,
aababaaa, aababaab, aabababa, aabababb, aababbaa, aababbab, aababbba, aababbbb,
aabbaaaa, aabbbaab, aabbbaaba, aabbbaabb, aabbabaa, aabbabab, aabbabba, aabbabbb,
aabbbaaa, aabbbaab, aabbbaaba, aabbbaabb, aabbbaa, aabbbaab, aabbbaa, aabbbbb,
abaaaaaa, abaaaaab, abaaaaba, abaaaabb, abaaabaa, abaaabab, abaaabba, abaaabbb,
abaabaaa, abaabaab, abaababa, abaababb, abaabbaa, abaabbab, abaabbba, abaabbbb,
ababaaaa, ababaaab, ababaaba, ababaabb, abababaa, abababab, abababba, abababbb,
ababbaaa, ababbbaab, ababbaba, ababbabb, ababbbaa, ababbbab, ababbbaa, ababbbb,
abbaaaaa, abbaaaab, abbaaaba, abbaaabb, abbaabaa, abbaabab, abbaabba, abbaabbb,
abbabaaa, abbabaab, abbababa, abbababb, abbabbaa, abbabbab, abbabbba, abbabbbb,
abbbaaaa, abbbaaab, abbbaaba, abbbaabb, abbbaaba, abbbaabab, abbbaabba, abbbaabb,*

*abbbbbaaa, abbbbbaab, abbbbbaaba, abbbbbaabb, abbbbbaabaa, abbbbbaabab, abbbbbaabba, abbbbbaabbb,
baaaaaaaa, baaaaaaab, baaaaaaba, baaaaaabb, baaaaabaa, baaaaabab, baaaaabba, baaaaabbb,
baaabaaa, baabaab, baabababa, baabababb, baababbaa, baababbab, baababbaa, baababbbb,
baabaaaa, baabaaab, baabaaba, baabaabb, baababaa, baababab, baababba, baababbb,
baabbaaa, baabbaab, baabbaba, baabbabb, baabbbaa, baabbbab, baabbbba, baabbbbb,
babaaaaa, babaaaab, babaaaba, babaaabb, babaabaa, babaabab, babaabba, babaabbb,
bababaaa, bababaab, babababa, babababb, bababbaa, bababbab, bababbba, bababbbb,
babbaaaa, babbaaab, babbaaba, babbaabb, babbaba, babbabab, babbabba, babbabbb,
babbbaaa, babbbaab, babbbaba, babbbabb, babbbbba, babbbbba, babbbbba, babbbbba,
bbaaaaaa, bbaaaaab, bbaaaaaba, bbaaaaabb, bbaaaabaa, bbaaaabab, bbaaaabba, bbaaaabbb,
bbaabaaa, bbaabaab, bbaababa, bbaababb, bbaabbaa, bbaabbab, bbaabbaa, bbaabbbb,
bbabaaba, bbabaabb, bbababaa, bbababab, bbababba, bbababbb, bbabaaaa, bbabaaab,
bbabbaaa, bbabbaab, bbabbaba, bbabbabb, bbabbbaa, bbabbbab, bbabbbba, bbabbbbba,
bbbaaaaa, bbbaaaab, bbbaaaba, bbbaaabb, bbbabaaa, bbbababab, bbbababba, bbbabbbb,
bbbbaaaa, bbbbbaab, bbbbbaaba, bbbbbaabb, bbbbbaaaa, bbbbbaabab, bbbbbaabba, bbbbbaabbb,
bbbbbaaa, bbbbbaab, bbbbbaaba, bbbbbaabb, bbbbbaaaa, bbbbbaabab, bbbbbaabba, bbbbbaabbb*

8 – digits : $2^9 := 512$

*aaaaaaaaa, aaaaaaaab, aaaaaaaba, aaaaaaabb, aaaaaabaa, aaaaaabab, aaaaaabba,
aaaaaabbb, aaaaabaaa, aaaaabaab, aaaaababa, aaaaababb, aaaaabbaa, aaaaabbab,
aaaaabbba, aaaaabbbb, aaaaabaaa, aaaaabaab, aaaaabaaba, aaaaabaabb, aaaaababaa,
aaaababab, aaaababba, aaaababbb, aaaabbaaa, aaaabbaab, aaaabbaba, aaaabbabb,
aaaabbbaa, aaaabbbab, aaaabbbaa, aaaabbbbba, aaabaaaaa, aaabaaaab, aaabaaaba,
aaabaaabb, aaabaabaa, aaabaabab, aaabaabba, aaabaabbb, aaababaaa, aaababaab,
aaabababa, aaabababb, aaababbaa, aaababbab, aaababbba, aaababbbb, aaabbaaaa,
aaabbaaab, aaabbaaba, aaabbaabb, aaabbabaa, aaabbabab, aaabbabba, aaabbabbb,
aaabbbaaa, aaabbbaab, aaabbbaaba, aaabbbabbb, aaabbbaaa, aaabbbaab, aaabbbaa,
aaabbbbba, aaabbaaaa, aaabbaaab, aaabbaaba, aaabbaabb, aaabbaaba, aaabbaabab,*

*baaabaab, baaabaaba, baaabaabb, baaababaa, baaababab, baaababba, baaababbb,
baaabbaaa, baaabbaab, baaabbaba, baaabbabb, baaabbbaa, baaabbbab, baaabbba,
baaabbbbb, baabaaaa, baabaaaab, baabaaaba, baabaaaab, baabaabaa, baabaabab,
baabaabba, baabaabbb, baababaaa, baababaab, baabababa, baabababb, baababbaa,
baababbab, baababbba, baababbbb, baabbaaaa, baabbaaaab, baabbbaaba, baabbbaabb,
baabbabaa, baabbabab, baabbabba, baabbabbb, baabbbaaa, baabbbaab, baabbbaba,
baabbbab, baabbbaa, baabbbbab, baabbbbbba, baabbbbbb, babaaaaa, babaaaaab,
babaaaaba, babaaaabb, babaaaba, babaaabab, babaaabba, babaaabbb, babaabaaa,
babaabaab, babaababa, babaababb, babaabbaa, babaabbab, babaabbba, babaabbbb,
bababaaa, bababaaab, bababaaba, bababaabb, babababaa, babababab, babababba,
babababb, bababbbaa, bababbaab, bababbaba, bababbabb, bababbbaa, bababbbab,
bababbbbba, bababbbbb, babbaaaaa, babbaaaaab, babbaaaba, babbaaabb, babbaabaa,
babbaabab, babbaabba, babbaabbb, babbabaaa, babbabaab, babbababa, babbababb,
babbabbaa, babbabbab, babbabba, babbabbbb, babbbaaaa, babbbaaaab, babbbbaaba,
babbbbaabb, babbbabaa, babbbabab, babbbabba, babbbabbb, babbbbaaa, babbbbaab,
babbbbaba, babbbbabb, babbbbbaa, babbbbbaab, babbbbbba, babbbbbbb, bbaaaaaa,
bbaaaaaab, bbaaaaaaba, bbaaaaaabb, bbaaaabaa, bbaaaabab, bbaaaabba, bbaaaabbb,
bbaaabaaa, bbaaabaab, bbaaababa, bbaaababb, bbaaabbaa, bbaaabbab, bbaaabba,
bbaaabbbb, bbaabaaaa, bbaabaab, bbaabaaba, bbaabaabb, bbaababaa, bbaababab,
bbaababba, bbaababbb, bbaabbaaa, bbaabbaab, bbaabbaba, bbaabbabb, bbaabbbaa,
bbaabbbab, bbaabbba, bbaabbbbb, bbabaaaa, bbabaaaab, bbabaaaba, bbabaaabb,
bbabaabaa, bbabaabab, bbabaabba, bbabaabbb, bbababaaa, bbababaab, bbabababa,
bbabababb, bbababbaa, bbababbab, bbababbba, bbababbbb, bbabbbaaa, bbabbbaab,
bbabbbaaba, bbabbbaabb, bbabbabaa, bbabbabab, bbabbabba, bbabbabbb, bbabbbaaa,
bbabbbaab, bbabbbaba, bbabbbab, bbabbbaa, bbabbbaab, bbabbbaa, bbabbbbb,
bbbaaaaa, bbbaaaaab, bbbaaaaba, bbbaaaaabb, bbbaaaba, bbbaaabab, bbbaaabba,
bbbaaabbb, bbbaabaaa, bbbaabaab, bbbaababa, bbbaababb, bbbaabbaa, bbbaabbab,
bbbaabbba, bbbaabbbb, bbbabaaa, bbbabaab, bbbabaaba, bbbabaabb, bbbababaa,
bbbababab, bbbababba, bbbababbb, bbbabbbaa, bbbabbaab, bbbabbaba, bbbabbabb,*

*baaababaab, baaabababa, baaabababb, baaababbaa, baaababbab, baaababbba, baaababbbb,
baaabbaaaa, baaabbaaab, baaabbaaba, baaabbaabb, baaabbabaa, baaabbabab, baaabbabba,
baabbabbbb, baaabbbaaa, baaabbbaab, baaabbbaba, baaabbabb, baaabbbaa, baaabbbbab,
baabbbbba, baaabbbbb, baabaaaaaa, baabaaaaab, baabaaaaba, baabaaaabb, baabaaabaa,
baabaaabab, baabaaabba, baabaaabbb, baabaabaaa, baabaabaab, baabaababa, baabaababb,
baabaabbaa, baabaabbab, baabaabbba, baabaabbbb, baababaaaa, baababaaab, baababaaba,
baababaabb, baabababaa, baabababab, baabababba, baabababbb, baababbaaa, baababbaab,
baababbaba, baababbabb, baababbbaa, baababbbab, baababbbaa, baababbbb, baabbaaaaa,
baabbaaaaab, baabbaaaba, baabbaaabb, baabbaabaa, baabbaabab, baabbaabba, baabbaabbb,
baabbabaaa, baabbabaab, baabbababa, baabbababb, baabbabbaa, baabbabbab, baabbabbba,
baabbabbbb, baabbbaaaa, baabbbaaab, baabbbaaba, baabbbaabb, baabbbaba, baabbbabab,
baabbbabba, baabbbabbb, baabbbaaaa, baabbbaaab, baabbbbaba, baabbbbabb, baabbbbbaa,
baabbbbbab, baabbbbbba, baabbbbbbb, babaaaaaa, babaaaaab, babaaaaaba, babaaaaabb,
babaaaabaa, babaaaabab, babaaaabba, babaaaabbb, babaaabaaa, babaaabaab, babaaababa,
babaaababb, babaaabbaa, babaaabbab, babaaabbba, babaaabbbb, babaabaaaa, babaabaab,
babaabaaba, babaabaabb, babaababaa, babaababab, babaababba, babaababbb, babaabbaaa,
babaabbaab, babaabbaba, babaabbabb, babaabbbaa, babaabbbab, babaabbbaa, babaabbbb,
bababaaaaa, bababaaaab, bababaaaba, bababaaabb, bababaabaa, bababaabab, bababaabba,
bababaabbb, babababaaa, babababaab, bababababa, bababababb, babababbaa, babababbab,
babababbba, babababbbb, bababbaaaa, bababbaaab, bababbaba, bababbbaab, bababbbaa,
bababbabab, bababbabba, bababbabbb, bababbbaa, bababbbaab, bababbbaa, bababbbab,
bababbbaa, bababbbab, bababbbaa, bababbbbb, babbaaaaaa, babbaaaaab, babbaaaba,
babbaaaaabb, babbaaaba, babbaaabab, babbaaabba, babbaaabbb, babbaabaaa, babbaabaab,
babbaababa, babbaababb, babbaabbaa, babbaabbab, babbaabbba, babbaabbbb, babbbaaaaa,
babbabaaaab, babbabaaba, babbabaabb, babbababaa, babbababab, babbababba, babbababbb,
babbabbaaa, babbabbaab, babbabbaba, babbabbabb, babbabbbaa, babbabbbab, babbabbba,
babbabbbb, babbbaaaaa, babbbaaaaab, babbbaaaba, babbbaaabb, babbbaabaa, babbbaabab,
babbbaabba, babbbaabbb, babbbabaaa, babbbabaab, babbbababa, babbbababb, babbbabbaa,
babbbabbab, babbbabbaa, babbbabbbb, babbbaaaaa, babbbaaaaab, babbbaaaba, babbbaaabb,*

*babbbbabaa, bbbbbabab, bbbbbabba, bbbbbabbb, bbbbbbaaa, bbbbbbaab, bbbbbbaba,
babbbbabb, bbbbbbbba, bbbbbbbab, bbbbbbbbba, bbbbbbbbbb, bbaaaaaaaaa, bbaaaaaaab,
bbaaaaaaba, bbaaaaaabb, bbaaaaabaa, bbaaaaabab, bbaaaaabba, bbaaaaabbb, bbaaaabaaa,
bbaaaabaab, bbaaaababa, bbaaaababb, bbaaaabbaa, bbaaaabbab, bbaaaabbba, bbaaaabbbb,
bbaaabaaaa, bbaaabaaab, bbaabaaba, bbaabaabb, bbaaababaa, bbaaababab, bbaaababba,
bbaaababbb, bbaaabbaaa, bbaaabbaab, bbaaabbaba, bbaaabbabb, bbaaabbbba, bbaaabbbab,
bbaaabbbbba, bbaaabbbbb, bbaabaaaa, bbaabaaaab, bbaabaaaba, bbaabaaabb, bbaabaabaa,
bbaabaabab, bbaabaabba, bbaabaabbb, bbaababaaa, bbaababaab, bbaabababa, bbaabababb,
bbaababbaa, bbaababbab, bbaababbba, bbaababbbb, bbaabbaaaa, bbaabbaaab, bbaabbaaba,
bbaabbaabb, bbaabbabaa, bbaabbabab, bbaabbabba, bbaabbabbb, bbaabbbaaa, bbaabbbaab,
bbaabbbaba, bbaabbbabb, bbaabbbbba, bbaabbbbab, bbaabbbbbba, bbaabbbbbb, bbabaaaaaa,
bbabaaaaab, bbabaaaaba, bbabaaaabb, bbabaaabaa, bbabaaabab, bbabaaabba, bbabaaabbb,
bbabaabaaa, bbabaabaab, bbabaababa, bbabaababb, bbabaabbaa, bbabaabbab, bbabaabbba,
bbabaabbbb, bbababaaaa, bbababaaab, bbababaaba, bbababaabb, bbabababaa, bbabababab,
bbabababba, bbabababbb, bbababbaaa, bbababbaab, bbababbaba, bbababbabb, bbababbbaa,
bbababbbab, bbababbba, bbababbbb, bbabbaaaa, bbabbaaaab, bbabbaaaba, bbabbaaabb,
bbabbabaaa, bbabbabab, bbabbabba, bbabbabbb, bbabbabaaa, bbabbabaab, bbabbababa,
bbabbababb, bbabbabba, bbabbabbab, bbabbabbba, bbabbabbbb, bbabbbaaaa, bbabbbaaab,
bbabbbaaba, bbabbbaabb, bbabbbaba, bbabbbabab, bbabbbabba, bbabbbabbb, bbabbbbaaa,
bbabbbbbaab, bbabbbbaba, bbabbbbabb, bbabbbbbba, bbabbbbbba, bbabbbbbbbb, bbaaaaaaaaa,
bbbaaaaaab, bbbaaaaaba, bbbaaaaabb, bbbaaaabaa, bbbaaaaabab, bbbaaaaabba,
bbbaaaaabb, bbbaaabaaa, bbbaaabaab, bbbaaababa, bbbaaababb, bbbaaabbaa, bbbaaabbab,
bbbaaabba, bbbaaabbbb, bbbaabaaaa, bbbaabaaab, bbbaabaaba, bbbaabaabb, bbbaababaa,
bbbaababab, bbbaababba, bbbaababbb, bbbaabbaaa, bbbaabbaab, bbbaabbaba, bbbaabbabb,
bbbaabbbaa, bbbaabbbab, bbbaabbba, bbbaabbbb, bbbaaaaaaa, bbbaaaaaab, bbbaaaaaba,
bbbaaaaabb, bbbaabaaba, bbbaaabab, bbbaaabba, bbbaaabbb, bbbaababaa, bbbaababaab,
bbbaabababa, bbbaabababb, bbbaababba, bbbaabbab, bbbaabbba, bbbaabbbb, bbbaabbaaa,
bbbaabbaab, bbbaabbaaba, bbbaabbaabb, bbbaabbabaa, bbbaabbabab, bbbaabbabba, bbbaabbabb,
bbbaabbbaa, bbbaabbbaab, bbbaabbba, bbbaabbbabb, bbbaabbbbba, bbbaabbbbb, bbbaabbbbba,*

*bbbabbbbbb, bbbbaaaaaa, bbbbaaaaab, bbbbaaaaba, bbbbaaaabb, bbbbaaaba, bbbbaaabab,
bbbbaaabba, bbbbaaabbb, bbbbaabaaa, bbbbaabaab, bbbbaababa, bbbbaababb, bbbbaabbaa,
bbbbaabbab, bbbbaabbba, bbbbaabbbb, bbbbabaaaa, bbbbabaaab, bbbbababa, bbbbababb,
bbbbaabaaa, bbbbababab, bbbbababba, bbbbababbb, bbbbabbaaa, bbbbabbaab, bbbbabbaba,
bbbbaabbab, bbbbaabbba, bbbbaabbbb, bbbbabbbba, bbbbabbbbb, bbbbaaaaaa, bbbbaaaaab,
bbbbaaaba, bbbbaaabb, bbbbaaaba, bbbbaaabab, bbbbaaabba, bbbbaaabbb, bbbbaabaaa,
bbbbaabaab, bbbbaababa, bbbbaababb, bbbbaabbaa, bbbbaabbab, bbbbaabbba, bbbbaabbbb,
bbbbaaaaaa, bbbbaaaaab, bbbbaaaba, bbbbaaabb, bbbbaabaaa, bbbbaabab, bbbbaabba,
bbbbaabbb, bbbbaabaaa, bbbbaabaab, bbbbaababa, bbbbaabbab, bbbbaabbba, bbbbaabbbb,
bbbbaaaaaa, bbbbaaaaab, bbbbaaaba, bbbbaaabb, bbbbaabaaa, bbbbaabab, bbbbaabba,
bbbbaabbb, bbbbaabaaa, bbbbaabaab, bbbbaababa, bbbbaabbab, bbbbaabbba, bbbbaabbbb,
bbbbaabbba, bbbbaabbbb*

5 Author's Contributions to Magic Squares

The **item-wise** author's work on magic squares is as follows:

- i. Digital Numbers Magic Squares - [5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 37];*
- ii. Block-Wise Construction of Bimagic Squares - [11];*
- iii. Connections with Genetic Tables and Shannon's entropy - [12];*
- iv. Selfie and Palindromic-type Magic Squares - [13, 28, 37];*
- v. Intervally Distributed and Block-Wise Magic Squares - [14, 15, 16, 28];*
- vi. Multi-digits and Number Patterns Magic Squares - [17, 27];*
- vii. Perfect Square Sum Magic Squares with Uniformity, Minimum Sum and Pythagorean Triples - [18, 19];*
- viii. Block-Wise Constructions of Magic and Bimagic Squares - [20, 21, 22, 23, 26, 29, 31];*
- ix. Magic Crosses: Repeated and Non Repeated Entries - [24];*
- x. Representations of Letters and Numbers With Equal Sums Magic Squares of Orders 4 and 6 - [25].*
- xi. Bordered Magic Squares - [32, 33, 34, 35, 36].*
- xii. 2-Digits Magic and Bimagic Squares - [38].*

References

- [1] **ALEX BELLOS**, Can you solve it? Toot toot for world palindrome day!,
<https://www.theguardian.com/science/2020/jan/27/can-you-solve-it-toot-toot-for-world-palindrome-day>, Jan. 27, 2020.
- [2] **AALE DE WINKEL**, The Magic Encyclopedia, <http://magichypercubes.com/Encyclopedia/>
- [3] **H. WHITE**, Magic Squares - <http://budshaw.ca/SODLS.html>
- [4] **H. WHITE**, Magic Squares - <http://budshaw.ca/BlockSquares.html>
- [5] **I.J. TANEJA**, Digital Era: Magic Squares and 8th May 2010 (08.05.2010), May, 2010, pp. 1-4,
<https://arxiv.org/abs/1005.1384>.
- [6] **I.J. TANEJA**, Universal Bimagic Squares and the day 10th October 2010 (10.10.10), Oct, 2010, pp. 1-5,
<https://arxiv.org/abs/1010.2083>.
- [7] **I.J. TANEJA**, DIGITAL ERA: Universal Bimagic Squares, Oct, 2010, pp. 1-8, <https://arxiv.org/abs/1010.2541>.
- [8] **I.J. TANEJA**, Upside Down Numerical Equation, Bimagic Squares, and the day September 11, Oct. 2010, pp. 1-7, <https://arxiv.org/abs/1010.4186>.
- [9] **I.J. TANEJA**, Equivalent Versions of "Khajuraho" and "Lo-Shu" Magic Squares and the day 1st October 2010 (01.10.2010), Nov. 2010, pp. 1-7, <https://arxiv.org/abs/1011.0451>.
- [10] **I.J. TANEJA**, Upside Down Magic, Bimagic, Palindromic Squares and Pythagoras Theorem on a Palindromic Day - 11.02.2011, Feb. 2011, pp.1-9, <https://arxiv.org/abs/1102.2394>.
- [11] **I.J. TANEJA**, Bimagic Squares of Bimagic Squares and an Open Problem, Feb. 2011, pp. 1-14,
<https://arxiv.org/abs/1102.3052>.
- [12] **I.J. TANEJA**, Representations of Genetic Tables, Bimagic Squares, Hamming Distances and Shannon Entropy, Jun. 2012, pp. 1-19, <https://arxiv.org/abs/1206.2220>.
- [13] **I.J. TANEJA**, Selfie Palindromic Magic Squares, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **18**(2015), Art. 98, pp. 1-15. <http://rgmia.org/papers/v18/v18a98.pdf>.

- [14] I.J. TANEJA, Intervally Distributed, Palindromic, Selfie Magic Squares, and Double Colored Patterns, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **18**(2015), Art. 127, pp. 1-45. <http://rgmia.org/papers/v18/v18a127.pdf>.
- [15] I.J. TANEJA, Intervally Distributed, Palindromic and Selfie Magic Squares: Genetic Table and Colored Pattern – Orders 11 to 20, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **18**(2015), Art. 140, pp. 1-43. <http://rgmia.org/papers/v18/v18a140.pdf>.
- [16] I.J. TANEJA, Intervally Distributed, Palindromic and Selfie Magic Squares – Orders 21 to 25 , **18**(2015), Art. 151, pp. 1-33. <http://rgmia.org/papers/v18/v18a151.pdf>.
- [17] I.J. TANEJA, Multi-Digits Magic Squares, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **18**(2015), Art. 159, pp. 1-22. <http://rgmia.org/papers/v18/v18a159.pdf>.
- [18] I.J. TANEJA, Magic Squares with Perfect Square Number Sums, Research Report Collection, **20**(2017), Article 11, pp. 1-24, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a11.pdf>.
- [19] I.J. TANEJA, Pythagorean Triples and Perfect Square Sum Magic Squares, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **20**(2017), Art. 128, pp. 1-22, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a128.pdf>.
- [20] I.J. TANEJA, Block-Wise Equal Sums Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order $4k$, **Zenodo**, January 31, 2019, pp. 1-17, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554288>.
- [21] I.J. TANEJA, Block-Wise Equal Sums Magic Squares of Orders $3k$ and $6k$, , **Zenodo**, Febuary 01, 2019, pp. 1-55 <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554895>.
- [22] I.J. TANEJA, Block-Wise Unequal Sums Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, Febuary 01, 2019, pp. 1-55 <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555260>.
- [23] I.J. TANEJA, Magic Rectangles in Construction of Block-Wise Pandiagonal Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, January 31, 2019, pp. 1-49 , <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554520>.
- [24] I.J. TANEJA, Magic Crosses: Repeated and Non Repeated Entries, **Zenodo**, Febuary 01, 2019, pp. 1-37, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554623>.
- [25] I.J. TANEJA, Representations of Letters and Numbers With Equal Sums Magic Squares of Orders 4 and 6, **Zenodo**, Febuary 01, 2019, pp. 1-82, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555287>.
- [26] I.J. TANEJA, Block-Wise Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 12 to 36, **Zenodo**, Febuary 01, 2019, pp.

- 1-53, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555343>. Also in <https://inderjtaneja.com/2018/01/10/block-wise-magic-and-bimagic-squares-part-i/> and <https://inderjtaneja.com/2018/01/10/block-wise-magic-and-bimagic-squares-part-ii/>.
- [27] I.J. TANEJA, Different Digits Magic Squares and Number Patterns, **Zenodo**, February 01, 2019, pp. 1-34, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555327>.
- [28] I.J. TANEJA, Palindromic, Patterned Magic Sums, Composite, and Colored Patterns in Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, February 02, 2019, pp. 1-99, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555741>.
- [29] I.J. TANEJA, Block-Wise Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 39 to 45, **Zenodo**, February 01, 2019, pp. 1-73, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555889>. Also in <https://inderjtaneja.com/2018/03/02/block-wise-construction-of-magic-and-bimagic-squares-of-orders-39-to-45/>.
- [30] I.J. TANEJA, Perfect Square Sum Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, April 29, 2019, pp. 1-65, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2653927>.
- [31] I.J. TANEJA, Block-Wise Constructions of Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 8 to 108, May 15, 2019, pp. 1-43, **Zenodo**, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2843326>.
- [32] I.J. TANEJA, Nested Magic Squares With Perfect Square Sums, Pythagorean Triples, and Borders Differences, **Zenodo**, June 14, 2019, pp. 1-59, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3246586>.
- [33] I.J. TANEJA, Symmetric Properties of Nested Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, June 29, 2019, pp. 1-55, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3262170>.
- [34] I.J. TANEJA, General Sum Symmetric and Positive Entries Nested Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, July 04, 2019, pp. 1-55, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3268877>.
- [35] I.J. TANEJA, Fractional and Decimal Type Bordered Magic Squares With Magic Sum 2020. **Zenodo**, January 20, 2020, pp.1-25, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3613698>.
- [36] I.J. TANEJA, Bordered Magic Squares With Order Square Magic Sums, **Zenodo**, January 20, 2020, pp. 1-26, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3613690>.
- [37] I.J. TANEJA, Universal Palindromic Day and Two Digits Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, February 2, pp. 1-22, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3633852>.

- [38] **I.J. TANEJA**, 2-Digits Universal and Upside-Down Palindromic Magic and Bimagic Squares: Orders 3 to 16, **Zenodo**, April 07, 2020, pp. 1-103, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3743362>.
- [39] **I.J. TANEJA**, Universal Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 17 to 32 With Digits 1 and 8, **Zenodo**, May 30, 2020, pp. 1-103, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3866366>.
- [40] **I.J. TANEJA**, Upside-down Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 17 to 32 With Digits 6 and 9, **Zenodo**, May 30, 2020, pp. 1-98, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3866396>.
-